

SEREP

SOUTHEAST EQUINE RESEARCH & EDUCATION PARTNERSHIP

A white horse stands on a wooden barrel in a grassy field. In the background, there is a large building, trees, and a group of people. The scene is set in a rural or farm environment.

**Honoring the Past –
Envisioning the Future**

Full Report: The Southeast Equine
Community & Research Center

The Southeast Equine Research and Education Partnership: Honoring the Past – Envisioning the Future

Full Report - June 2017

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The Southeast Equine Research and Education Partnership: Honoring the Past – Envisioning the Future

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Foreword

by **Walter H. Dalton**

President, Isothermal Community College

January 2019

Polk County, NC has a rich and dignified history in the equestrian sport dating before its serving as the training ground for the 1956 Olympic Equestrian Team. Venues such as Harmon Field and FENCE have hosted thousands of equestrian competitions in the disciplines of dressage, cross country, show jumping and others. The Block House Steeplechase has been a mainstay of equestrian culture in Polk County for many years and many equestrian farms and businesses dot the landscape of Polk, Rutherford, and surrounding counties in two states.

In 2015, the profile of the equestrian sport was magnified in the area with the advent of Tryon International Equestrian Center (TIEC), an international venue attracting international talent. Some questioned what would happen to existing venues and what would this mean to the amount and nature of growth in Polk County and surrounding areas.¹

The innovative minds of Polk Countian began to engage. Craig Hilton, a citizen of Polk, opined that TIEC was to equestrian as BMW is to automotive. He observed that Clemson University had created ICARS (Clemson University Center for Automotive Research) in the Greenville-Spartanburg area to conduct comprehensive automotive research and to leverage the presence and reputation of BMW and Michelin. With ICARS only 35 miles away, why couldn't our area propose a comparable research center in equine and animal science?

Bill Miller, former Polk County Superintendent of schools, discussed with an Isothermal Community College (ICC) official his concern for existing venues like Foothills Equine and Nature Center (FENCE) and Harmon Field and questioned their long term viability given the impact of TIEC and its growth in activity and facilities. It was suggested that perhaps part of FENCE could be made into an educational campus. These discussions morphed into the idea that perhaps a multidisciplinary facility could be developed, similar to ICARS or the Kannapolis NC Food Research Center, wherein multiple universities would engage in research in collaboration with private researchers from major companies and with Isothermal Community College having a presence to train in technical fields and assist with the operation of the facility and its ongoing activity.

¹ In 2018, the Tryon International Equestrian Center (TIEC) hosted the World Equestrian Games (WEG) which was attended by seventy countries. TIEC is consistently attracting international traffic and the increased activity has grown the equestrian activity in the area. TIEC and the Foothills Equestrian and Nature Center (FENCE), and Green Creek Farm (proposed venues for the SEREP) are 80 miles from Clemson University, 140 miles from the University of Georgia, and 150 miles from the University of Tennessee. These institutions and iv more have animal science programs which may be potential partners.

Libbie Johnson, a leader in Polk County and the Equestrian Community, was supportive and encouraging of the idea, as were others, as long as it was compatible and aesthetically pleasing with the bucolic nature of Polk. It was emphasized by all that it should complement, and not compete with, existing businesses. These discussions and more led to Isothermal seeking a grant to study such a research center and to hypothesize how such a center would look; how it would interface and coordinate with existing facilities; and how it might attract researchers and academics to the area. At the same time, such a center should act as a catalyst for students of Polk, Rutherford and the surrounding area to further their education and stay in the area to add to their own quality of life and that of the community.

With that backdrop, ARC graciously and generously gave Isothermal a grant to engage in such a study and Isothermal in accordance with its proposal in the grant application, contracted with NC State to do the study. The contract hypothesizes that the SEREP would have as its primary focus equine research at the university level using a multiple university/collaborative model and also, a component of technical training to be conducted by ICC which would be complementary to the research facilities and the equine economy and related industries in the area. The contract defined a scope of work and established guidelines for the study.

The study would culminate in conceptual drawings and identify, in general terms, financial resources as well as any public/private partnerships which might be formed to take advantage of the SEREP. During the course of the study, it was suggested that such a project be proposed in stages in five year increments over a twenty-year period of time in order to assure all efforts were to scale and sustainable into the future with each phase building upon the other. What follows is the final product from NC State, but not the final work of the committee, which was formed to assist with the grant.

The Committee plans to continue its work to refine proposals and adapt the suggestions of NC State to the original vision and its evolution as dictated by changing circumstances. In the meantime, Isothermal Community College is proceeding with the development of a curriculum in equine studies for an associate of science degree and articulation agreements with four year colleges and universities. Also, Isothermal is proposing a new human services therapy degree based on the horse as a service animal. Physical facilities such as a barn, therapeutic riding ring, and other ancillary facilities are being built, or are proposed to be built, on ICC's main campus. This can fill a void and initiate the process during this deliberative period.

The work of Isothermal in initiating these programs is a step toward the ultimate vision. Time and success, or lack thereof, will dictate whether the scale of the process will be sufficient to support the vision and the timeline for implementation.

These are things the committee will continue to address, assimilating the information derived from the study with its own knowledge and investigation.

Executive Summary

NC State SEREP Research Team
February 2019

The Southeast Equine Research and Education Partnership (SEREP) and eponymous research study arose from a grant received by Isothermal Community College (ICC) from the Appalachian Regional Commission (ARC). ICC engaged North Carolina State University (NC State) to conduct the study because of its expertise in equine education, animal and plant sciences, extension and community engagement among other disciplinary areas. SEREP was one of three community-university engagement initiatives in the state designed to take advantage of the comprehensive academic and research assets of the institution.

An interdisciplinary research team from NC State was formed to pursue the scope of work outlined in the contract. Over a period of two years, the team engaged with a number of individual, community, and organizational stakeholders in Rutherford and Polk counties, collected a variety quantitative and qualitative data to determine the feasibility of developing an equine research and education center, and developed a model that would take advantage of the long standing but burgeoning equestrian culture and economy in the Isothermal region of Western North Carolina. The resulting model captures the needs of existing communities, attract investment, create new businesses and jobs, and stimulate university-level research opportunities.

Honoring The Past – Summary of Report #1

The July 2017 progress report shared our preliminary findings in each of the areas outlined below. The contents represented knowledge derived through conversations with local community members and stakeholder groups, key equine-connected organizations and businesses, and NC State University faculty and administrators.

Time, Place, and Identity

- The Isothermal Region in the foothills of Western North Carolina has a long and rich history of equestrian economic, social and cultural activity. Primarily centered in Polk County, the equine economy extends eastward through Rutherford county, northwest to Buncombe County, and across the southern border of the state as far Greenville South Carolina. Notably, multiple economic analyses over the past few years have pointed to the strengths and assets of the Isothermal Region, as well as the challenges and opportunities for growth. In addition, the equine industry has deep roots in North Carolina as represented by a total economic impact to the state in 2009 of \$1.9 billion and 19,183 jobs (The Rural Center, 2009).

Case Studies of Equine Research and Education centers around the country

- Many universities have developed their equine centers close to their main campus, except for situations in which the centers could be located in a region that affords access to opportunities specific to a region.
- Centers are funded from a variety of sources, including tuition from academic programs, revenues from rental of facilities for events, fees of boarding research herds used in extramurally funded studies, as well as donations by donors and appropriation of public funds.
- The funding of new centers is usually associated with the political influence and/or philanthropic support of high-profile alumni and community members.
- Horse ownership and interest in equine sports and events help foster relationships with key supporters.

Potential Research and Education Activities for the EREC:

- Pasture management; to include activities like hay production research, pasture erosion prevention, rotational grazing patterns, waste management research, forest canopy and pasture edge relationship, sustainable best management practices.
- Equine health sciences; to include equine vet-tech training facilities, hay and pasture sample testing lab, equine nutrition research, equine quarantine research, equine rehabilitation research and training.
- Community engagement, to include therapeutic riding research, event hosting, community educational programming, equine and pedestrian trail stewardship, interinstitutional equine training and education programs.

Preliminary Geo-Spatial Analysis of Potential Physical Sites for an EREC

- Understanding that selecting a site will continue to remain an ongoing process, our preliminary site analysis has revealed that the Green Creek site followed by FENCE and the Henson Rd./ U.S. Hwy 221 site have the most ideal environmental conditions out of the five sites that were investigated earlier in the report. However, there are other non-environmental factors that must be accounted for in the next stage of this study, including potential partnerships, funding, program fit, potential for expansion beyond site boundaries, and community/stakeholder input. The information provided in this report is therefore preliminary and represents the initial phase of the site identification and selection process. Once the research and education activities are identified, it will be possible to evaluate how each site will be able to support those activities and the required spaces they demand. This will enable us to further identify the ideal site features and design the future EREC site.

Identifying Opportunities – Summary of Report #2

Community Engagement

Listening to the multiple voices in communities across the region has allowed us to gain an understanding of the assets, opportunities, and challenges that will play a role in a future *Equine Education and Research Center* (EREC). Overall, we learned that:

- The geographical location and conditions, deep roots in the equine tradition, and a network of supporting institutions are key assets that many believe can be leveraged for economic growth and job creation.
- The existing equine economy is seen as stable and broad throughout most of the region although many also believe that the prospects for large-scale economic growth resulting from the sector is limited. Relatedly, given that the equine culture in the two-county area lies more heavily in Polk rather than Rutherford, attracting people potential workers from the latter, more populous county, has proved to be a challenge. Notably, Isothermal Community College continues to its certificate and degree programs and has recently received funding to expand its physical plant to meet those educational needs.
- The region enjoys a core set of citizens and organizations, both horse lovers and non-equestrians, that care deeply about the area and support the equine industry and the benefits it brings. This civically engaged group may not always be obvious among the many stakeholders but nevertheless forms the foundation of what makes the area attractive to potential investors, and, can be mobilized to create new opportunities, including a potential EREC.
- While many community members appreciate and support the opportunities for growth in the area resulting from the presence of the Tryon International Equestrian Center, those views are accompanied by equally strong views that those opportunities must be balanced with the desire to maintain and enrich the character of the community, particularly the equine culture, and, the importance of creating opportunities that provide living wage jobs both within and outside the equine sector.
- The number of stakeholder institutions span both the government and private sectors, and, from our vantage point, are mostly anxious and willing to collaborate on bringing opportunity and investment to the area. This too is a plus for moving strategically towards an EREC.

While North Carolina State University is unlikely to invest in a high-end medical and research facility, A **One Health** research and education model, perhaps organized around the equine economy, holds great promise that we will continue to explore. In particular, a center that builds the capacity for equine assisted research and therapy has the potential for attracting national as well as international attention. Moreover, the prospect for an interdisciplinary research and education center may also be a more viable solution. Over the next couple of months, in addition to meeting with administrators and faculty in the more obvious areas of Animal Science and Veterinary Medicine, we will explore connections with faculty across all colleges of NC State University.

Feasibility Study

Regarding specific business activities:

- Breeding Services and Equine Appraisal and insurance stand out as the activities with the least attractiveness and human capital availability.
- Home and Barn Construction emerged as the most advantageous activity with relatively high local human capital.
- Hotels, Inns and B&Bs, as well as restaurants, bars and cafes were perceived as very advantageous but with need for improved human capital through education and training.
- Real estate is perceived as a business activity involving a capable few but it was perceived to bring modest benefits to the local community.

- An examination of equine and non-equine education and research centers operating in the US and internationally revealed that these units were usually characterized as:
- Equine research centers integral to land grant universities, located close to a main campus and rely primarily on research funding and donations.
- Equine R&D centers owned and operated by industry focused on conducting research that is best kept away from the public view, and Engaged research and learning centers operated by universities and characterized by a great deal of involvement with local stakeholders and industry peers.
- Each type of center demands specific financial models relying on a combination of public fund appropriation, philanthropy of a donor network, research administration fees, and hosting of recreational and educational visitors.

Overall, these findings suggest that the long-term feasibility of a prospect research and education center would likely need to be based on:

- Initial sizeable investment of local and state funds for land acquisition and building;
- Academic institution investment of initial staff and subsidization of initial programming and administration;
- Donor support coordinated by a “friends of” group integrating the primary academic institution and possibly high-level local equine groups;
- Research administration fees from active research programs complementary to research conducted in the parent academic campus(es);
- Lodging, food and activity revenues earned from hosting Extension, engaged learning, and tourists/visitors.

Design Analysis

The key planning principles guiding the future EREC complex include:

- Identifying potential locations and sites with essential landscape characteristics in place.
- Achieving quality facilities on the site that will reflect the EREC’s vision and its research and educational activities.
- Prioritizing sustainability that will minimize energy use and emissions, supporting sustainable land management for research, teaching, farming, natural areas, and other uses; and ensuring that land, facilities and activities work together to maximize knowledge transfer and positively impact local equine economy.
- Developing and promoting healthy environment, which may also represent **One Health** mission in support of well-being of researchers, faculty, students, visitors, staff, and horses.

Site Identification and Analysis Process

- Easy access to state highway, proximity to local equine suppliers, proximity to population centers, availability of water source, cost of land, adequate size of land (min. 100 acres), relatively flat land, existence of wooded areas onsite, proximity to existing equine activities, and proximity to other equestrian and agricultural lands, existence of infrastructure in place, and good quality of soils are considered as important factors for the future location of the EREC complex.

- The SWOT analysis revealed that the FENCE followed by the Green Creek and the Henson Rd./U.S. Hwy 221 sites have the most ideal environmental and contextual conditions out of the five sites that were identified and evaluated.

Preferences

One of the primary driving planning and design principles of the future EREC complex includes but not limited to:

- Creating a strong image through site layout and its facilities' architectural characteristics that will also be a good fit to the region's character.
- There is a strong desire for having the rustic style and timber/wood buildings on the site that will be surrounded with pastures including substantial tree presence.
- Centralized facilities with larger building masses located away from the roadside are preferred.
- The future site should have appropriate amount of natural vegetation with more pasture/open spaces around the facilities.

Imagining the Future – Summary of Report #3

The third and final report provided a conceptual framework for a comprehensive research and community center focused on horse, human, and environmental health. The proposed ***Southeast Equine Community and Research Center*** would accommodate the equine related education and research needs of local horse owners and farms, small businesses, and private and non-profit industry. We have provided conceptual and business models, as well as physical design scenarios, that outline a community oriented, economically viable, and environmentally sustainable center for research and education in the area. The center would increase local capacity and provide synergy to the ongoing initiatives by ICC to provide training and other educational opportunities aimed at building the equine workforce. And finally, in the areas of equine-related research, the center would provide an opportunity to leverage the strengths of NC State University in the agricultural, animal, natural, social, and veterinary sciences.

Our research determined that one of the more promising areas of equine-related research, and one for which there are few other centers in the United States, is in equine assisted activities (e.g. riding, learning, psychotherapy). In addition, the agricultural and technology needs of the local areas as well as the state of North Carolina would be well-served by research in the production of premium horse hay and other forages, manure and pasture management, and the development of a variety of agribusiness opportunities. Finally, a center would build on the increased equestrian-related visitors to the region and provide spaces for incubating small businesses and educating local communities and tourists on all aspects of the historical and present-day relationship between horses and humans.

Economic and community development in rural areas is always challenging but has long been central to the land grant mission of NC State University. We have been inspired by many in the Isothermal region who have long believed that the horse culture and economy there has been underappreciated. Our research affirms this view and provides one pathway for furthering the

economic, cultural, and community development that will over time not only benefit the local area, but the entire state of North Carolina and beyond. More immediately, we are confident this report can contribute to the next steps in growing the equine culture and economy in Western North Carolina.

Introduction and Overview

The successful implementation of the future Southeast Equine Community and Research Center and its mission requires a strong and sustainable vision, partnerships, research & educational focus, and physical environment that effectively support and address the equine related needs in the region.

The Southeast Equine Research and Education Partnership (SEREP) extends from a contract between North Carolina State University (NC State) and Isothermal Community College via a grant the latter received from the Appalachian Regional Commission. In 2016, the office of University Outreach and Engagement at NC State began a community-university partnership initiative in Polk and Rutherford counties to identify opportunities for the university to engage in intentional and collaborative projects that would significantly address community identified needs. Although a number of economic analyses and reports pointed to economic development opportunities in the region related to agriculture, tourism, and industrial activity (NC Isothermal Region C, 2017; Region C Workforce Development Board, 2016), for a number of reasons, many in these two local communities believed there were opportunities to be explored that could take advantage of the equestrian assets in the region. Moreover, given the economic contribution of the horse industry to the economy of North Carolina, which includes \$2 billion per year and 36,000+ jobs (American Horse Council Foundation, 2018), a focused initiative that connects equine activities across the state would provide added value.

SEREP arose out of these efforts and was intended to explore the feasibility of a multidisciplinary Equine Community and Research Center. The center would build on the historic strengths of the region embedded within its equestrian culture and economy as reflected in the large per capita number of horse owners and farms, equestrian businesses, and recreation and competition centers such as the Foothills Equestrian and Nature Center (FENCE). Further acknowledgement of these strengths was provided when in 2014 the Tryon International Equestrian Center (TIEC) opened what has become one of the premier horse competition parks in the United States. And more recently, TIEC hosted the 2018 World Equestrian Games, the largest horse event in the world, and the largest sporting event in North Carolina history. The SEREP research team included a multidisciplinary group of researchers in the social sciences, tourism, design, and natural resources, and, in consultation with faculty in animal science, agriculture and veterinary medicine. The goal of SEREP was to provide a conceptual and physical design for a center where private industries, local organizations and residents, and regional academic institutions could work in partnership to enhance the regional equine-based economy and culture. The broader, and admittedly ambitious long term vision of the local communities, is for a facility and farm that would become a world-class center for innovative equine related research and education. Our NC State team began our work with this vision in mind.

Over an 18 month period beginning in March 2017, the NC State SEREP team consulted with a broad range of local stakeholders across both public and private sectors of the isothermal region; identified and analyzed comparable equine research and education facilities across the country that were connected to research universities or the equestrian industry; surveyed and interviewed regional equine businesses and horse owners; reviewed research, education, and training programs that would fulfill regional and statewide needs; and generated physical design scenarios that would be economically and environmentally sustainable, able to generate local business development and jobs, and have the potential to become a world-class center for equine related research that would be significantly connected to the high technology capacity of NC State University and other higher education institutions in the region.

The following three reports provided details of this engagement study.

NC STATE
UNIVERSITY

SEREP

SOUTHEAST EQUINE RESEARCH & EDUCATION PARTNERSHIP

PROGRESS REPORT

JULY 2017

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SEREP BACKGROUND

The Appalachian Foothills of the North and South Carolina border claim a centuries-old equine history whose cultural contributions are a continual, growing, and integral part of regional identity. Recent private-sector investments have established an international equestrian presence and sparked local community leaders' vision of an equine-based economy that would fuel and direct regional growth. Local leaders believe that collaboration will be essential in:

- **Developing research, education, and training programs to support this burgeoning equine economy;**
- **Ensuring a strong connection to the local community; and**
- **Providing the innovation necessary for sustained success.**

The Southeast Equine Research and Education Partnership (SEREP) extends from a contract between North Carolina State University (NC State) and Isothermal Community College via a grant the latter received from the Appalachian Regional Commission. The project is designed to explore the feasibility of creating a multidisciplinary research and education center where private industries and local and regional academic institutions can work in partnership on enhancing the regional equine-based economy.

Over an 18 month period beginning in March 2017, an interdisciplinary team of researchers from NC State is meeting with stakeholders across the area, researching comparable equine research and education facilities across the country, identifying the types of research, education, and training programs that a center could support, and generating physical design scenarios that would best fit the local area. The broader goals will be to determine opportunities for equitable and sustainable local development, the potential for broader regional and international linkages, and identify options for partnerships between local and regional institutions.

This July 2017 progress report provides our preliminary analyses in each of these areas. The contents of this report represent knowledge derived through interaction with the local community, supporting NCSU faculty, academic research, and analysis. The physical sites chosen were suggested by community members and are not exhaustive. We look forward to receiving the feedback from all community stakeholders. Comments and questions should be directed to the NC State SEREP team via email at serep@ncsu.edu or via the project website: <http://go.ncsu.edu/SEREP>.

SEREP TIMELINE

FROM MARCH 1 2017 TO MAY 31 2018

	Apr-Jun 2017	Jul-Sep 2017	Oct-Dec 2017	Jan-Mar 2018	Apr-Jun 2018
Partnership Building					
Visits with stakeholders to clarify expectations, objectives, and action plans					
Collaboration and mutual learning with ICC faculty and students					
Community Engagement and Appraisal					
Secondary data gathering about local assets and local needs					
Participatory appraisal meetings with community and civic organizations					
Writing of technical reports and public information materials					
Feasibility study					
Interviews with local businesses and institutions about demand for services					
Interviews with institutional stakeholders about revenue sources					
Engagement with communities and local businesses to assess needs					
Writing of technical reports and public information materials					
Design Work					
Analysis of the context; mapping assets; gathering stakeholder input					
Planning/design visioning workshop					
Development and evaluation of alternative plan/design strategies					
Development and refinement of final physical development plan					
Writing of technical reports and public information materials					
Scholarship and future funding					
Production of reports, manuscripts and presentations					
Identification and application for additional funding opportunities					

TIME, PLACE, & IDENTITY

TIME, PLACE, & IDENTITY

REGIONAL HISTORY

1830sISOTHERMAL REGION
BEGINS TO SEE
INFORMAL
HORSE RACES**1925**TRYON RIDING &
HUNTING CLUB
ESTABLISHED**1927**HARMON FIELDS
IS ESTABLISHEDU.S. HIGHWAY 74
OPENS**1929**TRYON HORSE
SHOW ESTABLISHED**1827**BUNCOME
TURNPIKE
COMPLETED**1879**RAILROAD TO
CHARLESTON,
SOUTH CAROLINA
ESTABLISHED

The history of equine activity in the Polk/Rutherford area dates back hundreds of years and created the foundation for an equine-based economy. Horses became important recreational animals with the establishment of the first local racecourse in 1836¹. Throughout the 20th century the equine community continued to grow beginning with the establishment of [Harmon Field](#) in 1927 as a playground and recreation center, but which eventually became the venue for a variety of horse competitions. In addition, the [Tryon Riding and Hunt Club](#) founded and hosted the Tryon Hounds fox hunt, Tryon Horse Show, and Steeplechase Races².

The next big development happened in 1985 when the [Foothills Equestrian Nature Center](#) (F.E.N.C.E.) was established as an education and conservation based non-profit^{3,4}. F.E.N.C.E. eventually became the new host of the Steeplechase Races and the primary location in the region for horse shows. F.E.N.C.E. remains at the center of local equine culture. However, in 2014 this region's largest equine investment to date created the [Tryon International Equestrian Center](#) (TIEC). TIEC is a world class facility for horse competitions and the largest in the United States⁵. TIEC's regional and international presence was instrumental in being selected as the host for the [2018 World Equestrian Games](#). Maintaining the rural equestrian culture and heritage that gave rise to the recent and ongoing development will be critical to sustaining it for generations to come.

THE ISOTHERMAL REGION

Located in the foothills of the Appalachian Mountains, the Isothermal Region is comprised of four predominantly rural counties known for their natural beauty and temperate climates: Cleveland, McDowell, Polk, and Rutherford. Polk and Rutherford Counties are also located at the heart of the regional economic triangle that includes the major urban areas of Charlotte and Asheville (in North Carolina) and Spartanburg/Greenville (in South Carolina).

- Current Urbanized Development
- 2060 Projected Urbanized Development

This area is also at the heart of the “Char-lanta” region, which spans from Raleigh North Carolina to Atlanta Georgia and has been identified as the [third largest mega-region](#) in the country⁶.

According to a 2014 study “[The Southern Megalopolis](#),” urbanized development will increase substantially across the Char-lanta corridor⁷. This is backed up by population data increases over the past 50 years.

"CHAR-LANTA" GROWTH

Data Produced by Social Explorer and retrieved from the U.S. Census Bureau.

REGIONAL ECONOMICS

A number of economic analyses over the past few years have pointed to the strengths and assets of the Isothermal Region, as well as the challenges and potential areas for growth⁸⁻¹¹. During the recent years, the area has struggled with poverty and job security. The unemployment in the area is consistently above the state average. Although the job diversity is lower than the state average, the main employment sectors include manufacturing, healthcare, hospitality, education, and public administration. This has led to a greater focus on economic and workforce development opportunities in the following five areas:

1. Work with neighboring regions
2. Keep up with changing manufacturing needs
3. Diversify economic opportunities
4. Diversify education and training opportunities
5. Succeed an aging workforce⁸

To assist in these efforts and to combat poverty, unemployment, and emigration of the community's' younger citizens, the SEREP project seeks to capitalize on the region's strategic location by further developing its historically rich equine-based economy.

EQUESTRIAN ECONOMY

This is a map of equine related businesses, facilities, trainers, etc. retrieved from the **Tryon Equestrian Directory, First Edition**¹². Each dot on the map represents addresses and locations of equine related businesses and facilities. This map was generated using a GIS tool known as Kernel Density, which measures and calculates the density of features such as address points and locations. It makes it easier to understand the spatial extent of the industry in this region. Each dot represents individuals and/or businesses and their relative location. Later on in the report, this graphic will be broken down into more detail and will help generate the extents of our geo-spatial analysis.

LOCAL EQUESTRIAN STAKEHOLDERS

TRYON RIDING & HUNT CLUB

Founded in 1925 by Carter Brown, this organization became the backbone upon which Tryon's rich equestrian culture was built. The original vision was to foster the growth of the region's equestrian population as the area became a magnet for out of town visitors looking for the mountain experience¹³. This club gave rise to the Tryon Hounds, the Steeplechase race, and the Tryon Horse Show and really put Tryon on the map. Today, the mission of the Tryon Riding & Hunt Club is to encourage, support, and promote all types of horse activities which will enhance the equestrian tradition of the Tryon area. This is achieved through programs of education; demonstrations of equestrian skills; cooperation with allied programs of nature conservation; promotion of youth in equestrian endeavors through scholarships and mentoring, recreational and sporting events, and such other equestrian activities that will benefit the entire community.

FOOTHILLS EQUESTRIAN NATURE CENTER (F.E.N.C.E)

Originally envisioned as a non-profit nature center focused on conservation, F.E.N.C.E. (Foothills Equestrian Nature Center) evolved to include varied equine activities and competitions. The Center currently stands at 380 acres and serves roughly 65,000 people each year³. Until recently F.E.N.C.E. hosted the local Steeplechase Race, and it continues to host horse shows for more than 30 weeks of the year⁴. F.E.N.C.E. also serves the community through youth camps and partnerships with local schools to teach science-based programs that use traditional classroom education and active-learning nature field trips. One of F.E.N.C.E.'s most successful community programs is [Therapeutic Riding of Tryon](#) (TROT). Established in 2004, TROT is an equine-therapy program for youth and adults that provides benefits to both the service-users and the volunteers who run the programs. F.E.N.C.E. staff is also interested in exploring other avenues through which the non-profit can support the community⁴.

TRYON INTERNATIONAL EQUESTRIAN CENTER (TIEC)

Established in 2014, Tryon International Equestrian Center (TIEC) is the newest and largest equine facility in the region. Currently open year-round, TIEC has plans to host events every week of the year, offer boarding for training, develop quarantine stables for horses entering the United States, and develop multiple five-star hotels for guests arriving for equine events as well as for meetings, conferences, and weddings⁵. TIEC owners and operators are working to integrate into the community by offering food through locally-owned restaurants, offering free entry for all equine events, and hosting Saturday Night Lights family festival-style events⁵.

INTERNATIONAL DRAW OF WEG

The FEI (Fédération Equestre Internationale) [World Equestrian Games](#) (WEG) are held every four years will be taking place at TIEC in 2018. In 2010 the games generated 201 million dollars in revenue for the state of Kentucky¹⁴ and promised to create job opportunities in an area of high poverty and unemployment. In 2018, 132 different nations are expected to be represented at the WEG¹⁵ and will put the region on the international map.

132 COUNTRIES PARTICIPATING IN THE 2018 WORLD EQUESTRIAN GAMES

INCLUDING ATHLETES, TRAINERS, OWNERS, NF DELEGATES, & OFFICIALS

SOURCE: OFEI DATABASE, NATIONAL FEDERATION GROUPS

ALBANIA ALGERIA ANDORRA ANGOLA ANTIGUA & BARBUDA ARGENTINA ARMENIA AUSTRALIA AUSTRIA AZERBAIJAN BAHAMAS BARBADOS BELGIUM BREMUDA BOSNIA & HERZEGOVINA BELARUS BOLIVIA BOTSWANA BRAZIL BAHRAIN BRUNEI DARUSSALAN BOLGARIA CAMBODIA CANADA CONGO CAYMEN ISLANDS CHILE CHINA COLUMBIA COSTA RICA CROATIA CUBA CYPRUS CZECH REPUBLIC DENMARK DOMINICAN REPUBLIC ECUADOR EGYPT EL SALVADOR SPAIN ESTONIA FINLAND FRANCE GREAT BRITIAN GEORGIA GERMANY GREECE GRENADA GUATEMALA HAITI HONG KONG HONDURAS HUNGARY INDONESIA INDIA IRAN IRELAND IRAQ ICELAND ISRAEL VIRGIN ISLANDS ITALY JAMACIA JORDAN JAPAN KAZAKHSTAN KENYA KRYGYSZSTAN SOUTH KOREA SAUDI ARABIA KUWAIT LATVIA LIBYA LEBANON LIECHTENSTEIN LITHUANIA LUXEMBOURG MADGASCAR MOROCCO MALAYSIA MOLDOVA MEXICO MONGOLIA MACEDONIA MALTA MONACO MAURITIUS MYANMAR NAMIBIA NICARAGUA NETHERLANDS NORWAY NEW ZEALAND OMAN PAKISTAN PANAMA PARAGUAY PERU PHILIPPINES PALESTINE POLAND PORTUGAL PUERTO RICO QUATAR ROMANIA SOUTH AFRICA RUSSIA SENEGAL SINGAPORE SOLVENIA SAN MARINO SERBIA SRI LANKA SUDAN SWITZERLAND SLOVAKIA SWEDEN SWAZILAND SYRIAN ARAB REPUBLIC THAILAND TURKMENISTAN TRINIDAD TUNISIA TURKEY UNITED ARAB EMIRATES UKRAINE URUGUAY UZBEKISTAN VENEZUELA YEMEN ZAMBIA ZIMBABWE

PRELIMINARY CASE STUDIES

**REVIEW OF SELECT RESEARCH
& EDUCATION CENTERS**

PRELIMINARY CASE STUDIES

IDENTIFYING CASE STUDY TYPES

The Core Interdisciplinary Faculty team examined a select list of equine education and research centers operating in the US. In addition, university-affiliated centers were explored to learn from development, managerial, and design best practices. This list was created in consultation with Equine Faculty members at NC State University. The list of benchmark centers were grouped into three categories:

- 1) Equine centers from land grant universities used by these institutions to pursue their research, extension, and education missions.
- 2) Equine research and development centers owned and operated by industry to conduct R&D and also to serve as public relations showcases for their companies' products.
- 3) Non-equine research and learning centers operated by universities in partnership with community and industry partners to take advantage of unique opportunities afforded by those satellite locations.

More details will be available in a future SEREP report.

BENCHMARKS

1) EQUINE RESEARCH CENTERS INTEGRAL TO THE MISSION OF LAND GRANT UNIVERSITIES

These centers tend to be located close to a main campus and rely primarily on research funding for operation. For NC State University, some considerations for a center like this would be the willingness of NC State Office for Research, Innovation, and Economic Development to use shared facilities funds to operate a new facility a few hours West of Raleigh; as well as the perceived need of NC State faculty to write such a center into major multi-year grants.

SELECT BENCHMARKS

COLORADO STATE UNIVERSITY EQUINE SCIENCE PROGRAM

LOCATION: Fort Collins, Colorado
SIZE/ FACILITIES: 80 acres, 3 barns, 2 indoor arenas, an outdoor arena, indoor stalls, and outdoor paddocks, and centers dedicated to equine related activities.

The facilities are used for teaching, conferences, and research on equine-assisted activities and therapy.

OKLAHOMA STATE UNIVERSITY CLINE EQUINE CENTER

LOCATION: Stillwater, Oklahoma
SIZE/ FACILITIES: 60 acres, teaching barn, indoor arena, classrooms, treatment area.

The facilities are used for teaching, research, and extension.

PRELIMINARY CASE STUDIES

TEXAS A & M UNIVERSITY HILDEBRAND EQUINE COMPLEX

LOCATION: College Station, Texas

SIZE/ FACILITIES: 65 acres, including a 200' x 300' covered arena, boarding barn, and a laboratory. Off-site facilities include a large animal hospital, Horse Haven Equestrian Center, and the OD Butler Junior Animal Science Complex.

The facility offers education programs, research, horse sports, clinical services, and theriogenology.

CALIFORNIA POLYTECHNIC INSTITUTE EQUINE CENTER AT VIA CARTE

LOCATION: San Luis Obispo, California

SIZE/ FACILITIES: breeding lab, 1 folling stall, sand arenas, 2018 Center will expand with a new covered arena, stallion barn, and foaling barn

The equine science program includes science, research, and management and training of horses from an industry perspective.

MICHIGAN STATE UNIVERSITY HORSE TEACHING & RESEARCH CENTER

LOCATION: Lansing, Michigan

SIZE/ FACILITIES: 100 acres, show/training barn, reproduction barn, 2 quarantine barns, breeding shed, indoor arena/ classroom complex, storage shed

The center houses a majority of the universities equine courses as well as adult and youth extension programs, arabian horse breeding programs, and equine research lab.

NORTH CAROLINA STATE UNIVERSITY EQUINE VETERINARY SERVICE - COLLEGE OF VETERINARY MEDICINE

LOCATION: Raleigh, North Carolina

The facility offers up to date diagnostic procedures and treatment of medical and surgical disorders. They also offer emergency care and hospitalization.

EQUINE EDUCATIONAL UNIT

LOCATION: Raleigh, North Carolina

SIZE/ FACILITIES: 60 acres, breeding shed, reproduction laboratory, foaling stalls, student apartments, and a classroom.

The facility offers instruction through university and extension programs.

UNIVERSITY OF FLORIDA HORSE TEACHING UNIT

LOCATION: Gainesville, Florida

SIZE/ FACILITIES: 65 acres, outdoor arena, reproduction barn/ laboratory, mare and foal feeding barn, student housing, and a hay storage barn.

This facility's focus is the equine industry. Educational programs include breeding, training, marketing, farm management, and health care.

PRELIMINARY CASE STUDIES

2) EQUINE RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT CENTERS

OWNED AND OPERATED BY INDUSTRY:

It is important to examine how much interest there might be from select equine companies, considering possible proximity to their headquarters, and ties to Tryon. Private research institutions seem to focus on applied research, and in research that is best kept away from the public view. Additionally, marketing and public relations are primary functions for these facilities owned by feed and pharma companies.

SELECT BENCHMARKS:

1 PURINA HORSE RESEARCH FARM GREY SUMMIT FARM

LOCATION: Grey Summit, Missouri

SIZE/ FACILITIES: Part of the 1200-acre Purina Animal Nutrition Center.

This facility conducts focuses on equine nutrition research - including growth and development, digestive physiology, exercise physiology, palatability and intake behavior, and life stages - and food manufacturing.

2 KENTUCKY EQUINE RESEARCH JOE PAGAN

LOCATION: Versailles, Kentucky

SIZE/ FACILITIES: 150 acre research farm.

This company focuses on applied equine nutrition research and consultation, with a mission to create a healthier and more athletic horse by improving nutritional care throughout the lifespan.

3 PHARMACEUTICAL PFIZER: ZOETIS MERCK CENTER

LOCATION: Richland, Michigan

SIZE/ FACILITIES: 24,000 sq.ft (.55 acres)

This company focuses on expanding vaccines and therapies for horses.

3) ENGAGED RESEARCH & LEARNING CENTERS OPERATED BY UNIVERSITIES WITH MULTIPLE USER GROUPS :

These centers are characterized by high involvement of local stakeholders and industry peers, which may help local communities connect better with local natural resource economies (e.g., field ecology training programs).

SELECT BENCHMARKS:

UNIVERSITY OF THE WITWATERSRAND WITS RURAL FACILITY

LOCATION: Acornhoek, South Africa

SIZE/ FACILITIES: 865 acres, visitor accommodation, seminar and conference facilities, a restaurant, staff housing, offices, and laboratory space.

This facility was created to foster research, student training, and community engagement in a rural setting.

CLEMSON UNIVERSITY INTERNATIONAL CENTER FOR AUTOMOTIVE RESEARCH (CU-ICAR)

LOCATION: Greenville, South Carolina

SIZE/ FACILITIES: 250 acres & 4 research facilities. In 2005, a master plan was developed and updated in 2016 for further expansion of the automotive research campus and its facilities.

This facility supports education for students pursuing graduate degrees in automotive engineering, research, and economic development on a global scale.

PRELIMINARY CASE STUDIES

DAVID H. MURDOCK RESEARCH INSTITUTE

LOCATION: Kannapolis, North Carolina
SIZE/ FACILITIES: 350 acres, multiple laboratories.

This facility is multidisciplinary and uses an integrated approach to collaborate on research and development solutions at the intersection of human health, agriculture, and nutrition.

SHAVER'S CREEK ENVIRONMENTAL CENTER

LOCATION: Petersburg, Pennsylvania
SIZE/ FACILITIES: 72 acres, an amphitheater, classrooms, welcome center, gift shop, herb and flower garden, picnic area, raptor center, and displays and exhibits.

This facility is a community resource and field laboratory for students who wish to get hands-on experience teaching about the natural world in the areas of environmental education, plant sciences, recreation, park, and tourism management.

The purpose of examining these case studies was to glean lessons and questions from select benchmarks for further exploration through expert, community, and key stakeholder input. Among other nuanced lessons, these benchmarks reveal that:

- Many universities have developed their equine centers close to their main campus, with the exception of situations in which the centers could be located in a region that affords access to opportunities specific to a region (e.g., Wits Rural's location next to Kruger National Park), or access to an industry partner (e.g., Clemson's ICAR's proximity to BMW).
- Centers are funded from a variety of sources, including tuition from academic programs, facility management/service funds, use of research herds built into extramural grants, as well as internally managed programs and events for the public.
- The funding of new centers is usually associated with the political influence and/or philanthropic support of high-profile alumni and community members. Horse ownership and interest in equine sports and events helps foster relationships with key supporters.

MOVING FORWARD

So far, our analyses have taken into account a wide variety of relevant case studies to help us understand how select research and education centers function. Moving forward, it will be important to have a deeper understanding of the intended use of the facility. Further details of potential research and education activities will be identified through continued examination of existing centers and further community engagement. For now, potential research and education activities are listed below.

POTENTIAL RESEARCH & EDUCATION ACTIVITIES

PASTURE MANAGEMENT	EQUINE HEALTH SCIENCES	COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT
HAY PRODUCTION RESEARCH / BREEDING	EQUINE VET-TECH TRAINING FACILITIES	THERAPEUTIC RIDING RESEARCH
PASTURE EROSION PREVENTION	HAY AND PASTURE SAMPLE TESTING LAB	EVENT HOSTING
ROTATIONAL GRAZING PATTERNS	EQUINE NUTRITION RESEARCH	COMMUNITY EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMMING
WASTE MANAGEMENT RESEARCH	EQUINE QUARANTINE RESEARCH AND TRAINING	EQUINE AND PEDESTRIAN TRAIL STEWARDSHIP
FOREST CANOPY AND PASTURE EDGE RELATIONSHIP	EQUINE REHABILITATION RESEARCH AND TRAINING	INTER-INSTITUTIONAL EQUINE TRAINING AND EDUCATION PROGRAMS
SUSTAINABLE BEST MANAGEMENT PRACTICES		

GEO-SPATIAL ANALYSIS PRELIMINARY SITE SELECTION PROCESS

The vision for the future Equestrian Research and Education Center is ambitious and evolving. Five sites were identified by community members for the initial feasibility study and a program that includes equine health science was requested. The center is intended to support the equestrian community's needs and create a working relationship between academic and industry professionals. However, the appropriate academic research and industry development are not yet known. The SEREP has been tasked with identifying all of those opportunities and developing a strategy for building a center around them. Therefore it is critical that prior examples in other regions and local strengths are both leveraged to create a successful model. First, environmental conditions and the equine industry as they currently exist must be understood.

PRELIMINARY GEO-SPATIAL ANALYSIS

ESTABLISHING THE AREA OF INTEREST

TOTAL EQUINE ECONOMY

The equestrian community is predominantly located in the low population rural areas surrounding and to the east of Tryon (NC), Columbus (NC), and Landrum (SC). It also bridges the divide between North and South Carolina with little regard for the state line. This follows the region's history as it appears the equestrian community has grown out from the area that includes local equestrian cornerstones - Harmon Field and F.E.N.C.E. Additionally, it is important that any potential EREC site would be close and connected to this community. Therefore the study area for further analysis will be based on a 17 mile buffer that encompasses this area.

EQUESTRIAN COMMUNITY MAPPED

EQUINE RELATED SERVICES

- Traditional Equine Health Services
- Therapeutic Health Services
- Therapeutic Riding
- Farm Supply
- Hay Supply
- Retail Services
- Farriers
- Miscellaneous Equine Services
- Construction/ Management

FACILITIES

- Built Structures for Equine Programs
- Boarding Facilities
- Riding Trails
- Competition & Horse Shows
- Overnight Stays
- Cross Country Courses
- Covered Arenas
- Horse Paddocks

HORSE PEOPLE/ TRAINERS

- Instructional Training
- Breeders
- Consultants

PRELIMINARY GEO-SPATIAL ANALYSIS

STUDY AREA CONTEXT

This graphic shows the spatial extend of our study area as well as the locations of sites to be analyzed and their relation to regional population centers.

SITE CONTEXT

1

FOOTHILLS EQUESTRIAN & NATURE CENTER (F.E.N.C.E)

2

TRYON INTERNATIONAL EQUESTRIAN CENTER (TIEC)

3

GREEN CREEK

4

HARMON FIELDS

5

HENSON RD / U.S. 221 SITE (RUTHERFORD)

*Sites not shown to scale for graphic representation

PRELIMINARY GEO-SPATIAL ANALYSIS

POPULATION DATA**1 DOT (green) = 1 PERSON**

Our site selection considerations focus on the areas where the population of the region is located. The largest proportion of the population is concentrated around the larger cities of Hendersonville, Rutherfordton, Forest City, and Spartanburg. However, more centrally in our area of interest the population is concentrated along the State Highway 176 as it passes through Tryon and Landrum, as well as around the crossroads of Interstates 26 and 74 where Columbus is located. Clearly, the road infrastructure has been important to the population growth of this region.

URBANIZED/ IMPERMEABLE LAND

The location of the impermeable or urbanized land can show patterns of development and provide insights into the health of watersheds and other ecosystem functions. As it would be expected, the impermeable and urbanized land mostly coincides with population density and is located within cities and towns. The primary exceptions are commercial and industrial operations located in the countryside, such as nurseries, golf courses, and factories.

PRELIMINARY GEO-SPATIAL ANALYSIS

ELEVATION CONTOURS**100ft.CONTOUR LINES**

A contour map has been utilized to visualize the varied topography of the regional landscape. Slowly rising foothills in the Southeast give rise to an abrupt and steep range of mountains in the West that level off similar to a plateau in the area of Hendersonville. Most equine activities are best suited for the gently rising foothills but must account for occasional steep areas, streams and rivers flowing from the high land.

LAND COVER DATA

The existing conditions of land by cover type will aid in site selection by showing how the land is divided and grouped, as well as how other environmental characteristics overlap or coincide with certain land uses. Polk and Rutherford counties are dominated by two land use types, forest and pasture that are typically excluded from developed areas. Although scattered throughout, the forestland is concentrated in the high elevation and mountainous areas, while pastureland is located predominantly in slowly rising foothills to the east and the western plateau of the Hendersonville area. Interestingly, the cities at the center of the study area, Tryon, Landrum, and Columbus, are located right along a border dividing heavily forested and pasture lands.

 Crops / Hay / Pasture

 Deciduous Forest

 Evergreen Forest

PRELIMINARY GEO-SPATIAL ANALYSIS

SITE SELECTION CRITERIA

This list of geo-spatial criteria is a framework for evaluating which sites are most ideal for the expected Equestrian Research & Education Center. Although this list is preliminary in the site selection process, it will help narrow the focus of our analysis.

TRANSPORTATION

- Site within 30'-50' of an existing road
- No more than 1 linear mile away from highway/interstate

SOILS

- Prime Farmland and Well-Drained Soils are preferred to provide ideal pasture conditions

WATERSHEDS /FLOODPLAINS

- Constructed area must be 200 ft away from surface waters
- Constructed area must be 200 ft away from floodplain
- Site not within substantially large floodplains

SLOPE / ELEVATION

- Less than 20% slope
- Avoid steep slopes to protect against erosion, provide safe pasture, and promote ease of access

CANOPY / TREE COVER

- Less than 50% of property should have Tree Coverage
- Protect against deforestation and damage to natural beauty

LAND USE /ZONING

- Minimum 100 Acres
- 200 ft away from Residential Properties/Units

SITE ANALYSIS

*Sites not shown to scale for graphic representation

SITE CHARACTERISTICS

FOOTHILLS EQUESTRIAN & NATURE CENTER (F.E.N.C.E)

SIZE: 356 ACRES

OWNED BY: FOOTHILLS EQUESTRIAN & NATURE CENTER

CITY, STATE (COUNTY): TRYON, NC (POLK COUNTY)

GREEN CREEK

SIZE: 183 ACRES

OWNED BY: TRYON EQUESTRIAN FOUNDATION,
GREEN RIVER FARM, LLC

CITY, STATE (COUNTY): TRYON, NC (POLK COUNTY)

HENSON RD / U.S. 221 SITE (RUTHERFORD)

SIZE: 103 ACRES

OWNED BY: RUTHERFORD COUNTY

CITY, STATE (COUNTY): FOREST CITY, NC
(RUTHERFORD COUNTY)

TRYON INTERNATIONAL EQUESTRIAN CENTER (TIEC)

SIZE: 1,138 ACRES

OWNED BY: TRYON EQUESTRIAN PROPERTIES, LLC

CITY, STATE (COUNTY): MILL SPRING, NC (POLK COUNTY)

HARMON FIELDS

SIZE: 47 ACRES

OWNED BY: TOWN OF TRYON

CITY, STATE (COUNTY): TRYON, NC (POLK COUNTY)

PRELIMINARY GEO-SPATIAL ANALYSIS

SOILS/ PRIME FARMLAND

An equestrian research and education center will need to provide pasture and possibly other types of farmland. Hence, any site selected should have soil suitable for these purposes.

SITE ANALYSIS

RANKING CLASSIFICATION:

1= Most Suitable → 5= Least Suitable

SOILS/ PRIME FARMLAND

*Sites not shown to scale for graphic representation

2 Foothills Equestrian & Nature Center (F.E.N.C.E)

Much of the site has suitable soil for crops/pasture and is of statewide and local importance

1 Green Creek

Contains the highest percentage of soil suitable for crops/pasture. However, much of that land is dedicated to a racetrack for the Blockhouse Steeplechase and must be investigated further.

4 Henson Rd / U.S. 221 Site (Rutherford)

Much of the site contains farmland of statewide importance. This means it is not ideal but still functional agricultural land.

3 Tryon International Equestrian Center (TIEC)

Contains a considerable amount of soil unsuitable for crops/pasture and has lost much of the remaining suitable land to recent development

5 Harmon Fields

Has the lowest percentage of soil suitable for crops/pasture and much of it would require draining and protection from flooding.

PRELIMINARY GEO-SPATIAL ANALYSIS

WATER RESOURCES / FLOODPLAINS

Streams, rivers, and floodplains can cause substantial property damage during storms and are easily damaged by pollution. A site must therefore have space outside of the floodplain to locate structures, as well as an adequate buffer area to separate surface waters from any potential pollution the center may create, such as animal waste and eroded sediment. Since this region contains the headwaters of many streams and rivers that are important resources to local wildlife and many downstream towns and cities, protecting water quality is a priority. The site selection process will take into account which sites incur the lowest risk.

100 year floodplain

200 year floodplain

Surface Water (Site Analysis)

SITE ANALYSIS

RANKING CLASSIFICATION:

1= Most Suitable → 5= Least Suitable

*Sites not shown to scale for graphic representation

WATER RESOURCES / FLOODPLAINS

3 Foothills Equestrian & Nature Center (F.E.N.C.E)

Contains a medium sized tributary of the Pacolet River (currently under a conservation easement) with a limited floodplain and no wetlands.

1 GREEN CREEK

Contains the least water resources, consisting of only medium headwater streams with no area of floodplain or wetland.

2 Henson Rd / U.S. 221 Site (Rutherford)

Contains the second least water resources, consisting of multiple headwater streams entering the site with no area of floodplain or wetland.

4 Tryon International Equestrian Center (TIEC)

Contains a large and important tributary of the Green River with a substantial floodplain and wetland areas. Due to current development threatening the watershed, additional damage should be avoided.

5 Harmon Fields

Directly adjacent to the North Pacolet River with the majority of the site being in a floodplain. Additionally, contains wetland designated areas. This area is at increased risk of both damaging water resources and being damaged by them.

PRELIMINARY GEO-SPATIAL ANALYSIS

CANOPY / TREE COVERAGE

In our site selection considerations, we aimed to select sites with less than 50 percent tree coverage. The natural beauty of this region is a result of its forests and environmental character. It is important that any potential EREC development does not contribute to substantial deforestation and works to preserve this character.

Tree Coverage

SITE ANALYSIS

RANKING CLASSIFICATION:

1= Most Suitable → 5= Least Suitable

CANOPY / TREE COVERAGE

*Sites not shown to scale for graphic representation

5 Foothills Equestrian & Nature Center (F.E.N.C.E)

Contains the largest percentage of canopy cover but the area without canopy is in many areas undeveloped.

2 Green Creek

Canopy coverage is limited but the most open area is already dedicated to a racetrack for the Blockhouse Steeplechase and must be investigated further.

3 Henson Rd / U.S. 221 Site (Rutherford)

Contains the second highest percentage of canopy cover but the area without canopy is entirely undeveloped.

4 Tryon International Equestrian Center (TIEC)

Contains the third most canopy cover despite extensive deforestation over the past 2 years. However, most of the area without canopy is under development and unavailable.

1 Harmon Fields

Contains the lowest percentage of canopy cover and most of the canopy exists in undevelopable land around the river.

PRELIMINARY GEO-SPATIAL ANALYSIS

SLOPE PERCENTAGE

SURFACE SLOPE PERCENTAGE

In addition to understanding the elevation of various areas in the study area, our site selection considerations must take into account the slope of the land. In mountainous regions slope can limit the uses and development of land because of the potential for erosion and landslides. For the purposes of an equestrian research and education center a majority of the site should have minimal slopes to allow for safe horse movement and limit erosion resulting from both horse traffic on pasture and construction.

SITE ANALYSIS

RANKING CLASSIFICATION:

1= Most Suitable → 5= Least Suitable

SLOPE PERCENTAGE

*Sites not shown to scale for graphic representation

4 Foothills Equestrian & Nature Center (F.E.N.C.E)

Has the second greatest percentage of steep slopes but does contain a large total acreage of undeveloped area that is not steeply sloping and out of a floodplain.

2 GREEN CREEK

Has the lowest percentage of steep slopes. However much of that land is dedicated to a racetrack for the Blockhouse Steeplechase and must be investigated further.

3 Henson Rd / U.S. 221 Site (Rutherford)

Increases in slope across the site as you get further away from Highway 221. However, the majority of the site has a consistently minor slope.

5 Tryon International Equestrian Center (TIEC)

This site contains the greatest percentage of steep slopes. Additionally, most of the areas that don't have steep slopes are either already developed or are in the floodplain.

1 Harmon Fields

This site has the second lowest percentage of steep slopes but most of that land is in the floodplain.

PRELIMINARY GEO-SPATIAL ANALYSIS

TRANSPORTATION DATA

Due to limited access, this region has developed along transportation corridors throughout its entire history. Therefore, understanding the network of roads and highways of the region, as well as each potential site's proximity to them, are important for the site selection considerations. Accessibility will be an important factor to future employees and visitors of the Equestrian Research and Education Center. Therefore, the preferred site should have the greatest accessibility possible. The connectivity to major routes will enable access to a wider population that might arrive from the greater distances and will be considered advantageous for the site selection considerations.

U.S. Interstate Highways
 Major Roads/Highways
 Minor Roads

SITE ANALYSIS

RANKING CLASSIFICATION:

1= Most Suitable → 5= Least Suitable

TRANSPORTATION ACCESS

*Sites not shown to scale for graphic representation

1 FOOTHILLS EQUESTRIAN & NATURE CENTER (F.E.N.C.E)

The largest roadway in our study area (Interstate-26), which runs from Charleston, SC to Kingsport, TN, cuts through this site. This corridor extremely important for future development in the area.

5 GREEN CREEK

The site is only accessible by 2 lane roads although one is heavily trafficked locally (Highway 9). There are no nearby interstates or multi-lane highways.

3 HENSON RD / U.S. 221 SITE (RUTHERFORD)

The site is adjacent to Highway 221, a four lane highway and is closer than Green Creek to the nearest freeway (US-74).

2 TRYON INTERNATIONAL EQUESTRIAN CENTER (TIEC)

This site is adjacent to the second largest roadway in our study area (US-74) that runs from Charlotte, NC to Columbus, NC. Access is however limited on the Southwest side due to the river and limited secondary roads.

4 HARMON FIELDS

This site is the nearest to a population center (Tryon, NC and Columbus, NC) but is only accessible by two lane roads and isn't particularly close to nearby interstates or multi-lane highways

PRELIMINARY GEO-SPATIAL ANALYSIS

IDENTIFYING AN ADDITIONAL SITE

All but one of the prospective sites considered for a potential Equestrian Research and Education Center, which were identified by local stakeholders, are affiliated with an existing member of the larger equine community. By selecting one of these sites, the area would be expanding on the value it already provides. The center could benefit from the affordable land and connections an existing entity would provide while building momentum for a successful launch. However, It is important to ask whether the total benefit to the community would be greater if the center was built independent from the existing equine infrastructure. Would creating a research and education center that stands alone build more substantial value for the equestrian community? Would sharing a site with an existing entity dilute the value they have already established? This relationship will be explored throughout the next stage in the study. Meanwhile, the SEREP team will work to identify additional unaffiliated sites for further analysis.

CONCLUSION OF SITE ANALYSIS

Understanding that selecting a site will continue to remain an on-going process, our preliminary site analysis has revealed that the Green Creek site followed by F.E.N.C.E. and the Henson Rd./ U.S. Hwy 221 site have the most ideal environmental conditions out of the five sites that were investigated earlier in the report. However, there are other non-environmental factors that must be accounted for in the next stage of this study, including potential partnerships, funding, program fit, potential for expansion beyond site boundaries, and community/stakeholder input. The information provided in this report are therefore preliminary and represents the initial phase of the site selection process. Once the research and education activities are identified, it will be possible to evaluate how each site will be able to support those activities and required spaces they demand. At that point it will be possible to select the most appropriate site and move forward with the design process.

PROGRESS REPORT SUMMARY

SUMMARIZING OUR PLACE IN THE PROCESS

- Our analysis and engagement thus far has provided a preliminary understanding of regional identity, context, and the key stakeholders
- Candidate sites have been identified and their spatial/environmental characteristics have been analyzed, compared, and documented
- Preliminary case studies have provided an understanding of existing facilities with related programs in the United States and abroad

NEXT STAGES AND GOALS

- Continued engagement with stakeholders and community leaders
 - Document perspectives of local farmers and equine related business people.
 - Identify potential EREC research and education activities.
- Finalize site selection (including sites yet to be identified)
 - Re-evaluate sites based on improved/more targeted quantitative data/information
 - Re-evaluate sites based on qualitative properties/information from engagement activities
 - Select the most appropriate site for development of planning and design
- Refine Case Study Analysis to target highly correlated programming and their physical properties
 - Design+Planning criteria
 - Economic & Community
 - Research & Education

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REFERENCES

Image/Graphic Credit:

Photo Credit: Cover Page, Page(s) 1, 4-5. 10. 12-14, 16-18, 26-27, 31, 48 - Tyler Kuss

Page 6-7:

1. Tryon Fabric TR&H archive
 2. Learn NC, <http://www.learnnc.org/lp/editions/nchist-newnation/4304>
 3. Saluda History historicalsaluda.org
 4. Tryon Daily Bulletin, <http://www.tryondailybulletin.com/2016/04/07/block-house-honors-the-mahler-family/>
 5. Tryon Riding & Hunt Club Archives
 6. Nautical: the Horse with the Flying Tail, <https://www.pinterest.com/pin/380694974737258543/>
 7. Independent Mail, <http://archive.independentmail.com/features/locals-remember-early-years-of-i-85>
 8. U.S. Department of Transportation, Federal Highway Administration, https://www.fhwa.dot.gov/highwayhistory/resultsDisplayImg.cfm?img=nc_5_I26_fhwa_1967_445.jpg
- 9-12. Photo Credit: Tyler Kuss

Page 6:

1. Terando AJ, Costanza J, Belyea C, Dunn RR, McKerrow A, Collazo JA, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0102261>

Page 41:

1. Colorado State University College of Agricultural Sciences <http://ansci.agsci.colostate.edu/graduate/ansci-graduate-academic-programs/grad-reproduction/>
2. Oklahoma State University <http://timeline.okstate.edu/>

Page 42:

1. Equestrian College Advisor <https://equestriancollegeadvisor.wordpress.com/2017/04/10/a-visit-to-texas-a-and-m-university/>
2. Cal Poly Equine Center <https://ranchhorse.calpoly.edu/http%3A//ranchhorse.calpoly.edu/content/about-us>
3. Michigan State University - Wyn Farm, <http://msutoday.msu.edu/feature/2016/a-seat-at-the-table/>

Page 43:

1. NC State Veterinary Hospital, <https://cvm.ncsu.edu/nc-state-vet-hospital/equine/ophthalmology/>
2. Tom Law - This is Horse Racing, <http://www.thisishorseracing.com/news/index.php/news/2018-high-dollar-colt-a-source-of-pride-for-florida->

Page 44:

1. Purina Mills, <https://www.purinamills.com/horse-feed/education/detail/science-and-innovation-behind-purina-horse-feed>
2. Kentucky Equine Research, <http://www.microsteed.com/About>
3. Pfizer Inc., www.mlive.com/business/west-michigan/index.ssf/2011/11/pfizer_opens_new_animal_health.html

Page 45:

1. earthworks, <http://earthworksmagazine.co.za/a-bushveld-education-wits-rural-facility/>
2. Clemson Automotive Engineering, www.clemson.edu/cecas/departments/automotive-engineering/academic-programs/

Page 46:

1. North Carolina State University, www.nonprofitcollegesonline.com/top-online-masters-aerospace-engineering/
2. Melissa Griffin, <https://blog.weatherstem.com/shavers-creek/>

GIS Data & Information Retrieved From:

- Social Explorer
- U.S. Census Bureau
- Libbie Johnson, Tryon Equestrian Directory: First Edition
- OFEI Database
- ESRI World Imagery
- U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) GIS
- NC OneMap Geospatial Portal
- Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA)
- United States Department of Agriculture (USDA), Natural Resources Conservation Service Soils
- Polk County GIS, Henderson County GIS, Rutherford County GIS, Spartanburg County GIS, Greenville County GIS

REFERENCES

1. Carolina Foothills Chamber of Commerce. (2012, -01-08T12:15:24-04:00). *Polk county horse country: The equestrian tradition*. Retrieved from <http://www.carolinafoothillschamber.com/equestrian-tradition/>
2. Friends of Harmon Field. (n.d.). Harmon field in tryon NC: History. Retrieved from <http://www.serendipityrancher.com/harmonfieldhx.htm>
3. Foothills Equestrian Nature Center. (2017). Retrieved from <http://www.fence.org/about>
4. F.E.N.C.E. (2017, May 10). *Meeting between F.E.N.C.E. staff and NC State University SEREP Team*
5. TIEC. (2017, May 11). *Meeting between TIEC staff and NC State University SEREP Team*
6. Florida, R. The dozen regional powerhouses driving the U.S. economy. Retrieved from <http://www.theatlanticcities.com/jobs-and-economy/2014/03/dozen-regional-powerhouses-driving-us-economy/8575/>
7. Terando AJ, Costanza J, Belyea C, Dunn RR, McKerrow A, Collazo JA (2014) *The Southern Megalopolis: Using the Past to Predict the Future of Urban Sprawl in the Southeast U.S.* PLoS ONE 9(7): e102261 Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0102261>
8. DeBellis, J., & Holmes, D. (2016). *The Region C Economy*. Retrieved from <http://regioncwdb.com/wp/wp-content/uploads/2016/12/Region-C-WDB-Presentation-Nov-2016.pdf>
9. NC Isothermal Region C. (2017). *NC isothermal region C: Economic development plan*. (). Stronger Economies Together Initiative.
10. Polk County Board of Commissioners. (2010). *Polk county 20/20 vision plan*. (). Polk County, NC: Polk County Board Of Commissioners.
11. Poole, K. E., & White, M. C. (1994, Jan 1,). Region C: Cleveland, McDowell, polk and rutherford. *Business North Carolina*, 14, 35.
12. Johnson, Libbie. *Tryon Equestrian Directory, First Edition*. 2016: 7-187. Print.
13. Tryon Riding and Hunt Club. (2017). *About TR&HC*. Retrieved from <http://www.tryonridingandhuntclub.org/?n=2014trhchistory&t=0>
14. \$200 million economic impact on kentucky from WEG. (2011). *Dressage News* Retrieved from <http://www.dressage-news.com/2011/06/27/200-million-economic-impact-on-kentucky-from-weg/>
15. Fédération Equestre Internationale Database. (2017). Retrieved from <https://data.fei.org/default.aspx>

SEREP

SOUTHEAST EQUINE RESEARCH & EDUCATION PARTNERSHIP

Progress Report II Identifying Opportunities

February 2018

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Introduction

The Southeast Equine Research and Education Partnership (SEREP) extends from a contract between North Carolina State University (NC State) and Isothermal Community College via a grant the latter received from the Appalachian Regional Commission. The project is designed to explore the feasibility and design of a multidisciplinary Equine Research and Education Center (EREC) where private industries and local and regional academic institutions can work in partnership on enhancing the regional equine-based economy. More specifically, a successful EREC would support the following community-identified needs:

- Develop a research, education, and training programs to support this burgeoning equine economy;
- Ensure a strong connection to the local community; and
- Provide the innovation necessary for sustained success.

Over an 18 month period beginning in March 2017, an interdisciplinary team of researchers from NC State is meeting with stakeholders across the area, researching comparable equine research and education facilities across the country, identifying the types of research, education, and training programs that a center could support, and generating physical design scenarios that would best fit the local area. The broader goals will be to determine opportunities for equitable and sustainable local development, to evaluate the potential for broader regional and international linkages, and to identify options for partnerships between local and regional institutions.

Summary of the July 2017 Progress Report

The July 2017 progress report shared our preliminary findings in each of the areas listed above. The contents represented knowledge derived through interaction with the local community members and stakeholder groups, key equine-connected organizations and businesses, and NC State University faculty and administrators. Key findings included:

Time, Place, and Identity:

- The Isothermal Region in the foothills of Western North Carolina has a long and rich history of equestrian economic, social and cultural activity. Primarily centered in Polk County, the equine economy extends eastward through Rutherford county, northwest to Buncombe County, and across the southern border of the state as far Greenville South Carolina. Notably, multiple economic analyses over the past few years have pointed to the strengths and assets of the Isothermal Region, as well as the challenges and opportunities for growth. In addition, the equine industry has deep roots in North Carolina as represented by a total economic impact to the state in 2009 of \$1.9 billion and 19,183 jobs (The Rural Center, 2009).

Case Studies of Equine Research and Education centers around the country:

- Many universities have developed their equine centers close to their main campus, with the exception of situations in which the centers could be located in a region that affords access to opportunities specific to a region.
- Centers are funded from a variety of sources, including tuition from academic programs, revenues from rental of facilities for events, fees of boarding research herds used in extramurally funded studies, as well as donations by donors and appropriation of public funds.
- The funding of new centers is usually associated with the political influence and/or philanthropic support of high-profile alumni and community members. Horse ownership and interest in equine sports and events help foster relationships with key supporters.

Potential Research and Education Activities for the EREC:

- Pasture management; to include activities like hay production research, pasture erosion prevention, rotational grazing patterns, waste management research, forest canopy and pasture edge relationship, sustainable best management practices.
- Equine health sciences; to include equine vet-tech training facilities, hay and pasture sample testing lab, equine nutrition research, equine quarantine research, equine rehabilitation research and training.
- Community engagement, to include therapeutic riding research, event hosting, community educational programming, equine and pedestrian trail stewardship, interinstitutional equine training and education programs.

Preliminary Geo-Spatial Analysis of Potential Physical Sites for an EREC:

- Understanding that selecting a site will continue to remain an ongoing process, our preliminary site analysis has revealed that the Green Creek site followed by FENCE and the Henson Rd./ U.S. Hwy 221 site have the most ideal environmental conditions out of the five sites that were investigated earlier in the report. However, there are other non-environmental factors that must be accounted for in the next stage of this study, including potential partnerships, funding, program fit, potential for expansion beyond site boundaries, and community/stakeholder input. The information provided in this report is therefore preliminary and represents the initial phase of the site identification and selection process. Once the research and education activities are identified, it will be possible to evaluate how each site will be able to support those activities and the required spaces they demand. This will enable us to further identify the ideal site features and design the future EREC site.

Current Progress Report

The goal of this report was to advance our research and understanding in each of the areas that would contribute to a sustainable Equine Research and Education Center (EREC). A second and equally important goal is to help potential stakeholders understand the context and opportunities for an EREC that would attract potential public and private investors in academic (including NC State), research, industry, and commercial arenas. In summary, our findings point to the following:

1. Community Engagement

Listening to the multiple voices in communities across the region has allowed us to gain an understanding of the assets, opportunities, and challenges that will play a role in a future Equine Education and Research Center. Overall we have found that:

- The geographical location and conditions, deep roots in the equine tradition, and a network of supporting institutions are key assets that many believe can be leveraged for economic growth and job creation.
- The existing equine economy is seen as stable and broad throughout most of the region although many also believe that the prospects for large-scale economic growth resulting from the sector is limited. Relatedly, given that the equine culture in the two-county area lies more heavily in Polk rather than Rutherford, attracting people potential workers from the latter, more populous county, has proved to be a challenge. Notably, Isothermal Community College continues to its certificate and degree programs and has recently received funding to expand its physical plant to meet those educational needs.
- The region enjoys a core set of citizens and organizations, both horse lovers and non-equestrians, that care deeply about the area and support the equine industry and the benefits it brings. This civically engaged group may not always be obvious among the many stakeholders but nevertheless forms the foundation of what makes the area attractive to potential investors, and, can be mobilized to create new opportunities, including a potential EREC.
- While many community members appreciate and support the opportunities for growth in the area resulting from the presence of the Tryon International Equestrian Center, those views are accompanied by equally strong views that those opportunities must be balanced with the desire to maintain and enrich the character of the community, particularly the equine culture, and, the importance of creating opportunities that provide living wage jobs both within and outside the equine sector.
- The number of stakeholder institutions span both the government and private sectors, and, from our vantage point, are mostly anxious and willing to collaborate on bringing opportunity and investment to the area. This too is a plus for moving strategically towards an EREC.

- While North Carolina State University is unlikely to invest in a high-end medical and research facility, aOne Health research and education model, perhaps organized around the equine economy, holds great promise that we will continue to explore. In particular, a center that builds the capacity for equine assisted research and therapy has the potential for attracting national as well as international attention. Moreover, the prospect for an interdisciplinary research and education center may also be a more viable solution. Over the next couple of months, in addition to meeting with administrators and faculty in the more obvious areas of Animal Science and Veterinary Medicine, we will explore connections with faculty across all colleges of NC State University.

2. Feasibility Study

In regards to specific business activities:

- Breeding Services and Equine Appraisal and insurance stand out as the activities with the least attractiveness and human capital availability.
- Home and Barn Construction emerged as the most advantageous activity with relatively high local human capital.
- Hotels, Inns and B&Bs, as well as restaurants, bars and cafes were perceived as very advantageous but with need for improved human capital through education and training.
- Real estate is perceived as a business activity involving a capable few but it was perceived to bring modest benefits to the local community.

An examination of equine and non-equine education and research centers operating in the US and internationally revealed that these units were usually characterized as:

- Equine research centers integral to land grant universities, located close to a main campus and rely primarily on research funding and donations.
- Equine R&D centers owned and operated by industry focused on conducting research that is best kept away from the public view, and
- Engaged research and learning centers operated by universities and characterized by a great deal of involvement with local stakeholders and industry peers.
- Each type of center demands specific financial models relying on a combination of public fund appropriation, philanthropy of a donor network, research administration fees, and hosting of recreational and educational visitors.

Overall, these findings suggest that the long-term feasibility of a prospect research and education center would likely need to be based on:

- Initial sizeable investment of local and state funds for land acquisition and building;
- Academic institution investment of initial staff and subsidization of initial programming and administration;
- Donor support coordinated by a “friends of” group integrating the primary academic institution and possibly high-level local equine groups;
- Research administration fees from active research programs complementary to research conducted in the parent academic campus(es);
- Lodging, food and activity revenues earned from hosting Extension, engaged learning, and tourists/visitors.

3. Design Analysis

The key planning principles guiding the future EREC complex include:

- Identifying potential locations and sites with essential landscape characteristics in place.
- Achieving quality facilities on the site that will reflect the EREC’s vision and its research and educational activities.
- Prioritizing sustainability that will minimize energy use and emissions, supporting sustainable land management for research, teaching, farming, natural areas, and other uses; and ensuring that land, facilities and activities work together to maximize knowledge transfer and positively impact local equine economy.
- Developing and promoting healthy environment, which may also represent One Health mission in support of well-being of researchers, faculty, students, visitors, staff, and horses.

Site Identification and Analysis Process:

- Easy access to state highway, proximity to local equine suppliers, proximity to population centers, availability of water source, cost of land, adequate size of land (min. 100 acres), relatively flat land, existence of wooded areas on-site, proximity to existing equine activities, and proximity to other equestrian and agricultural lands, existence of infrastructure in place, and good quality of soils are considered as important factors for the future location of the EREC complex.

- The SWOT analysis revealed that the FENCE followed by the Green Creek and the Henson Rd./U.S. Hwy 221 sites have the most ideal environmental and contextual conditions out of the five sites that were identified and evaluated.

Preferences

One of the primary driving planning and design principles of the future EREC complex includes but not limited to:

- Creating a strong image through site layout and its facilities' architectural characteristics that will also be a good fit to the region's character.
- There is a strong desire for having the rustic style and timber/wood buildings on the site that will be surrounded with pastures including substantial tree presence.
- Centralized facilities with larger building masses located away from the roadside are preferred.
- The future site should have appropriate amount of natural vegetation with more pasture/open spaces around the facilities.

SEREP Timeline

(From March 1st, 2017 to May 31st, 2018)	Apr-Jun 2017	Jul-Sep 2017	Oct-Dec 2017	Jan-Mar 2018	Apr-Jun 2018
Partnership Building					
Visits with stakeholders to clarify expectations, objectives, and action plans					
Collaboration and mutual learning with ICC faculty and students					
Community Engagement and Appraisal					
Secondary data gathering about local assets and local needs					
Participatory appraisal meetings with community and civic organizations					
Writing of technical reports and public information materials					
Feasibility study					
Interviews with local businesses and institutions about demand for services					
Interviews with institutional stakeholders about revenue sources					
Engagement with communities and local businesses to assess needs					
Writing of technical reports and public information materials					
Design Analysis and Development					
Analysis of the context; mapping assets; gathering stakeholder input					
Planning/design visioning workshop					
Development and evaluation of alternative plan/design strategies					
Development and refinement of final physical development plan					
Writing of technical reports and public information materials					
Scholarship and future funding					
Production of reports, manuscripts and presentations					
Identification and application for additional funding opportunities					

PARTNERSHIP BUILDING

any decision points
for us now
for 2015?

RESEARCHERS (TECHNICALS)
IMPLEMENTATION TECHNICALS

sustainable
sanitation
alliance

Handwritten notes on a piece of paper, including a list of names and dates.

The New Engagement Model for University: Community Engagement

Figure 1: Talent - Innovation - Place (TIP Model)

NC State's University Outreach and Engagement (UO&E) office is committed to enhancing the extension and engagement mission of the institution through a number of strategies. Goal 2 of the 2016-2020 Strategic Plan is designed to "leverage the distinct assets of the university to realize opportunities that emphasize reciprocity, collaboration and strong partnerships". Accordingly, UO&E developed a University-Community Partnership (UCP) model in three geographically distinct regions of the state of North Carolina. The Isothermal region, and particularly Polk and Rutherford counties in Western NC includes rural, small town, and semi-urban areas, has a strong historical and cultural mix of agriculture (including equine) and industry, and is seeking to transition from stronger economies and a workforce based on these assets but has experienced considerable decline in recent years. The framework for NC State's UCP model (see below) is designed to engage local communities in a reciprocal process that builds on the talent in both the area and the university to develop new and innovative economic and workforce models that take advantage of the uniqueness of place. Accordingly, the Southeast Equine Research and Education Partnership, generated through the partnership between Isothermal Community College and NC State, is a major part of the Rutherford-Polk University-Community initiative. At its core, it seeks to take advantage of the talent and innovation of both institutions as well as the broader Isothermal region.

Principles of Engagement

Developing effective and reciprocal university-community partnerships requires an approach that is shared and transparent among all stakeholders. From the beginning of the SEREP initiative, our interdisciplinary team from NC State operated from an approach that emphasizes good data, strong scholarship, and an understanding that success would be greatly determined by how we adhered to the following principles of engagement:

1. Interdisciplinarity

Interdisciplinarity involves collaboration between two or more disciplines to achieve a common goal. Interdisciplinary research recognizes that many of the complexities of the world are best approached using expertise from multiple fields, both academic and non-academic. Interdisciplinary approaches to research broaden opportunities and can offer creative solutions to practical challenges by identifying insights that no single discipline may be able to provide alone. Although the primary disciplinary focus of SEREP is on equine science, we continue to explore opportunities across multiple disciplinary areas as they may contribute to the primary outcomes for a research and education center: economic and workforce development, enhancing community assets, and attracting investment.

2. Sustainability

In its simplest form, sustainability refers to the ability for something to withstand the test of time. As we have been exploring the feasibility of a future EREC, we are looking at how both the physical structures, as well as the economic and revenue generating model should be sustainable. Sustainability also refers to how well the center is embedded in the local and regional community and is environmentally-friendly, well planned, and well executed. Thus, our work has attempted to understand and learn as much about the people, businesses, places, and culture of the region.

3. Placemaking

Placemaking can best be understood from this quote by “Project for Public Spaces:”

“Many residents of small towns and rural communities care deeply about the future of their towns and they value their uniqueness and strong sense of community. At the same time, many of today’s rural communities face urgent challenges: How can they add jobs and support local businesses? How do they create a positive future for their kids? How can they most effectively utilize limited financial, human, and infrastructural resources?”

Accordingly, our approach has asked the question of how can placemaking be used to collectively reimagine and reinvent the already-existing equine-based historical, natural, and cultural assets of the communities in the region. Moreover, and consistent with what we have heard from citizens across the area, how can we create a place that will contribute to keeping young people in the area and attracting the talent pool to help rebuild the economy?

4. Community Wellbeing

Although not the direct focus of SEREP, sustainable and place-based community and economic development is successful to the degree to which it contributes to community wellbeing. Community wellbeing is defined as "...the combination of social, economic, environmental, cultural, and political conditions identified by individuals and their communities as essential for them to flourish and fulfill their potential" (Wiseman & Brasher, 2008). In other words, and similar to the principles listed above, our hope is that an EREC will be sustainable, achieve placemaking goals, and contribute to the overall wellbeing of communities in the Isothermal region and the citizens who live within them.

Figure 2: Community Well-being and its components
(Source: <http://www.npsp.sa.gov.au>)

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT and APPRAISAL

Summary of Engagement Activity

Over the past few months our NC State Team has engaged a number of individual and organizational stakeholders in the local (Polk and Rutherford counties) and regional (Isothermal and equestrian-economy) areas. Our local engagement efforts, which included a series of two to five day visits over the last 10 months, have allowed us to meet with stakeholders and experience the culture and explore the history of the area. We have had formal and informal conversations, interviews, and focus groups with a variety of community residents, as well as representatives from groups and agencies listed in the List of Engaged Stakeholders table below.

In addition, we have sought to identify and gauge the interests of the potential higher education institutions and how they may intersect with an Equestrian Research and Education Center (EREC). We are in the process of sharing the information we have collected thus far with administrators and faculty at NC State University and have continued discussions with Isothermal Community College. And finally, in recognition of the fact that an ideal and sustainable EREC model should also be able to serve the needs of the equestrian communities throughout the state of North Carolina, we have met with representatives from other equine programs and veterinary clinics in Wake and Guilford counties, as well as the North Carolina Horse Council. We will be reaching out to others in the Isothermal region over the next couple of months as well.

Isothermal Region	Educational Institutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizens of the Isothermal region (individuals) • Foothills Equestrian and Nature Center (FENCE) • Isothermal Council of Governments • Isothermal Planning and Development Commission • Isothermal Community College • Polk County Government • Polk County Tourism Development Authority • Polk County Extension • Polk County Schools • Rutherford County Extension • Rutherford County Schools • Rutherford County Government • T. C. Hilton Foundation • Tryon Equine Hospital • Tryon International Equestrian Center (TIEC) • Tryon Horse Country, Horse Country Promotions • Tryon Riding and Hunt Club <p>Non-Isothermal Locations Visited</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CORRAL Riding Academy (Cary) Helping Horse Therapeutic Riding Program (Raleigh) NC Horse Council (Raleigh) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NC State University <ul style="list-style-type: none"> College of Agriculture and Life Sciences <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Office of the Dean Animal Science NC Cooperative Extension College of Design <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Landscape Architecture College of Humanities and Social Sciences <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Applied Social and Community Psychology Communication College of Natural Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Office of the Dean Parks, Recreation and Tourism Management College of Veterinary Medicine <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Office of the Dean Equine Primary Care Equine Surgery Office of Partnerships and Economic Development University Outreach and Engagement • Isothermal Community College <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Office of the President Academic and Student Services Business Sciences Community Workforce Development • Clemson University <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Therapeutic Equine Recreation • University of Tennessee <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Animal Science

In addition, we have sought to identify and gauge the interests of the potential higher education institutions and how they may intersect with an Equestrian Research and Education Center (EREC). We are in the process of sharing the information we have collected thus far with administrators and faculty at NC State University and have continued discussions with Isothermal Community College. And finally, in recognition of the fact that an ideal and sustainable EREC model should also be able to serve the needs of the equestrian communities throughout the state of North Carolina, we have met with representatives from other equine programs and veterinary clinics in Wake and Guilford counties, as well as the North Carolina Horse Council. We will be reaching out to others in the Isothermal region over the next couple of months as well.

Community Engagement Findings

Four main themes emerged from our observations, meetings, interviews, and conversations with individuals and groups across the local and regional communities. These are summarized below as assets, needs, opportunities, and challenges.

a) Assets

Environmental - The natural beauty and climate of the region has been repeatedly highlighted by many who live in the area, as well as those from the outside. Thousands of acres of natural resources in Polk and Rutherford counties, as well as the surrounding counties in North and South Carolina, have been protected by the Carolina Mountain Land Conservancy and the Pacolet Area Conservancy since the late 20th century (Rayner, 1994; Reinhard, 2017). These resources include rare plant and animal species (Padgett, 2006; Conserving Carolina, 2017), as well as water and soil conservation efforts. Appreciation for this natural beauty has led to the creation of at least 16 individual trails in Polk County (Polk County Parks and Recreation, 2017), 29 individual trails in Rutherford County (Rutherford Outdoor Coalition, 2017), and an estimated 125 - 150 miles of trails maintained by the Foothills Equestrian Trail Association (Foothills Equestrian Trails Association, 2017).

Additionally, the counties' unique location in the Isothermal region of the North Carolina foothills results in a temperature inversion that causes mild weather year-round. Some community members have also cited the weather as one reason for emigration into the region and as a possible factor in the local establishment of the Tryon International Equestrian Center (TIEC). Lastly, the quality of the land and climate has allowed for diversified options for the development of EREC that could serve the needs of both Polk and Rutherford Counties, as well as the larger equine-economic region.

Economic - The Isothermal region is also broadly connected to the mid-Atlantic area of the southern United States and includes three international airports, five interstate highways, and two railroads, rendering it highly accessible both domestically and internationally. The town centers of Rutherfordton, Columbus, Tryon, and Saluda are becoming increasingly revitalized and attracting local and tourist dollars to enjoy the regional art, music, dining, and shopping (REF). The region's natural resources (e.g., Chimney Rock, Lake Lure, and the state forests and gamelands) have a long history of drawing national and international visitors. The beer brewing and distilling industries are on the rise and complement the existing wineries and farmer's markets that sell local products. Family and child-friendly activities are also highly valued in the region, as evidenced by the numerous events at the Foothills Equestrian and Nature Center (FENCE), Saturday Night Lights at TIEC, and a youth-oriented history walk and a children's museum in downtown Rutherfordton, to name only a few. And finally, although mostly centered in Polk county, the business and recreation industries that support the equine industry is broadly represented in both North Carolina and South Carolina. The economic contributions and opportunities related to this industry are more fully explored later in this document.

Institutional - Polk and Rutherford Counties have numerous institutions interested in supporting community members and development. The public education sector from elementary through high school is working to develop programs that provide educational opportunity that respond to to changing economic opportunities in the region. This includes STEM education programs within the High Schools and the equine-related job training programs being offered and developed by Isothermal Community College's (ICC). Institutional assets also includes, however, the work done by the North Carolina Cooperative Extension offices in both Polk and Rutherford County. The agencies offer services that are dedicated to providing agricultural assistance, 4-H youth development, and family and consumer sciences. In addition, the equine industry has numerous institutions devoted to it including a number of businesses that provide products and services (see Feasibility section below), a high quality veterinary hospital, and the educational, social, and entertainment contributions of numerous equine-centered organizations (e.g., FENCE/TROT, TIEC, the Tryon Riding and Hunt Club, etc).

Civic Participation - One of the key indicators of a healthy community is the degree to which local residents feel a sense of attachment to the area and are involved in maintaining its desired characteristics and contributing to its growth (Cordes, et al., 2003; Choi, et al., 2015) . In the isothermal region, dedicated and engaged community members have fostered relationships across county, state, and international lines. Many citizens are working hard to maintain an atmosphere described as “small-town friendly” while cautiously taking advantage of the attention and development being driven by TIEC and the World Equestrian Games. Moreover, when asked about the prospects for an Equestrian Research and Education Center, many community members involved in the equestrian life expressed their desire to see it preserve and promote the long standing equine history and culture, as well as the infrastructure of land conservation, in ways that can also stimulate jobs and growth.

b) Needs

Despite the numerous assets in the Rutherford and Polk county areas identified above, several community members suggested it would be good to conduct a similar inventory throughout the larger equine region that includes the Greenville/Spartanburg areas of South Carolina and adjacent counties in North Carolina. Nevertheless, the needs reported included those related to a significant shortage of skilled farm labor in both equine and agriculture as well as the burgeoning hospitality arena, the limited education and job training opportunities in all of those areas, and employment services to connect people with those jobs. In the areas of research, waste management (horse), biofuel production, pasture and management, and forage development that is specific to the climate and soils of the region were mentioned among the top needs. And finally, an improved tourism infrastructure was also mentioned as something that could greatly improve the economic prospects and job creation in the region. It should be noted that many of these needs were consistent with the recent local and regional reports from a variety of sources mentioned in the first SEREP progress report (Carolina Foothills Chamber of Commerce, 2012; DeBellis & Homes, 2016; NC Isothermal Region C Economic Development Plan, 2017; Polk County Board of Commissioners, 2010).

c) Stakeholder Identified Opportunities

Despite the numerous assets in the Rutherford and Polk county areas identified above, several community members suggested it would be good to conduct a similar inventory throughout the larger equine region that includes the Greenville/Spartanburg areas of South Carolina and adjacent counties in North Carolina. Nevertheless, the needs reported included those related to a significant shortage of skilled farm labor in both equine and agriculture as well as the burgeoning hospitality arena, the limited education and job training opportunities in all of those areas, and employment services to connect people with those jobs. In the areas of research, waste management (horse), biofuel production, pasture and management, and forage development that is specific to the climate and soils of the region were mentioned among the top needs. And finally, an improved tourism infrastructure was also mentioned as something that could greatly improve the economic prospects and job creation in the region. It should be noted that many of these needs were consistent with the recent local and regional reports from a variety of sources mentioned in the first SEREP progress report (Carolina Foothills Chamber of Commerce, 2012; DeBellis & Homes, 2016; NC Isothermal Region C Economic Development Plan, 2017; Polk County Board of Commissioners, 2010).

North Carolina State University - Many stakeholders in the region have expressed a strong interest in fostering a greater NC State university presence in the area. At this point in the SEREP project, it is our view that EREC presents an opportunity for creating a mutually beneficial relationship between NC State and the local communities and have identified multiple research platforms to this end. Although one possibility (and desired by several) is a high-end medical research facility that would be an extension of the College of Veterinary Medicine. For a variety of reasons, and after exploring the possibility with faculty and administrators at the university, this scenario is highly unlikely.

Another option, however, and one that has been initially met with more enthusiasm, is a facility dedicated to equine assisted research and therapy, one of our more interesting and innovative discoveries. In addition to the services offered in the area by FENCE/TROT (REF), many local and statewide professionals (CORRAL, Helping Horse-REF) have pointed to the growing need for research on the effectiveness of different therapeutic techniques, the populations who can most benefit, and the training of both horses and humans. Currently there are an abundance of equine assisted activities and therapy being used worldwide, with little quality research conducted on their benefits. In addition, the equine therapy industry does not have a strong presence in the United States (REF) and most of the more consolidated research and training centers are located in Europe (REF). Given the strength of the local equine community and culture in the region and state, the opportunity for equine therapeutics to be a centerpiece of an EREC is one we believe stakeholders should seriously consider, and, we will continue to explore.

Relatedly, another research vision that also holds promise is an interdisciplinary and holistic One Health program model devoted to studying interactions between all members of an ecosystem (equine, human, plant, etc.) in order to promote health and wellness. Indeed, a version of this model already exists at [NC State University](#) (NC State Veterinary Medicine, 2017). Although we are unaware of such a model that is based in equine, this type of research could include examining the best forage for horses and to maintain the natural ecosystem of the region, the interaction between horses and humans, and best practices for maintaining ecologically and financially sustainable farms and businesses. In addition, the One Health model would create a unique focus that distinguishes it from other equine centers in the southeast such as those in Kentucky and Florida.

In the short run, NC State Extension, and perhaps with support from the local communities, should strongly consider adding an agent who specializes in equine-related services, a request that was highlighted on multiple occasions by extension staff in Polk County and the Western Region, as well as several horse and farm owners in the region. The needs that this extension specialist would assist with include education in horse health and emergency medical training, equine geriatric care, colic prevention and treatment, equine dental care, hoof care, equine nutrition, parasites, and farm management.

Summary of Community Engagement Activities

Listening to multiple voices has allowed us to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the existing assets and opportunities in the region that will ultimately determine the viability of an EREC. We believe this work has also contributed to the ongoing efforts to identify, articulate and address the current and forthcoming issues they deem important. Overall, we have found that the geographical location, deep roots in the equine tradition, institutional infrastructure, and civic engagement of its citizens provides a strong foundation on which to build an EREC or comparable new and innovative resource for generating jobs, growing the economy, and serving the research and education needs of the equine community. Although the initial desire for a major presence in the area by NC State University has been less viable, we remain optimistic about the option of the university pursuing a more interdisciplinary, yet still equine-centered investment. Moreover, in addition to the community engagement work, our team has been enumerating and examining various other avenues that might support the long term feasibility of an EREC. The following section reports findings from the perspectives and insights we collected from local entrepreneurs, business owners, and managers, operating in the local equine economy, a review of a variety of secondary data collected, and via the input of equine faculty from various institutions in the broader region.

FEASIBILITY STUDY

Examination of Equine-Based Business Sector Attractiveness

The long term feasibility of a prospect equine research and education center in the NC Foothills region depends on the center's ability to serve as a catalyst for the local communities' economic development ambitions. Accordingly, in October 2017, the SEREP research team created and administered an on-line survey, aiming at learning the opinions of the local business community on the scope of work and design of a possible university-led center devoted to helping the Foothills region leverage the growing local equine-based economy. In particular, this survey targeted community members involved in and/or cognizant of the various business subclusters in the local equine-based economy. The participants were inquired about which equine-based business activities were likely to bring the most benefits to their counties. In this context, we asked them to rate each of the business activities listed below according to four indicators:

- 1) Local availability of human capital - the amount of knowledge, talent, and skills their county has to advance each business activity;
- 2) Potential to create and support jobs - the potential of each business activity to create and support jobs for residents in their county;
- 3) Potential to attract investment - the potential of each business activity to attract investment of financial capital for economic development initiatives in their county;
- 4) Potential to support new local small businesses - the potential of each business activity to generate new local small businesses in their county.

Figure 3: Equine-based business subclusters

According to Porter (2000), a business cluster is a “geographically proximate group of interconnected companies and associated institutions in a particular field, linked by commonalities and complementarities” (p. 16). This concept helps us understand the complex relationships and social dynamics that link seemingly disparate businesses into a competitive economic sector, as is the case with the equine industry in the NC foothills. We used Garkovich, Brown, and Zimmerman’s (2008) equine economic cluster model observed in central Kentucky as the starting point for the categorization of equine-based business activities. Then we refined the categories using input from stakeholders and from our team’s fieldwork observations and interviews. The final equine-based business cluster model is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Equine-based business subclusters in the NC Foothills

The research team collaborated with key equine community leaders as well as with stakeholders from county-level economic development, chamber of commerce and tourism in Polk and Rutherford Counties to assemble a comprehensive list of equine-related businesses located in the region. Inspection of the list revealed that some subclusters were underrepresented, for which we used web searches to garner additional contacts and ensure that all subclusters were represented in our sample. The final database of equine-related businesses in the NC foothills region was comprised of 340 businesses.

Upon obtaining institutional approval to conduct the online survey (IRB #12355) the team administered the survey online using Qualtrics web application. The survey was first pilot tested with the team members for a quality-check. After receiving the results of pilot-testing, the team decided on the specific dates and times for the official administration of the survey with the study sample. The first email invitation to participate in the survey was sent on Thursday September 28th, with reminders sent the following Monday October 2nd, Thursday October 5th and Monday October 9th.

We closed the survey on Thursday October 12th, at which point we had received a total of 85 responses, yielding a response rate of 25.0%. We expected a higher response rate because of the relevance of the study topic to our target sample; however online survey research is now often yielding similar or lower response rates (Groves, 2011) and the findings seem consistent with our field observations as well as with follow-up checks with key informants which makes us confident of the validity of the study findings.

Local Business Community Sample

The majority of respondents said they resided in Polk County (42%), followed by Rutherford County (17%), and Spartanburg County (13%). A significant slice (28%) reside in neighbouring counties within North Carolina and also across the state line in South Carolina. Except for one participant who claimed to be a frontline staffer, all the remainder participants were either owners of a business or held managerial positions within the ranks of a company. This particular owner/manager perspective was deliberately sought by the research team, given that these individuals are likely to have a more nuanced perspective on the economic development potential of the region.

Figure 5: Local residence and management position of participants

When it comes to the location of the businesses, they were mostly from Polk County (42%), Rutherford County (17%), and Spartanburg county (13%). The businesses ranged from 0 employees (single owner/manager business) to 200 employees, with a mean of 6.4 and a median of 2 (the business with 200 employees was considered an extreme outlier and thus not accounted for in descriptive analysis). The most represented subclusters were professional services (15), followed by Equine services (14), and Tourism, culture and entertainment (12) (refer to the histogram). Farm Services and Supplies and Transportation services were not represented in the sample, albeit businesses in these subclusters were included in the original sample of contacts. A sizeable portion of businesses surveyed (15%) appear to offer services or products encompassing more than one subcluster (refer to the pie chart). In the future, it would be interesting to examine if this is a deliberate business strategy of local entrepreneurs reflecting diversification or the flux caused by a transitioning and rapidly changing local economy.

Location of Business

Representation of Equine Clusters

Figure 6: Location, size and type of businesses surveyed

Figure 7: Types of businesses surveyed

The Business Cluster Optimization Matrix

The goal of this section is to help identify the potential impact of different equine-related economic activities in the region and provide insight to strategies that would privilege the development of activities more beneficial to the community, and regulate activities that might be yielding benefits of just a few residents or mostly for outsider investors or organizations.

There is an established convention of viewing aspects of an economic actor's performance in terms of its position in a matrix. This convention has been developed by a number of highly credible organizations, including the Boston Consulting Group (BCG) and the General Electric Company (GE). Matrix representations allow economic actors to be viewed in terms of their performance on two measures, and also in terms of the interaction between those measures (Thacker & Handscombe, 2003). For this study we developed a 3x3 matrix (an adaptation of the GE matrix to the context of community development) plotting local availability of human capital in the y-axis and advantage for the community on the x-axis. In Figure 8 we indicate what kinds of strategic actions are advised for business activities falling in the various cells.

Relative Business Cluster Opportunities

Figure 8: Business Cluster Optimization Matrix

In order to measure the economic potential of the different business subclusters, we asked the respondents to rate 40 business activities according to four criteria:

- 1) Local availability of human capital (i.e., the amount of knowledge, talent, and skills your county has to advance each business activity);

2) Potential to create and support jobs (i.e., the potential of each business activity to create and support jobs for residents in your county);

3) Potential to attract investment (i.e., the potential of each business activity to attract investment of financial capital for economic development initiatives in your county);

4) Potential to support new local small businesses (i.e. the potential of each business activity to generate new local small businesses).

We used an ordinal scale with three anchors for the effect, namely “1=low”, “2=medium”, and “3=high” to plot the first dimension against a composite of the remaining dimensions, to which we called “community advantage”. The resulting plot (Figure 8), centered around the intersection of factor means, reproduces the Business Cluster Optimization Matrix above, with each cell having a height and width of 2 standard deviations. The bar chart illustrates the average ratings each business activity received from the sample. The business activities are listed in decreasing order of the advantage they are expected to bring to the community.

In Figure 10 [the scatter plot] each subcluster of business activities is represented by a different color, with numbered circles representing all the business activities (a color-coded legend is provided). The analysis reveals that Professional Services is the subcluster with the lowest availability of local human capital and also the type of business that is perceived to bring the least benefit to the local communities. Conversely Tourism, Culture and Entertainment emerge as a very attractive business subcluster with a moderate availability of local human capital. One should stress what appears to be a positive linear relationship between these two dimensions, which indicates that, at least in the eyes of the respondents, the higher the subcluster attractiveness the higher the availability of human capital or vice-versa (no implied causal relationship). Also, pairwise, values of human capital are consistently lower than attractiveness for any given activity or subcluster, which might indicate that there is a general perceived need to improved human capital, justifying further investments in education and professional training.

In regards to specific business activities, Breeding Services and Equine Appraisal and insurance stand out as the activities with the least attractiveness and human capital availability. These and other activities proximal to them in the matrix denote low importance to the region’s equine-based economy, and should be maintained at baselines.

On the other side of the spectrum, Home and Barn Construction emerged as the most attractive activity, and there is a perceived high availability of local human capital for the activity. This is consistent with field observations suggesting that the the region has a long equine tradition and a healthy horse farm and estate history; in addition, it was noteworthy to observe that the Polk County school system has a high-school home construction program that enables local youth to get started as contractors or to be more competitive when seeking civil engineering university degrees.

Figure 9: Attractiveness of equine-based activities

Hotels, Inns and B&Bs, as well as restaurants, bars and cafes, are deemed business activities with great potential to bring benefits but they show comparatively lower levels of human capital available. Accordingly, we commend the Isothermal Community College for attempt to close this human capacity gap through offering the Hospitality & Tourism Institute, which prepares local youth for hospitality careers. In addition, the findings suggest that appropriate tourism service and entrepreneurship educational programs might need to be developed in the local school systems.

Real estate and realtors business activity was identified as the business activity with the highest availability of human capital, but it was deemed as bringing modest benefits to the local community: therefore local stakeholders should explore policies that mitigate negative impacts of real estate development and retain benefits locally.

Legend:

- **Equine Health Services:**
 - 1 Veterinarian and lab services
 - 2 Horse massages & physiotherapy
 - 3 Holistic therapy and wellness
 - 4 Equine dentistry
 - 5 Breeding services
 - 6 Horse retirement
- **Farm Services & Supplies**
 - 7 Hay farming and sale
 - 8 Repair of tack/leather equipment
 - 9 Blanket cleaning and repair
 - 10 Manure removal and processing
 - 11 Sustainable farming for direct sale to restaurants
 - 12 Soil and feed testing labs
- **Equine Manufacturing and Retail Service**
 - 13 Blacksmiths, tanners and saddle makers
 - 14 Home and barn construction
 - 15 Manufacturing and retail of horse trailers
 - 16 Manufacturing and retail of farm equipment
 - 17 Manufacturing of bedding and footing
 - 18 Fence building and maintenance
- **Transportation Services**
 - 19 Auto, truck, and trailer sales and repair
 - 20 Equine transport services
 - 21 Airport and hotel van shuttles
 - 22 Tire retail and repair
 - 23 Farm equipment repair
- **Tourism, Retail, Culture and Entertainment Services**
 - 24 Hotels, Inns and B&Bs
 - 25 Private vacation rentals
 - 26 Restaurants, bars and cafes
 - 27 Visits to vineyards and farms
 - 28 Galleries, crafts and antiques
 - 29 Tack-shops
- **Professional Services**
 - 30 Real estate and realtors
 - 31 Specialty publications and photography
 - 32 Accounting, CPAs
 - 33 Equine appraisal and insurance
 - 34 Architecture and interior design
 - 35 Web design and emarketing consulting
- **Specialized Equine Services**
 - 36 Farriers
 - 37 Grooming
 - 38 Horse boarding
 - 39 Riding lessons and coaching
 - 40 Therapeutic riding programs
 - 41 Colt starting

Figure 10: Business Cluster Optimization Matrix applied to the NC Foothills equine-based economy

Examination of Equine-Based Research and Education Opportunities

The SEREP team examined a comprehensive list of fourteen equine and non-equine education and research centers operating in the US and internationally. The purpose was to learn from managerial best practices, ascertain how the specific topic of research relates to the local context, and understand how different centers generate revenue either by offering services to the public, through the administration of research grants or by securing endowments. In this report, we will report six of these centers, which we believe best represent the three categories that emerged from our research.

1. Equine research centers integral to land grant universities - These may tend to be close to a main campus and rely primarily on research funding for operation. Some considerations for a center like this would be the willingness of O -IED to use shared facilities funds to operate a new facility a few hours West of Raleigh; as well as the perceived need of NC State faculty to write such a center into major multi-year grants.

- Colorado State University Equine Science program
- Michigan State University

2. Equine R&D centers owned and operated by industry - We want to examine how much interest there might be from select equine companies, considering possible proximity to their headquarters, and ties to Tryon. Private research institutions seem to focus on applied research, and in research that is best kept away from the public view. Additionally, marketing and public relations are primary functions for these facilities owned by feed and pharma companies.

- Purina Horse Research Farm in MO - Grey summit farm
- Kentucky Equine Research - Joe Pagan

3. Engaged research and learning centers operated by universities and with multiple user groups - These centers are characterized by a great deal of involvement from local stakeholders and industry peers, which may help local communities connect better with local natural resource economies (e.g., field ecology training programs).

- Wits Rural Facility in ZA
- David H. Murdock Research Institute in Kannapolis, NC

Benchmarks

Colorado State University

The Equine Sciences program is housed in the Foothills Campus, composed of three barns, an outdoor arena, multiple indoor stalls and outdoor pens, and two indoor arenas. One of them, the B.W. Pickett Equine Center is a \$5.2 million, football field-sized, indoor facility with seating for 2,000 spectators, concession stands, ticket booths, a show office and crow's nest, faculty offices and a multimedia classroom, and a conference room. In addition, the program has the Temple Grandin Equine Center (projected), specifically focused on equine-assisted activities and therapy (EAAT). According to the website, research conducted through the center will provide a body of evidence that supports practice and education in EAAT, expands services to broader groups of people, and promotes horse welfare. The program collaborates with the College of Veterinary Medicine, which offers specialized training at the college's Equine Reproduction Laboratory and Orthopaedic Research Center.

Financial Model:

The facilities are primarily used for education and research purposes. In addition, third-party organizations provide EAAT programs and services, such as therapeutic horsemanship and hippotherapy. The program has several revenue-generating activities outlined in their outreach and engagement page. The program rents the facilities when they are not busy with research and education program. The Equine Orthopaedic Research Center is associated with high-level philanthropic contributions from university supporters - for example, the Malone family donated \$42.5M for regenerative medicine research and services in 2014 because of their love of horses. In the same line, the Temple Grandin Equine Center is being partially funded through Naming and Endowment opportunities. In terms of research funding, Equine Orthopaedic Research Center declared 53 research accounts in fiscal year 2012-2013, totaling \$1,175,924 for the biennium, with the biggest contributor being the National Institutes of Health.

Image Credits Colorado State University <http://tgec.agsci.colostate.edu/>

Faculty Input:

The center was built by in the 60s, largely funded by the reproduction/breeding horse industry. It has a research part with a world class reproduction program, and a teaching part offering short courses where they train people. Despite generating considerable revenue, they have to pay overhead to the central administration. Overall, the center may not be very lucrative. Later, they created what is now a world-renowned orthopedic center for helping hurt horses recover. The center has strong ties with horse owners, which were forged by services to their horses. If researchers want to use the facilities and the horses, they have to build in costs into the research grant. The same applies to the education program, for expenses with barn managers and maintenance. University administrators are sympathetic with the center because it brings in big donations.

Michigan State University (<http://www.msuarabians.com/facility.html>)

The MSU Horse Teaching and Research Center (HTRC) is located on 100 acres, and consists of a show/training barn, a reproduction barn, 2 quarantine barns, a breeding shed, an indoor arena/classroom complex, and a storage shed. It is the site of the majority of the horse classes taught at Michigan State University, both in the Animal Science Equine Program and the Horse Management Program. The annual student sale is also conducted at the HTRC. The farm is also the site of many of the Adult Extension and Youth Extension programs at Michigan State University, as well as several ongoing projects of the Equine Research Lab. The horse facility has a long history of breeding purebred Arabians since the 1940's, and continues to use them in the teaching and research programs conducted at the center.

It is also home to the annual student-run horse auction. This auction is incorporated into the Animal Science and Horse Management programs, and give students the opportunity to experience all aspects of marketing, from horse preparation to sales ring design and advertising.

Financial Model:

At present, Michigan State is home to approximately 200 equine oriented students enrolled in both the two-year certificate-granting program offered by the Institute of Agricultural Technology Horse Management program and the Bachelor of Science degree offered by the Animal Science Department.

The Endowment for the Preservation of the Arabian Breeding Program at MSU was established by an organization called "Friends of The MSU Horse Teaching and Research Center", and is supported by membership dues and annual fund raising activities, including the annual MSU Friends Arabian Horse Show conducted on campus at the MSU Pavilion.

Every year, horses bred at the center are auctioned off at the The MSU Spartan Spectacular Arabian Horse Auction. Within the student-engaged enterprise system, students work with a horse then get a slice of the sale when the horse is auctioned off.

Faculty Input:

A referendum was passed during the early nineties passed with the support of the horse industry. It is primarily an educational facility, which enables the center to be financially supported through the legislature. However, there is limited involvement by the Veterinary school, which may limit the center's ability to generate revenue.

Image Credits: Google Maps

Purina Horse Research Farm in Missouri

This facility houses more than 70 horses, ranging from newborn foals to senior horses, including a group of rescued off-the-track Thoroughbreds used in exercise physiology research. Over the years, their in-house nutrition research has led to the creation of a number of new products and patents on feed and manufacturing processes. Purina's nutritional research generally falls into the following categories: growth and development, digestive physiology, exercise physiology, palatability and intake behavior, and life stage investigations.

Financial Model:

Research is financed by the commercial branch. In most cases, they utilize their own herd of horses to conduct their studies, but they also partner with university equine research programs with specialized capabilities for particular projects.

Faculty Input:

Purina develops and sells many kinds of animal feed. Purina does product development and research in this facility, but the primary function of the facility is marketing. Accordingly, the company brings in groups of customers and vets. Given that are the source of recommendations and advice for most horse owners, they strive to make them feel they are the only company that has such a specialized experimental facility.

Image Credits: AIA Chicago https://www.aiachicago.org/dea_archive/2015/purina-animal-nutrition-center/

Kentucky Equine Research

Kentucky Equine Research (KER) is an international equine nutrition, research, and consultation company serving horse owners and the feed industry. KER's goals are to advance horse industry knowledge of equine nutrition and exercise physiology; to apply that knowledge to produce healthier, more athletic horses, and support the nutritional care of all horses throughout their life. KER was founded in 1988 when Joe Pagan, Ph.D., who realized that information generated from research was not disseminated to the individuals who needed it most: feed manufacturers and horse owners.

Financial Model:

The company has two main revenue streams. First and foremost, they provide consultancy to feed manufacturers. Secondly, their nutritionists work with mill owners and managers internationally to formulate feeds that complement typical local forages. The website claims KER is one of the most prolific private equine nutrition and exercise physiology research organizations in the world, with a publication rivaling that of leading universities. However, it is not clear whether they have any active research grants.

Faculty Input:

This organization tests products for industry. Nevertheless their researchers take part in academic conferences, and usually report and share research findings. In general, they are competent, engaged, and respected scientists.

This organization does not compete directly with university programs because they focus on applied research. This and a few other similar organizations (with or without a physical facility) tend to conduct research projects that are better conducted less visible to the general public.

Image Credits: Saracen Horse Feeds <https://www.saracenhorsefeeds.com/company/kentucky-equine-research>

Wits Rural Facility

Wits Rural Facility (WRF) is a rural campus of the University of the Witwatersrand, established in 1989 with a grant from the Anglo-DeBeers Chairman's Fund. The purpose was to create a base from which Wits could bring academic resources to bear on development challenges created by the Apartheid homeland system. The facility continues to support a wide range of research, student training and community engagement in a rural setting. Infrastructure includes a variety of visitor accommodation, seminar and conference facilities, a restaurant, staff housing, offices, and laboratory space.

Financial Model:

The facility hosts faculty and students from the Wits University and other collaborating universities. In addition, Wits Rural offers accommodation and catering to the general public, as well as venues for conferences and other events.

The facility has a small group of resident research faculty involved in long-term externally funded research. The research focuses on rural development and rural health, with some research involvement in neighboring wildlife preserves and Kruger National Park. The center's proximity of Kruger national Park has helped Wits faculty and international colleagues develop a close relationship with South Africa's National Parks.

Faculty Input:

Wits Rural Facility is a satellite research and education campus of Wits University. This "campus" enables many Wits faculty to attract research grants. There are a few residential field research faculty, and many faculty from Wits and other international universities do semester-long residencies. Likewise, many groups of domestic and international students enroll for mid-length courses. Ultimately, the facility exists to help local communities connect better with local natural resource economies (e.g. field ecology training programs).

Image Credits: University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg
<https://www.wits.ac.za/campus-life/arts-and-culture/wits-rural-facility/accommodation/>

David H. Murdock Research Institute (<http://dhmri.org/>)

The David H. Murdock Research Institute (DHMRI) is a nonprofit life sciences research institute that provides collaborators research and development solutions at the intersection of human health, agriculture and nutrition. DHMRI contains instrumentation, resident expertise, and well-equipped laboratories that bring together a variety of disciplines under one roof. DHMRI has developed a multidisciplinary, integrated approach that incorporates a variety of scientific platforms.

Although there is not any reference to equine research engendered by the Institute, its founder is a breeder of more than 200 prized Arabian horses. In addition, at the time of this survey, there were two faculty members of NC State Vet College working at the institute.

Financial Model:

The institute offers technical support to customers with research projects, or can act as a subcontractor on research grants. Lab space rental is also available. They also offer laboratory sabbaticals including walk-up access to state of the art equipment. In addition, David Murdock, the founder started an endowment in 2014 that donates \$15 million a year to the center.

Equine Consulting Faculty Summary Input:

There are a couple faculty from NC State's main campus housed in this institute, but they are perceived to visit the NC State main campus or interact with other faculty very infrequently. Those faculty members are perceived as competent but other faculty struggle to reach out to them in Kannapolis.

Likewise, none or few faculty from NC State's main campus have visited the Kannapolis institute. Therefore, it is likely that the faculty in the institute may feel isolated and unsure about their colleagues.

Image Credits: NC Research Campus <https://transforming-science.com/350-acre-campus/>

Input from the Equine Faculty from NC State University, Clemson University, and University of Tennessee

According to early stakeholder input, the prospective equine research and education center is expected to address the educational, research and extension missions of universities in the Southeastern US region. Accordingly, between April and November 2018 faculty from NC State University, Clemson University and the University of Tennessee were interviewed face-to-face, by phone, and by email, using in-depth unstructured interviews. The questions used in these interviews included:

- If an equine education and research center were built in the NC Foothills region, to what extent would you personally see yourself involved in professional activities there?
- Based on your insight into other equine centers devoted to research and education, how do you think such a center could be financially viable in the long-term?
- As we explore the appropriate scope and business model for a prospect equine research and education center in the NC Foothills region, what tips do you have for our team!

A total of eight faculty in equine sciences, veterinary medicine and equine therapeutic recreation were recruited for the study, and 5 were able to participate in the interviews. The interviews were recorded, transcribed, and shared with one more member of the SEREP team. The two SEREP team members conducted a thematic analysis of the data using constant comparison as a form of researcher triangulation, and then shared the summarized findings with the rest of the team for insider briefing validation. The analysis yielded the following insights:

Focus of center must fit local socio-cultural characteristics and equine culture.

In terms of research related to equine physiology, medicine, nutrition and animal care, informants explained that *“The focus in Tryon is on competition - so if this center is close by the research should be related to those issues as well.”* We learned that contrasting with Kentucky where racing is the focus *“Tryon is focused on sporting equine activities. These horses [in NC] have much more longevity than the race horses that have a very short lifespan.”* Indeed, *“After racing prime [horses] are repurposed – only the best ones are used for breeding stock. In North Carolina many people buy racing veterans for our sporting industry.”* Therefore in Kentucky research and education would focus on improving race performance, and in North Carolina the focus should be on issues related to healthy longer lives. Additionally, we learned that in North Carolina *“there are procedures associated with breeding horses that veterinarians have to do these procedures. Some of the big reproduction centers/facilities will be in states where technicians can conduct the procedures with the supervision of vets. NC has never been in the biz of high-level equine reproduction because we do not have racing.*

These centers are located in States with gambling horse racing [and loser regulations].” Therefore, breeding services are not very central to the context of equine research and education in the NC foothills.

Participants also explained that high-level equine sporting teams *“that come to tryon do not have many [equine care] needs other than their food and boarding.”* They noted that those teams would not likely allow their horses to be involved in research projects due to their high value and proprietary care processes. Nevertheless the region will have an inherent draw for researchers and educators in the equine fields, therefore becoming *“Possibly a good place for conferences in this center. Equine conferences could be organized there. There are many equine groups that could organize meetings there. [The center should have] Capacity to host a lot of people...”*

The relationship between the center and a parent campus will be challenging.

Equine faculty voiced several concerns in regards to the ability to develop a sustained synergistic collaboration between a center in the NC foothills and their respective parent campus. One noted that *“Distance from main campus is a problem - we cannot separate the equine faculty and we cannot move them all there”* and *“faculty do not like to drive often.”* They noted that competitive teams are increasingly multi-disciplinary involving regular formal and informal interactions across campus including equine and non-equine researchers; therefore researchers located full time in a remote location would be at a great disadvantage. In addition, some research activities require constant or regular involvement by the specialized researcher, for example *“you may have to monitor a pregnant mare every day”*.

Informants alerted that a possible center would need permanent staff on site, and that the composition of that team should be very carefully delineated. One noted that overlap in research foci might bring conflict because *“in terms of funding, whether it*

is big or small grants (NC Horse Council) [they would be] competing with our faculty here." Subject-matter gaps varied across institutions including genetics, therapeutic equine recreation, and livestock.

The center must serve the local community.

A third salient theme stemming from the equine faculty interviews was that a prospect center should be designed to serve the needs of the broad community groups in the NC Foothills and not just equine sporting elites, specific business factions or "the Tryon center and high-end horse owners." Very importantly, "This center should not duplicate or compete" with existing businesses and institutions like the Isothermal Community College or the Tryon horse Hospital. One participant suggested that "Maybe it would work to have a farrier horse school" in the center, but such program could encroach on the future plans of local education and training institutions like the county public school systems, the community college and the NC Cooperative Extension offices. Another participant suggested that the center could conduct applied research on how hay desired by high-end horses could be grown in the region and marketed to local horse owners as well as visiting equine teams. Indeed, research and subsequent local training and take-to-market efforts on growing and selling hay/feed seem to be emerging as a thread consistent with needs expressed by community stakeholders in the course of this project, and suitable to be pursued by a multidisciplinary team including specialists in equine sciences, nutrition, crop and soil scientists, as well as agribusiness and consumer behavior.

The center needs a unique and locally-appropriate focus.

In business development terms, the participants explained that we need to identify the center's *unfair advantage* - i.e., an innovative and savvy focus that can be pursued in this region better than in any other region. When talking about this theme, faculty considered numerous factors like:

- a) the rich equine sporting culture
- b) the local soil and climate
- c) the regional socio-economic profile
- d) the State's substantial military presence
- e) the State's legal structure governing equine care services
- f) the grand challenges affecting our society and extramural funding

A focus on the convergence between human and animal health (like in Colorado State University) seemed agreeable to most participants. More specifically, some mentioned the opportunity to focus on holistic veterinarian medicine (e.g., equine acupuncture), and possibly the health benefits of recreation with horses for humans (e.g., military vet recovery through equine recreation therapy). And another possibly complementary thread was to focus the center in researching and enabling a region to adapt in a sustainable and equitable manner from agriculture and manufacturing - to an equine services economy.

The funding and function of the center will be shaped by philanthropy and influence

The equine faculty noted that existing equine research and education centers were created or significantly expanded due to high-value philanthropic donations or the political lobbying of strong supporters that generate public fund streams. For example, Colorado State's Equine Orthopaedic Research Center was built thanks to a donation of \$42M by the Malone family whom were thankful of the institution's role in caring for one of their very beloved family horses. Michigan State's Horse Teaching and Research Center was started with state funding resulting from a referendum supported by the horse industry, and since more recently it also is funded by fundraising campaigns and membership fees for the Endowment for the Preservation of the Arabian Breeding Program. And *"in KY set portion of all racing funds get designated towards equine research and education. [So, the] University of Kentucky, etc, they all get a portion of those funds."* In this regard, the faculty wondered if NC Horse Council funding could support the centers; and whether this would be a constraint for the involvement of out of state institutions.

On one hand, equine faculty noted that fundraising for the center *"might compete with donations for"* their parent campuses. On the other hand they ventured that a center in the NC foothills might provide their respective institutions *"access to high value donors that go to Tryon."* In this context, a participant stated that *"if there is going to be a building then it is likely that we'd like to be involved because if not us, then someone else might become involved."*

Summary of Feasibility Study

The long term feasibility of a prospect equine research and education center in the NC Foothills region depends on the center's ability to serve as a catalyst for the local communities' economic development ambitions. In this regard, following a 6-month participatory fieldwork in the region, the team administered an online survey asking participants to rate business activities according to availability of local human capital, potential to create and support local jobs, attract outside investment, and support new local small businesses. Analysis generated a matrix illustrating the relationship between perceptions of community benefits and human capital for each business activity. Breeding Services and Equine Appraisal and insurance stood out as the least advantageous and also among the activities with the least human capital. Home and Barn Construction emerged as the most advantageous activity with relatively high local human capital. Tourism sector business activities were perceived as very advantageous but with need for improved human capital through education and training. Conversely real estate is perceived as a business activity involving a capable few but does not yield proportional equitable benefits to the overall community.

The team concomitantly interviewed faculty from NC State University, Clemson University and the University of Tennessee, and examined a comprehensive list of equine and non-equine education and research centers operating in the US and internationally. These primary and secondary data suggest that research and education centers fall under three categories:

- 1) equine research centers integral to land grant universities, which tend to be close to a main campus and rely primarily on research funding;
- 2) equine R&D centers owned and operated by industry, which tend to conduct research that is best kept away from the public view, and
- 3) engaged research and learning centers operated by universities characterized by a great deal of involvement from local stakeholders and industry peers.

Each type of center would demand specific financial models relying on a combination of public fund appropriation, philanthropy of a donor network, research administration fees, and hosting of recreational and educational visitors. Overall, these findings suggest that the long-term feasibility of a prospect research and education center would likely need to be based on:

- a) Initial sizeable investment of local and state funds for land acquisition and building;
- b) Academic institution investment of initial staff and subsidization of initial programming and administration;
- c) Donor support coordinated by a "friends of" group integrating the primary academic institution and possibly high-level local equine groups;

- d) Research administration fees from active research programs complementary to research conducted in the parent academic campus(es);
- e) Lodging, food and activity revenues earned from hosting Extension, engaged learning, and tourists/visitors.

The findings from this Feasibility Study built upon Community Engagement insights and they inform the following section focused on design orientations for a proposed future center facility.

DESIGN ANALYSIS

Planning and Design Process Overview

The successful implementation of the future Equine Research and Education Center and its mission requires a strong vision, partnerships, research and educational focus, and physical environment that effectively support and address the equine related needs in the region. The intent is to improve the equine industry in the region, while providing cutting edge education and research in support of care and welfare of the horse. Therefore the SEREP team aims to develop a vision plan with guiding design principles that will demonstrate how a site and functional facilities can encompass the required equine related educational and research activities, as well as provide growth and flexibility for the future.

The partnership model required for this new equine complex is currently unknown. However, using a systematic approach merged with design thinking process, as well as placemaking principles, the SEREP team aims to develop a spatial program and conceptual site design scenarios that will support potential research and education activities in a premier equine research and education complex that might also become a focal place for various community equine-related services in the region. The key planning principles guiding the future EREC complex include:

- Achieving quality facilities on the site that will reflect the EREC's vision;
- Prioritizing sustainability that will minimize energy use and emissions, supporting sustainable land management for research, teaching, farming, natural areas, and other uses; and ensuring that land, facilities and activities work together to maximize knowledge transfer and positively impact local equine economy.
- Developing and promoting healthy environment, which may also represent EREC's *One Health* mission in support of well-being of researchers, faculty, students, visitors, staff, and horses.

Figure 11: Planning and design process considered for SEREP

The SEREP design and planning process started with regional community analysis, stakeholder engagement and GIS analysis. Identifying potential sites for the future EREC complex has been a priority for the SEREP team. During the first phase of this project, the team has identified several sites for consideration through various stakeholder meetings (in both large/small groups and individual meetings) and the GIS based mapping and evaluation. Site identification process aimed to identify locations where sites will be used most efficiently and new development will not negatively impact critical environmental and cultural resources in the area.

The team then conducted a context-sensitive site analysis evaluating the preliminary site conditions and contextual factors that can sustain the future uses or activities of the EREC complex. This analysis included documentation of site conditions including biophysical features such as topography, soils, geology, and vegetation. The team also mapped the contextual factors, which included physical conditions such as the size of land, access to utilities - water; access to population centers; access to transportation routes; visibility/visual quality; landscape types such as rolling hills, pastures, mature vegetation; adequate soil drainage and quality topsoil; and absence of hazards. Using these factors, strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of each site (SWOT analysis) have been identified. This process enabled the team to rate each site and create a short list including 3 sites for the new EREC complex under consideration.

Figure 12: Site identification and analysis process

The second phase of our efforts focused on understanding the expectations of the equine business community, as well as the preferences for site options, layout, and the aesthetic characteristics and qualities of the future EREC complex. Using the on-line survey administered in October 2017 (as presented in the earlier section), the SEREP team tried to understand how the new EREC complex can achieve a physical environment that effectively supports the key educational and research activities, while providing quality environment and strong identity that are best fit to the character of the region.

The findings from the survey intend to formulate the design and planning principles, which will inform the spatial programming and design scenario development efforts during the next phase of this project.

Site Identification Process

The site identification process was conducted on the basis of the future project uses and activities. Each project program generates site requirements that must be met. These may include minimum parcel size, proximity to transportation routes and utilities, suitable soils, and many other parameters. Hence, the site selection criteria were established during the first phase of the project aiming to help identify alternative sites that can be evaluated and compared before selecting the preferred site(s).

The key driving site selection criteria included:

- **Transportation** – Site(s) within 30’-50’ of an existing road with no more than 1 linear mile away from highway/interstate were considered. Accessibility is an important factor to future employees and visitors of the EREC complex.
- **Soils** – Prime farmland and well-drained soils are preferred to provide ideal pasture conditions. An equestrian research and education center is ideally expected to provide pasture and possibly other types of farmland.
- **Watershed/Floodplains** – The sites that are not within substantially large floodplains are preferred. Constructed area must be 200ft away from surface waters and 200 ft away from floodplain. This is essential in order to protect any substantial property damage during storms and the water quality of streams, rivers, and floodplains. The future site must therefore have space outside of the floodplain to locate structures, as well as an adequate buffer area to separate surface waters from any potential pollution the center might create, such as animal waste and eroded sediment.
- **Slope/Elevation** – The future site will have less than 20% slope. Avoiding steep slopes will protect against erosion, provide safe pasture, and promote ease of access. For an equestrian research and education center complex the site should have minimal slopes to allow for safe horse movement and limit erosion resulting from both horse traffic on pasture and the future development on the site.
- **Canopy/Tree Cover** – The future site, with less than 50% of property, will have tree coverage. It is a priority that the future development will protect against deforestation and damage to natural beauty of the area.
- **Land Use/Zoning** – The future site will have minimum 50 acres and will be 200ft away from residential properties and units.

Figure 13: Identified sites for the future EREC complex

Using GIS based site analysis and the stakeholder input for potential partnerships the following sites have been identified for further consideration:

- F.E.N.C.E (non-profit)
- Green Creek (private)
- Rutherford County (public)
- Tryon Vet Hospital (private)

Additionally, various sources such as multiple listing services for property that is for sale, as well as the GIS analysis of vacant and redevelopable lands were used to identify more sites for consideration. Based on this analysis the following sites was identified:

- Peniel Road (private)

The following section provides further information on the analysis of each site revealing how best each site is suitable for the future EREC complex.

SWOT Analysis

Foothills Equestrian & Nature Center (F.E.N.C.E.)

The F.E.N.C.E. site is owned by a non-profit organization which serves as a community resource for the preservation of green space while providing educational and recreational opportunities linking nature, animals, and people. Located on 356 acres in Tryon, Polk County, FENCE provides programs in nature study, outdoor recreation and equestrian competition through its equestrian facilities and outdoor amenities available on its site. It is a very well-known and visible site in the local community and it is deeply rooted in local equine community.

Soils/Prime Farmland

Water Resources/Floodplains

Transportation Access

Canopy/Tree Coverage

Slope Percentage

Figure 14: Site Analysis

Using the site selection criteria the F.E.N.C.E. site provides the following biophysical and contextual factors:

- Much of the F.E.N.C.E. site has suitable soil for crops/pasture and is considered as a farmland that has statewide and local importance.
- The site contains a medium sized tributary of the Pacolet River, which is currently under a conservation easement, with a limited floodplain and no wetlands.
- The site contains the largest percentage of canopy cover but the areas without canopy are undeveloped providing an opportunity for developing the new EREC complex on the site.
- The site has quite steep slopes but contains a large total acreage of undeveloped area that is not steeply sloping and out of a floodplain.
- The largest roadway in the area (Interstate-26), which runs from Charleston, SC to Kingsport, TN, cuts through the F.E.N.C.E. site. This might be considered as a challenge while considering connectivity between existing and future amenities on the site. However, easy access to this corridor is extremely important for the future development in the area.
- The site is located within a close proximity to major population centers (i.e. Landrum and Tryon).
- The F.E.N.C.E. site provides an opportunity to build on in addition to the existing facilities and infrastructure on the site. The existing natural ecosystem presents recreation and education opportunities in support of the existing and future programs as part of the new EREC complex. However, any future new development on the site can provide increased potential for ecological harm and risk of displacing current community uses on the FENCE site.

Image Credits: Benjamin Jones

Green Creek Site

The Green Creek site is located in Tryon, Polk County. This 183 acres site is owned by the Tryon Equestrian Foundation and the Green River Farm, LLC. The site currently contains limited existing infrastructure (e.g. existing race track) and limited highway access due to its location. It is also surrounded by residential areas.

Soils/Prime Farmland

Water Resources/Floodplains

Transportation Access

Canopy/Tree Coverage

Slope Percentage

Figure 15: Site Analysis

Additionally the site provides the following biophysical and contextual factors:

- The Green Creek site contains the highest percentage of soil suitable for crops and pasture. However, much of the land is currently dedicated to a race track for the Blockhouse Steeplechase.
- The site contains the least water resources, consisting of only medium headwater streams with no area of floodplain or wetland.
- The canopy coverage on the site is limited. However, the site has the most open area, which is currently dedicated to the racetrack for the Blockhouse Steeplechase.
- The site has the lowest percentage of steep slopes. However, most of that flat land is currently dedicated to the racetrack for the Blockhouse Steeplechase.
- The site is only accessible by two lane roads, although one is heavily trafficked locally (Highway 9). There are no nearby interstates or multi-lane highways.

Image Credits: Benjamin Jones

The Henson Rd./US 221 Site (Rutherford County)

This 103 acres of land is owned by the Rutherford County and is located on a major highway in Forest City, in Rutherford County. The site is within close proximity to major population centers including Rutherfordton and Forest City, however it is located farther outside of the existing equine community in the area. It currently has large amounts of cleared land usable for future development, however the site currently has no existing infrastructure available.

Figure 16: Site Analysis

Additionally the site provides the following biophysical and contextual factors:

- Much of the site contains farmland of statewide importance with functional agricultural land.
- The site contains the second least water resources, consisting of multiple headwater streams entering the site with no area of floodplain or wetland.
- The site contains the second highest percentage of canopy cover but the area without canopy is entirely undeveloped.
- The slope across the site increases as you get further away from Highway 221. However, the majority of the site has a consistently minor slope.
- The site is adjacent to Highway 221, a four lane highway and is closer to the freeway (US-74), which is closer than the Greek Creek site.

Image Credits: Benjamin Jones

3344 Peniel Road Site

This 83 acres of property is owned by the Peniel Farms LLC and is located in Tryon. The site is currently valued at approximately \$1.8 million. The site currently does not include much infrastructure except for a housing unit on site.

Soils/Prime Farmland

Water Resources/Floodplains

Transportation Access

Canopy/Tree Coverage

Slope Percentage

Figure 17: Site Analysis

The site provides the following biophysical and contextual factors:

- The site contains the highest concentration of quality soil acreage suitable for crops/pasture out of all the sites examined. Over 85% of the property is considered to be prime farmland.
- The site contains the least amount of water systems on site, consisting of only small headwater streams with no area of floodplain or wetland.
- The site contains the lowest percentage of canopy cover. Most of the canopy is either concentrated around already existing built infrastructure and property edges or is scattered throughout the landscape.
- The site has the lowest percentage of steep slopes out of all the sites examined. Much of the steeper slopes are concentrated along the property edges and existing water systems.
- Even though the only access to the site is along two lane roads, it is a seven-minute drive to a population center (Columbus, NC) as well as a major interstate highway.

Image Credits: wwerealty.com <https://wwerealty.com/property-details/>

Former Tryon Vet Hospital Site

The former Tryon Vet Hospital is the smallest site (6 acres) identified for consideration. The site is owned by the D&M Partners LLC in Columbus, NC. It provides a small amount of land for development with restricted equine use within the property. The site provides not much opportunities for land expansion. It currently contains infrastructure and it is within a very close proximity to population centers including Tryon and Columbus. It is also very close to the ICC Polk Center. Although this site has limited long-term expansion and programming opportunities for EREC's vision, it provides an opportunity to implement the short-term goals and small scale equine based educational activities.

Image Credits: Benjamin Jones

Summary

Overall site identification and analysis process utilized the criteria developed based on the future EREC complex program and the site requirements that must be met. These criteria were also verified by the survey input received from the equine business community residing in the region. The survey results revealed that the prioritized contextual and site specific biophysical features were indeed considered as important factors for the future EREC site complex. All the criteria the SEREP project team set forth were considered as moderately important by the business community. The most important criteria identified were the availability of water resources, proximity to existing equine programs and activities, and proximity to other equestrian and agricultural lands. Among all criteria the two lowest ranked factors considered were the existence of wooded areas on site and the proximity to population centers.

Easy Access to State Highway

Cost of Land

Proximity to Local Equine Suppliers

Size of Land (acreage)

Proximity to Population Centers

Relatively Flat Land

Figure 18: Site characteristics preference and survey findings

Proximity to Existing Equine Programs and Activities

Existence of Wooded/Forested Areas on Site

Proximity to Other Equestrian and Agricultural Lands

Availability of Water Sources

Figure 18: Site characteristics preference and survey findings (cont.)

The SEREP team’s site evaluations were based on the SWOT analysis using the criteria listed earlier. Each site provides unique features related to its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats that are important to consider for future site selection and decision making in the future. Our analysis revealed that FENCE followed by the Green Creek and the Henson Rd./U.S. Hwy 221 sites have the most ideal environmental and contextual conditions out of the five sites that were evaluated. During the next phase of this study the spatial programming elements will be developed in support of the EREC’s vision. The SEREP team will then apply and evaluate how best each of these three short listed sites can accommodate the desired site program.

	Easy access to a state highway	Proximity to local equine suppliers	Proximity to population centers	Proximity to existing equine programs and activities	Proximity to other equestrian and agricultural lands	Availability of water resources	Low cost of land	Adequate size of land	Relatively flat land	Existence of wooded areas or forests on-site	Has existing infrastructure in place	Good quality soils
FENCE	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Light Blue	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red
Green Creek	Orange	Dark Red	Orange	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red
Rutherford Site (U.S. 221)	Dark Red	Blue	Orange	Blue	Blue	Orange	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Light Blue	Dark Red
3344 Peniel Rd. Site	Orange	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Blue	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Orange	Dark Red
Former Vet Hospital	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Orange	Dark Red	Blue	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red	Dark Red

Figure 19: Overall site evaluations

Understanding Preferences on Site Layout and Aesthetic Characteristics

Creating a strong image is important to the development of the future EREC complex. This image through the site's architectural qualities, landscape features, and the overall site layout are expected to be responsive to its surroundings and the unique character of the Appalachian communities. Preserving the natural landscapes and open space characteristics in the area is also a priority. Easy access together with functional programmatic needs such as circulation, safety and function are important aspects of the future site. Movement of people, animals, and vehicles in and around the new EREC complex is very important and should be carefully planned to encourage safe and efficient flow and interaction of researchers, faculty, students, visitors, staff, and horses.

During the second phase of the project, the SEREP team inquired about the preferences of future EREC complex according to site layout, image, as well as the landscape and architectural characteristics. Understanding these expectations before the design phase was important since designing according to the existing character and qualities of the area is a priority set by the stakeholders. These preferences were captured via the online survey questions, among which were images of natural landscapes/horse pastures, equine related facilities, research and education facilities, and the schematic site layout of equestrian facilities.

Series of survey questions presented schematic site layout images, which included scenarios representing variation of site configurations, vegetation density, building configuration and its relation to major road, as well as the building coverage area and the footprint size on the site. Participants were asked to select the sets of images in each category indicating their most preferred site layout options. Majority of the respondents indicated that the future EREC complex should have larger building footprints (62%) and centralized facilities (59%), which will be located further away from the street but visible (74%) surrounded with reasonable amount of natural vegetation (with medium density) and pastures (67%) available on the site. Overall, the selected schematic schemes revealed that respondents prefer site layouts that provide proper transition from road (public space) to pasture (neutral outdoor spaces) and to center (denser building facilities).

62%

Larger Amount of Built Space

38%

Smaller Amount of Built Space

59%

Centralized Facilities

41%

Spread Out Facilities

74%

Further from the Street

26%

Closer to the Street

67%

Less Natural Vegetation & More Pasture

33%

More Natural Vegetation & Less Pasture

Figure 20: Site layout preference survey results

The natural landscapes/pasture instances represented seven images presenting a diverse set of horse pasture types with a unique set of landscape characteristics. Participants were asked to select the image including the features that are the most appropriate for the region's character. 53% of the respondents indicated that the future EREC complex should include open pastures with rolling hills containing limited tree vegetation.

53%

Figure 21: Pasture types preference survey results

Another question aimed to understand the preferences on the architectural style and aesthetic features of the future EREC facilities. Participants were asked to select the image (among seven options) that will be the most appropriate style and fit to the character of the region. The top two preferred images (38%) and (33%) show that people prefer rustic style and wood-panel façade buildings (iconic and grand entry areas) over modern style buildings with flat roofs.

38%

33%

25%

3%

3%

0%

0%

Figure 22: Architectural style and aesthetics preference survey results

Survey participants were also asked to select the image among seven options representing varying horse stable types with varying architectural styles. Majority of respondents (32%) indicated that they prefer common rustic style stables with earth-tone facades and gable roofs over modern ones with flat roofs.

32%

Figure 23: Horse stable types preference survey results

Summary

One of the primary driving planning and design principles of the future EREC complex includes (but not limited to) identifying potential locations and sites with essential landscape characteristics in place and creating a strong image through site layout and its facilities' architectural characteristics. In order to achieve these intentions the online survey was utilized to understand the preferences of local people from the area. The survey findings revealed that there is a strong desire for having the rustic style and timber/wood buildings on the site that will be surrounded with pastures including substantial tree presence. The respondents also indicated their preferences for centralized facilities with larger building masses and located away from the roadside.

They also indicated that the future site should have appropriate amount of natural vegetation with more pasture/open spaces. These findings are expected to provide better quality design that is more representative of local culture and better accepted styles by local stakeholders.

Moving Forward - Design Visioning and Development of Scenarios

Context sensitive site planning and design requires a process to understand relevant site and contextual attributes, thorough analysis of the site conditions, establishment of strong design vision, development of spatial programming in support of future user groups of the site, and development of conceptual design scenarios that will help envisioning the future EREC complex. The next phase will address these steps through the use of design knowledge, graphic skills and values that will aim to decide the future EREC site design. Three short-listed sites including F.E.N.C.E, the Green Creek and the Henson Rd./U.S. Hwy 221 sites will be used in order to demonstrate the application of design principles representing the vision of the future EREC complex. Participatory process involving input from stakeholders will be at the center of each phase.

SUMMARY and NEXT STEPS

Our research and community engagement efforts over the past few months point to a conceptual framework for an equine-based multimodal center that must:

- 1) broadly meet the needs of multiple stakeholders and communities in the isothermal region of North Carolina and beyond
- 2) attract investment from a number of research and academic communities (primarily NC State) as well as other public, private, and philanthropic interests,
- 3) operate through a market-savvy business model that considers research, teaching, and other revenue streams that builds on and supports local equestrian, conservation, and economic activities, and
- 4) leverage the growing national and international attention being generated by the Tryon International Equestrian Center (TIEC).

Over the course of the next few months of SEREP, we will solicit input from all stakeholders on this conceptual framework. This feedback will be incorporated into a proposed model that will delineate both the physical design and operational components of the center. The final report will provide a refinement of the conceptual model along with detailed physical designs that Isothermal communities can use to determine what and how a center can be best realized in the coming years.

REFERENCES

Brookins, C. C., Morais, D., Pasalar, C., Scheunemann, A., Kuss, T., Jones, B. & Ferreira, B. (2017). Southeast equine research and education partnership – an NC state-isothermal community college partnership. Retrieved from <https://serep.wordpress.ncsu.edu/>

Carolina mountain land conservancy and pacolet area conservancy. Retrieved from <https://conservingcarolina.org/who-we-are/>

Choi, J. Y., Reiter, E. M., & Theodori, G. L. (2015). The impact of rurality, community attachment, and community involvement on health among rural texans. *Journal of Rural Social Sciences*, 30(1), 1.

Conserving Carolina.Conserving carolina. Retrieved from <https://conservingcarolina.org/>

Foothills Equestrian Trails Association.Foothills equestrian trails association. Retrieved from <http://www.fetatrails.org/home>

Groves, R. M. (2011). Three eras of survey research. *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 75(5), 861-871.

NC Isothermal Region C. (2017). NC isothermal region C: Economic development plan. Stronger Economies Together Initiative.

NC State College of Veterinary Medicine.One health/ one medicine research at the NC state college of veterinary medicine | NC state veterinary medicine. Retrieved from <https://cvm.ncsu.edu/one-health-one-medicine-research-at-the-nc-state-college-of-veterinary-medicine/>

Padgett, J. E. (2006). An inventory of the significant natural areas of rutherford county, north carolina. Raleigh, NC: North Carolina Natural Heritage Program Office of Conservation and Community Affairs Department of Environment and Natural Resources.

Polk County Parks and Recreation.Polk trails. Retrieved from <https://www.polktrails.org>

Rayner, D. A. (1994). Inventory of the natural areas of the pacolet area: Polk county, north carolina and upper greenville and spartanburg counties, south carolina. [Raleigh, N.C.]: [Conservation Trust for North Carolina].

Region C Workforce Development Board. (2016). The region C economy. Rutherfordton, NC: Isothermal Planning and Development Commission.

Reinhard, E. (2017). Pacolet area conservancy upholds polk county's realms of diversity. Retrieved from <http://thelaurelofasheville.com/outdoors/pacolet-area-conservancy-upholds-polk-countys-realms-diversity-2/>

Rutherford Outdoor Coalition.Rutherford outdoor coalition. Retrieved from <http://www.rutherfordoutdoor.org/>

S, C., J, A., R.C, B., G.D, L., L.J, R., V.D, R., & R, S. (2003). Social capital, attachment value, and rural development: A conceptual framework and application of contingent valuation. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 85(5), 1201-1207. doi:10.1111/j.0092-5853.2003.00530.x

Thacker, C., & Handscombe, B. (2003). Innovation, competitive position and industry attractiveness: A tool to assist SMEs. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, 12(4), 230-239.

Image Sources:**Pasture**

<https://www.shutterstock.com/video/clip-997858-stock-footage-horses-eating-in-the-countryside.html>
<https://georgiapioneers.com/counties/countylumpkin.html>
<http://www.americanforests.org/magazine/article/venerable-trees-of-the-bluegrass/>
<https://cgconstr.com/portfolio/horse-paddock-construction/>
<https://equine.ca.uky.edu/horsepastures>
<http://horse.good.us/horse-farms-for-sale-lexington-ky/>
<https://wallhere.com/en/wallpaper/28101>

Barn

<http://www.barnpros.com/gallery.aspx>
<http://www.sethstein.com/projects/leisure/equestrian-centre-mornington-peninsula-victoria-australia-2/>
http://www.kingbarns.com/Small_Barns.html
<http://www.precisebuildings.com/build/view/califont-nj/93>
<http://www.dustymars.net/horse-barn/>
<http://www.gevico.be/buitenschrijnwerk/paardenstal>
<http://www.spfa.com/project/somis-hay-barn/>

Research Centers

<https://www.travelocity.ca/Whitefish-Hotels-Grouse-Mountain-Lodge.h15527.Hotel-Information>
<http://www.kansaspolymer.com/>
<https://divisare.com/projects/200357-canvas-arquitectos-luis-asin-spanish-portuguese-agricultural-research-center-ciale>
<http://www.rmhgroup.com/projects/laboratories-research/>
<http://csu-cvmb.colostate.edu/academics/clinsci/equine-orthopaedic-research-center/Pages/default.aspx>
<http://www.jacobsenconstruction.com/projects/usu-matthew-hillyard-animal-teaching-research-center/>
<https://www.clarknexsen.com/project/unc-coastal-studies-institute/>

GIS Data & Information Retrieved From:

- Social Explorer
- U.S. Census Bureau
- Libbie Johnson, Tryon Equestrian Directory: First Edition
- OFEI Database
- ESRI World Imagery
- U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) GIS
- NC OneMap Geospatial Portal
- Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA)
- United States Department of Agriculture (USDA), Natural Resources Conservation Service Soils
- Polk County GIS, Henderson County GIS, Rutherford County GIS, Spartanburg County GIS, Greenville County GIS

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We look forward to receiving feedback from stakeholders across communities and sectors in the Isothermal region. Comments and questions should be directed to the NC State SEREP team via email at serep@ncsu.edu or via the project website: <http://go.ncsu.edu/serep>.

SEREP

SOUTHEAST EQUINE RESEARCH & EDUCATION PARTNERSHIP

Envisioning
the Future:

The Southeast Equine
Community & Research Center

Work presented in this book was completed by an interdisciplinary research team including faculty and students from NC State University from February 2017 to December 2018. It complements the previous two interim reports presented through the duration of this project. Previous reports can be downloaded from (<https://serep.wordpress.ncsu.edu/updates/>).

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Foreword

by **Walter H. Dalton**

President, Isothermal Community College
January 2019

Polk County, NC has a rich and dignified history in the equestrian sport dating before its serving as the training ground for the 1956 Olympic Equestrian Team. Venues such as Harmon Field and FENCE have hosted thousands of equestrian competitions in the disciplines of dressage, cross country, show jumping and others. The Block House Steeplechase has been a mainstay of equestrian culture in Polk County for many years and many equestrian farms and businesses dot the landscape of Polk, Rutherford, and surrounding counties in two states.

In 2015, the profile of the equestrian sport was magnified in the area with the advent of Tryon International Equestrian Center (TIEC), an international venue attracting international talent. Some questioned what would happen to existing venues and what would this mean to the amount and nature of growth in Polk County and surrounding areas¹.

The innovative minds of Polk Countian began to engage. Craig Hilton, a citizen of Polk, opined that TIEC was to equestrian as BMW is to automotive. He observed that Clemson University had created ICARS (Clemson University Center for Automotive Research) in the Greenville- Spartanburg area to conduct comprehensive automotive research and to leverage the presence and reputation of BMW and Michelin. With ICARS only 35 miles away, why couldn't our area propose a comparable research center in equine and animal science?

Bill Miller, former Polk County Superintendent of schools, discussed with an Isothermal Community College (ICC) official his concern for existing venues like Foothills Equine and Nature Center (FENCE) and Harmon Field and questioned their long term viability given the impact of TIEC and its growth in activity and facilities. It was suggested that perhaps part of FENCE could be made into an educational campus. These discussions morphed into the idea that perhaps a multidisciplinary facility could be developed, similar to ICARS or the Kannapolis NC Food Research Center, wherein multiple universities would engage in research in collaboration with private researchers from major companies and with Isothermal Community College having a presence to train in technical fields and assist with the operation of the facility and its ongoing activity.

Libbie Johnson, a leader in Polk County and the Equestrian Community, was supportive and encouraging of the idea, as were others, as long as it was compatible and aesthetically pleasing with the bucolic nature of Polk. It was emphasized by all that it should complement, and not compete with, existing businesses. These discussions and more led to Isothermal seeking a grant to study such a research center and to hypothesize how such a center would look; how it would interface and coordinate with existing facilities; and how it might attract researchers and academics to the area. At the same time, such a center should

¹ In 2018, the Tryon International Equestrian Center (TIEC) hosted the World Equestrian Games (WEG) which was attended by seventy countries. TIEC is consistently attracting international traffic and the increased activity has grown the equestrian activity in the area. TIEC and the Foothills Equestrian and Nature Center (FENCE), and Green Creek Farm (proposed venues for the SEREP) are 80 miles from Clemson University, 140 miles from the University of Georgia, and 150 miles from the University of Tennessee. These institutions and more have animal science programs which may be potential partners.

act as a catalyst for students of Polk, Rutherford and the surrounding area to further their education and stay in the area to add to their own quality of life and that of the community.

With that backdrop, ARC graciously and generously gave Isothermal a grant to engage in such a study and Isothermal in accordance with its proposal in the grant application, contracted with NC State to do the study. The contract hypothesizes that the SEREP would have as its primary focus equine research at the university level using a multiple university/collaborative model and also, a component of technical training to be conducted by ICC which would be complementary to the research facilities and the equine economy and related industries in the area. The contract defined a scope of work and established guidelines for the study.

The study would culminate in conceptual drawings and identify, in general terms, financial resources as well as any public/private partnerships which might be formed to take advantage of the SEREP. During the course of the study, it was suggested that such a project be proposed in stages in five year increments over a twenty-year period of time in order to assure all efforts were to scale and sustainable into the future with each phase building upon the other. What follows is the final product from NC State, but not the final work of the committee, which was formed to assist with the grant.

The Committee plans to continue its work to refine proposals and adapt the suggestions of NC State to the original vision and its evolution as dictated by changing circumstances. In the meantime, Isothermal Community College is proceeding with the development of a curriculum in equine studies for an associate of science degree and articulation agreements with four year colleges and universities. Also, Isothermal is proposing a new human services therapy degree based on the horse as a service animal. Physical facilities such as a barn, therapeutic riding ring, and other ancillary facilities are being built, or are proposed to be built, on ICC's main campus. This can fill a void and initiate the process during this deliberative period.

The work of Isothermal in initiating these programs is a step toward the ultimate vision. Time and success, or lack thereof, will dictate whether the scale of the process will be sufficient to support the vision and the timeline for implementation.

These are things the committee will continue to address, assimilating the information derived from the study with its own knowledge and investigation.

Executive Summary

The Southeast Equine Research and Education Partnership (SEREP) and eponymous research study arose from a grant received by Isothermal Community College (ICC) from the Appalachian Regional Commission (ARC). ICC engaged North Carolina State University (NC State) to conduct the study because of its expertise in equine education and because of the “Ultimate Community Partnership” between the two institutions that was ongoing at the time, an intentional community-university partnership between the office of Outreach and Engagement at NC State and the Isothermal community. An interdisciplinary research team from NC State was formed to pursue the scope of work outlined in the contract for the study.

Over a period of two years our team engaged with a number of individual, community, and organizational stakeholders in Rutherford and Polk counties and collected a variety quantitative and qualitative data to determine the feasibility of developing an equine research and education center in the Isothermal region of Western North Carolina. The primary goal was to determine how to take advantage of the long standing but burgeoning equestrian culture and economy in the region in a way that would serve the needs of existing communities, attract investment, create new businesses and jobs, and stimulate university-level research opportunities. This third and final report builds on findings in the [previous two reports](#)¹ and provides a conceptual framework for a comprehensive research and community center focused on horse, human, and environmental health.

The proposed Southeast Equine Community and Research Center would accommodate the equine-related education and research needs of local horse owners and farms, small businesses, and private and non-profit industry. We have provided conceptual and business models, as well as physical design scenarios, that outline a community oriented, economically viable, and environmentally sustainable center for research and education in the area. The center would increase local capacity and provide synergy to the ongoing initiatives by ICC to provide training and other educational opportunities aimed at building the equine workforce. And finally, in the areas of equine-related research, the center would provide an opportunity to leverage the strengths of NC State University in the agricultural, animal, natural, social, and veterinary sciences.

Our research determined that one of the more promising areas of equine-related research, and one for which there are few other centers in the United States, is in equine assisted activities (e.g. riding, learning, psychotherapy). In addition, the agricultural and technology needs of the local areas as well as the state of North Carolina would be well-served by research in the production of premium horse hay and other forages, manure and pasture management, and the development of a variety of agribusiness opportunities. Finally, a center would build on the increased equestrian-related visitors to the region and provide spaces for incubating small businesses and educating local communities and tourists on all aspects of the historical and present day relationship between horses and humans.

¹ Brookins, C. C., Morais, D., & Pasalar, C. (2019, February 12,). Project updates – southeast equine research and education partnership. Retrieved from <https://serep.wordpress.ncsu.edu/updates/>

Economic and community development in rural areas is always challenging but has long been central to the land grant mission of NC State University. We have been inspired by many in the Isothermal region who have long believed that the horse culture and economy there has been underappreciated. Our research affirms this view and provides one pathway for furthering the economic, cultural, and community development that will over time not only benefit the local area, but the entire state of North Carolina and beyond. More immediately, we are confident this report can contribute to the next steps in growing the equine culture and economy in Western North Carolina.

NC State SEREP Research Team

February 2019

Introduction and Overview

The Southeast Equine Research and Education Partnership (SEREP) extends from a contract between North Carolina State University (NC State) and Isothermal Community College via a grant the latter received from the Appalachian Regional Commission. In 2016, the office of University Outreach and Engagement at NC State began a community-university partnership initiative in Polk and Rutherford counties to identify opportunities for the university to engage in intentional and collaborative projects that would significantly address community identified needs. Although a number of economic analyses and reports pointed to economic development opportunities in the region related to agriculture, tourism, and industrial activity (NC Isothermal Region C, 2017; Region C Workforce Development Board, 2016), for a number of reasons, many in these two local communities believed there were opportunities to be explored that could take advantage of the equestrian assets in the region. Moreover, given the economic contribution of the horse industry to the economy of North Carolina, which includes \$2 billion per year and 36,000+ jobs (American Horse Council Foundation, 2018), a focused initiative that connects equine activities across the state would provide added value.

The successful implementation of the future Southeast Equine Community and Research Center and its mission requires a strong and sustainable vision, partnerships, research & educational focus, and physical environment that effectively support and address the equine related needs in the region.

SEREP arose out of these efforts and was intended to explore the feasibility of a multidisciplinary Equine Community and Research Center. The center would build on the historic strengths of the region embedded within its equestrian culture and economy as reflected in the large per capita number of horse owners and farms, equestrian businesses, and recreation and competition centers such as the Foothills Equestrian and Nature Center (FENCE). Further acknowledgement of these strengths was provided when in 2014 the Tryon International Equestrian Center (TIEC) opened what has become one of the premier horse competition parks in the United States. And more recently, TIEC hosted the 2018 World Equestrian Games, the largest horse event in the world, and the largest sporting event in North Carolina history.

The SEREP research team included a multidisciplinary group of researchers in the social sciences, tourism, design, and natural resources, and, in consultation with faculty in animal science, agriculture and veterinary medicine. The goal of SEREP was to provide a conceptual and physical design for a center where private industries, local organizations and residents, and regional academic institutions could work in partnership to enhance the regional equine-based economy and culture. The broader, and admittedly ambitious long term vision of the local communities, is for a facility and farm that would become a world-class center for innovative equine related research and education. Our NC State team began our work with this vision in mind.

Over an 18 month period beginning in March 2017, the NC State SEREP team consulted with a broad range of local stakeholders across both public and private sectors of the isothermal region; identified and analyzed comparable equine research and education facilities across the country that were connected to research universities or the equestrian industry; surveyed and interviewed regional equine businesses and horse owners; reviewed research, education, and training programs that would fulfill regional and statewide needs; and generated physical design scenarios that would be economically and environmentally sustainable, able to generate local business development and jobs, and have the potential to become a world-class center for equine related research that would be significantly connected to the high technology capacity of NC State University and other higher education institutions in the region.

The following sections provide details in each of these areas.

Figure 1. Stakeholder meeting hosted by Isothermal Community College.

Figure 2. Site visit to CORRAL, Cary NC - Therapeutic Riding

The Southeast Equine Community and Research Center (SECRC): Proposed Conceptual Model

A center enabling the collaboration between academia, private industry and local communities for the enhancement of the local equine-based economy's contribution to equitable and sustainable regional development.

The findings from our previous reports (Brookins et al., 2017; Morais et al., 2018) point to the viability of an equine community and research center to be connected to and located within the Isothermal region. The proposed Southeast Equine Community and Research Center (SECRC) would include a multidisciplinary *research hub* that would leverage and support the local equine ecosystem and provide opportunities for innovative research, particularly related to the health of horses, humans, and the environment; a *community village* that provides amenities to enable short and long-term stays for researchers and athletes; and a *business hive* that engages with visitors and community members and enables grassroots equine-based economic development.

Research Hub	The Village	Local Business Hive
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equine health and sciences lab • Smart rural communities lab • Equine manufacturing lab • Equine-assisted therapy lab • Equine-based agribusiness lab 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research and athlete lodging • Horse boarding barns • Food services marketplace • Large group multi-function hall 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visitor and community concierge • Local farmers and artisans market • Regional business incubator • Equine history and science museum

Figure 3. Proposed conceptual model for SECRC.

The Business Case for SECRC

In this section our team drew from findings reported in the previous reports as well as from the team's collective field experience in the study region and on our multi-disciplinary expertise to develop concise business models for each unit. We employed a Business Model Canvas approach to generate and illustrate these business models. Below is an illustration of the content in these Business Model Canvases.

Business Model Canvases

When developing an organization's business model, it is thought through the following flow of questions and variables:

1. Customer segments: The first focus of the business model development process is to identify to whom the organization is creating value. There are likely to be many types of market segments, so in this step it is important to single out the most appealing/important segments.

2. Unique value proposition: A crucial next step is to carefully identify the value that the organization is creating and delivering to each customer segment. Value is created when we solve a customer's problem or meet an unsatisfied need. Unique value propositions are best articulated when they identify an unfair advantage of the organization in contrast with its competitors.

3. Channels: The following focus should be on identifying which channels will be most effective to communicate with the various customer segments. Additionally, in each phase of the interaction with customers (e.g., awareness, purchase, after sales) different channels may be necessary.

4. Customer relationships: Next it is important to characterize the type of relationship that the organization needs to nurture with its customers. Some segments will prefer short transactional exchanges while others will require long-term costly and profitable membership approaches.

5. Revenue streams: Calculating the value customers are willing to pay is crucial to the business model. The revenue streams flesh out how and through which pricing mechanisms the organization is capturing value.

6. Key activities: The organization then must identify key communication, production and relational activities that support the plan.

7. Key resources: In addition to the organization's operations, some resources may be critical to the organization's success. These resources may be physical like facilities, but they may include intellectual property, social capital with partners, and access to human resources.

8. Key partners: Success and impact often requires collaboration, so in this step of the business model development it is time to list key partners of the organization. These partners may contribute with resources, or they may be suppliers, or they may help reduce risk or make the organization connect better with the local community or with customer segments.

9. Cost structure: Lastly it is necessary to enumerate the most significant costs inherent to the proposed business model. The most expensive resources should be identified, as should costly key activities and customer relationship needs.

In sum, the canvas makes it possible to map out the entire business model in one image, which is useful to both start-up entrepreneurs and the most senior business planners. However, it is not sufficient to just enumerate the nine building blocks, given that it is equally important to map them out on a pre-structured framework, which has been termed business model canvas (Osterwalder et al., 2015). The tool has helped entrepreneurs mapping, discussing, designing and inventing new business models, and is widely taught at entrepreneurship programs at the college level.

Figure 4. Business Model Canvas.

Research Hub

The proposed research complex is envisioned as a “hub” that brings together faculty, students, postdocs and research staff from various disciplines and institutions to address major challenges and research questions relevant to areas in equine sciences and equine veterinarian medicine, equitable and sustainable development; equine manufacturing; equine-assisted therapy, and equine-based agribusiness. This hub will aim to foster multidisciplinary research to support the regional and local equine ecosystem; to create innovative and progressive partnerships among universities, industry and community; and to maximize local opportunities by integrating research, teaching, and outreach programs. The physical space will accordingly aim to support interactions among research teams that cycle in and out of the center. Hence, the research facilities will be designed with maximum flexibility accommodating labs, classrooms, workspace and meeting areas to enable interdisciplinary collaboration across research teams.

Equine Health & Sciences Lab

A flexible use wet lab facility for equine sciences and veterinary medicine research; with a residential research herd as well as structural access to a large network of private horses in the region; with a small permanent staff, and earning revenue from fees to research grants.

This facility will include flexible use space for equine sciences, veterinary health, and human health research. It should also include offices, active learning spaces, and wet labs. These spaces will need to have access to horse fields and lodging, and be connected with the Village.

Research teams will pay for facility rental and for the boarding of a research herd. These fees will cover the costs of utilities, building maintenance, and on-demand animal care staffing.

Equine Health & Sciences Lab

Business Model Canvas

Key Partners <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NC State University (CVM, CALS) • Isothermal Community College • Private horse owners in the region 	Key Activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rental of space • Rental of research herd • Liaison with private horse owners 	Value Proposition <p>For equine sciences and equine veterinarian medicine research teams, who struggle with limited access to experimental units (horses), SECRC's Equine Health & Sciences Lab is a flexible use wet lab facility that offers a residential research herd as well as structural access to a large network of private horses in the region.</p> <p>Unlike traditional equine research labs, the Equine Health & Sciences Lab offers an expandable research herd by utilizing private horses when necessary to meet specific research needs, which leads to increased efficiency and reduction in costs.</p>	Customer Relationships <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers are tenants of the facilities for the duration of the contract • Researchers pay to use horses from the residential herd • Researchers can buy access to private horses owned by network of private residents in the region 	Customer Segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research teams from universities in the Southeastern US • Corporate research teams
Key Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lab space • Lab equipment • Boarding of residential research herd • Relationship with a regional network of horse owners • Staff: administrative, research herd caretaker 	Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct marketing • Acknowledgement of SECRC in research publications and presentations involving the lab 	Revenue and Benefits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fees from rental of space for research • Fees from rental of research herd • Fees for access to private horses • Fees for use of facility for Extension and education programs 	Costs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employee salaries (administrative staff, maintenance) • Legal • Utilities • Equipment updates 	

Smart Rural Communities Lab

A central hub for a geographically dispersed network of public institutions and community members involved in data collection and the co-creation of solutions for the region's equitable and sustainable development; with office space for a small staff; earning revenue from fees to research grants, and technical services to local governments.

This lab will provide access to a network of community members involved in data monitoring and available for social science and equine sciences research. The physical facilities' needs are limited to office space but the lab will require significant server and/or cloud space for data storage. An initial set of field equipment (e.g., water quality sensors) will be required and increase over time through externally funded projects.

Research teams will pay fees for access to this geographically dispersed network of participants for their projects. Research teams might pay for access to data collected by this lab. Local government might pay for the provision of dashboard indicators of community health, environmental health and economic development.

Costs will include data management and the staffing of a communities research liaison.

Smart. Communities

Smart Rural Communities Lab

Business Model Canvas

<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Region residents • Civic groups • Local public agencies • Isothermal Community College (facilitate connections with community stakeholders and policy-makers) 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data collection and management • Coordination of data collection partnerships with residents, civic groups and public agencies 	<p>Value Proposition</p> <p>For researchers, who need access to multi-faceted system-wide just-in-time data, SECRC's Smart Rural Communities Lab is a central hub coordinating continuous data collection in cooperation with local residents and agencies that offers access to large longitudinal multi-disciplinary system-wide data sets.</p> <p>Unlike current data sets about rural communities that are time-limited and discipline-specific, the Smart Rural Communities Lab offers large longitudinal multi-disciplinary system-wide data, which enables multi-disciplinary research and policy to effectively address the complex challenges facing rural areas.</p>	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers buy access to data sets • Researchers buy long-term involvement in the lab • Public agencies buy technical reports and advice to inform strategy and policy • Networking between researchers and public agencies will be facilitated 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research teams from universities in the Southeastern US • Public agencies devoted to equitable and sustainable development 	
<p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equipment for automated field data collection (e.g., water quality monitoring robots) • Data storage infrastructure • Staff: community partnerships and data science research associate 		<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct marketing • Acknowledgement in research publications and presentations involving the lab 		<p>Revenue and Benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sale of data sets • Fees from research fellow memberships • Sale of technical reports 	
<p>Costs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employee salaries • Compensation of participating residents, civic organizations and local public agencies • Server and/or cloud space for data storage and management • Field equipment update 					

Equine Manufacturing Lab

A multi-purpose facility for materials testing and applied engineering research, serving a regional consortium of equine manufacturing industry members; earning revenue from consortium membership fees, testing services, and fees to research grants.

This facility will include a multi-purpose lab conducting materials testing and applied engineering research. The facility is envisioned as a large open space adaptable to various types of projects.

Principal Investigators will include facility rental fees in their grants. Equine manufacturing companies in the region (e.g. footing, horse trailer manufacturers) may also outsource R&D projects to this lab with contracts or in the form of a long-term consortium.

Costs will include facility utilities and maintenance, as well as flexible animal care staffing. Basic equipment may be needed and additional specialized equipment may be included in grants.

Manufacturing.

Equine Manufacturing Lab

Business Model Canvas

<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NC State (COE) • Isothermal Community College (SBDC) (connections with SMEs; collaboration in grants) • Local equine equipment industry consortium 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rental of space • Facilitation of partnerships between local equine manufacturing industry and research teams 	<p>Value Proposition</p> <p>For product research and development teams from local SMEs, who can't afford in-house test facilities, SECRC's Equine Manufacturing Lab is a multi-purpose lab facility for materials testing and applied engineering research that offers a large open space adaptable to various types of projects, access to qualified research teams and a broad spectrum of basic and specialized equipment.</p> <p>Unlike in-house test facilities, the Equine Manufacturing Lab does not require high initial investment and operational costs, which leads to a reduction in R&D expenditures and accelerates business innovation.</p>	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers are tenants of the facilities for the duration of the contract • Networking between researchers and members of the industry consortium will be facilitated 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research teams from universities in the Southeastern US • Product research and development teams from local SMEs
<p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lab space • Lab equipment • Staff: technical equipment operation and maintenance 		<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct marketing 		
<p>Costs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employee salaries (administrative staff, maintenance) • Legal • Utilities • Equipment updates 		<p>Revenue and Benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fees from rental of space to research teams working on contracts • SBTDC grants to subsidize R&D services to local industry consortium • Fees for use of facility for education programs 		

Equine-Assisted Therapy Lab

An equine-assisted therapy indoor/outdoor facility designed to optimize and observe the structured interaction of humans with horses for the study of their effect on human health; with a small residential research herd as well as collaborations with a network of therapy programs in the region; earning revenue from therapy services to public and private clients as well as fees from research grants.

Over the last 30 years equine assisted therapy has evolved into a dynamic therapeutic option (Bizub, Joy & Davidson, 2003). Utilizing equines in therapeutic settings has garnered much national and international attention as the application of, and outcomes associated with, horse and human interaction becomes a more common intervention for the treatment of a variety of physical, cognitive, and mental health issues. Although research in this area is emerging, it spans the human experience, including: victims who have experienced sexual violence (Kemp, Signal, Botros, Taylor & Prentice, 2014), veterans (Lanning & Krenek, 2013), children (Lentini & Knox, 2015), individuals with PTSD (McCullough, 2011), at-risk youth (Burgon, 2011; Maujean et al. (2013)), people with autism (Anderson & Meints, 2016), people with cerebral palsy (Zadnikar & Kastrin, 2011), court involved youth (Hemingway, Meek & Hill, 2012), patients with eating disorders (Christian, 2005) and business executives (Kelly, 2014). Research in these areas would be a key component of the SECRC, directly benefit the equine assisted activities in both the region and North Carolina, and has the potential to become a world leader in research on Equine Assisted Activities. See Appendix # for a more thorough review of this research.

This lab will include indoor space for interaction between therapists and their human participants, paddocks specially designed for the participants' interactions with horses, and easy access to horse boarding areas where participants can care for the horses. The facility should also have easy access to the public areas of the Hive so that family, friends and public can observe the programs.

Principle Investigators will include facility rental fees, the boarding of a therapy herd, and perhaps human participant incentives in their grants. The lab can generate programming revenues when providing services to local government institutions (e.g., school system, juvenile penal system), or to other organizations (e.g., wounded warrior program). Additionally, many equine-assisted programs have a strong record of securing philanthropic contributions by donors.

Costs will include facility utilities and maintenance as well as flexible animal care staffing. Specialized/certified equine therapy staff will be needed.

Equine-Assisted Activities Research Lab

Business Model Canvas

Key Partners <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equine Assisted Activities programs in the region and state of North Carolina • Isothermal Community College (collaborations in hands-on education and training) • Foothills Equestrian and Nature Center (FENCE) 	Key Activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Therapy programs • Training and certifications of equine-assisted practitioners (Therapists, Equine Specialists, Educators) • Networking of equine assisted activity practitioners • Evidence-based research on equine assisted activities 	Value Proposition <p>For organizations requiring equine-assisted therapy for their clients and a valid assessment of its impacts on the patients, SECRC's Equine-assisted Research and Therapy lab offers therapy programs by certified staff and the assessment of outcomes by multi-disciplinary and experienced researchers.</p> <p>Unlike other equine-assisted therapy programs that lack the capacity to monitor the impacts of their programs, this lab offers paid therapy programs with an evaluation process and specialized researchers that monitor impact, which enables clients to document the impact on their clients to justify funding.</p>	Customer Relationships <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prospective customer organizations are invited to visit the lab to learn about therapy methods and impact evaluation research methods • Customers of therapy services enroll for mid and long-term programs 	Customer Segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • US Military veterans and wounded warrior programs • Schools systems • Youth at Risk and Adjudicated Youth organizations • Individual families with children or adults in need of therapy • Individuals who have experienced trauma or abuse • Equine-assisted activities/programs
Key Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-house therapy herd • Staff: Psychotherapists, Equine Specialists, Therapeutic Riding Instructors, Barn Manager 	Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct marketing • Active participation in academic forums • Organized network of equine-assisted programs in NC 	Revenue and Benefits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fees from therapy programs • Fees from training programs (for practitioners) • Fees from research grants 	Costs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employee salaries (administrative staff, maintenance, therapist) • Veterinarian & Farrier costs for therapy herd • Legal costs- Insurance costs • Utilities • Boarding of residential therapy herd 	

Equine-Based Agribusiness Lab

A facility for research exploring solutions for leveraging the equine-based economy for local equitable and sustainable development, with office space and structural connections to a regional network of farmers, horse owners, venues and public institutions; earning revenue from fees to research grants, and services provided to local public institutions.

This lab will facilitate multi-disciplinary research examining and enabling local supply chains of products and services for the equine-based economy. One of the most clear areas is the production and sale of forage for sport horses. In this context, this lab will seek soil and crop science solutions for the production of high-value forages, for the adoption of these crops by local farmers, for the consumer adoption of these local forages, and for their seamless retail to local markets (i.e., private horse owners and equine sports venues). The physical facilities needs are limited to office space, and access to the Village's Large group multi-function barn for workshops, networking events and meetings.

Research teams will pay fees for the lab's role in economic development and ag development grants. Neighboring Extension offices may pay fees to the lab for the organization of training workshops.

Costs will consist mostly of staffing.

Equine. Economy

Equine-Based Agribusiness Lab

Business Model Canvas

<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NC State University (CALs, PCOM, CNR) • Cooperative Extension • TIEC and other equine sports venues and organizations • Isothermal Community College (connections with key stakeholders) 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rental of lab space • Rental of experimental plots • Liaison with local growers, agricultural support organizations, equine supplies retailers, and consumer groups 	<p>Value Proposition</p> <p>For multidisciplinary research teams exploring solutions for leveraging the equine-based economy for equitable and sustainable development, who struggle with limited access to actors across the spectrum of the equine-based agribusiness supply-chain, SECRC's Equine-based Agribusiness Lab offers access to growers, support organizations, retailers and consumers willing to participate in research projects.</p> <p>Unlike traditional agribusiness research initiatives, the Lab is structured as a gateway to the complex equine agribusiness supply-chain in the region, which affords the opportunity to conduct multi-disciplinary research that integrates production, distribution and consumer behavior components.</p>	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers are tenants of the facilities for the duration of the contracts • Researchers pay to use experimental plots • Lab will nurture relationships with growers and consumer groups through networking events and communications 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research teams from universities in the Southeastern US • Corporate research teams • Forage growers and their support organizations • Horse owners and equine sports venues
<p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lab space • Lab equipment • Experimental plots • Relationship with a regional network of growers • Staff: administrative, maintenance 	<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct marketing • Acknowledgement in research publications and presentations involving the lab • Direct relationships and contacts with ag product industry and with consumer groups 	<p>Revenue and Benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fees from rental of space lab for research • Fees from rental of experimental plots • Fees for use of facility for Extension and education programs 	<p>Costs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employee salaries (administrative staff, maintenance) • Legal • Utilities • Events and communications 	

The Village

In support of the proposed research hub, the “Village” will incorporate shared facilities, outdoor spaces, and lodging for postdocs, students, faculty, research staff, athletes and visitors; horse boarding barns; a food services marketplace for guests of the village, and multi-functional community hall for large events including conferences and workshops. The village will serve as a place where researchers and visitors can relax and connect with each other. It will also provide stalls designed to host primarily research and therapy horses and herds.

Researcher, Athlete and Visitor Lodging

Self-catered lodging operation with multiple short and long-term rental units designed to host researchers, students, equestrian athletes, and tourists; providing convenient access to the center’s facilities and to neighboring venues and communities; earning revenue from rentals.

The Center will have a cluster of 10 homes lodging between 6 and 10 people, each with two rooms, a living area and a self-catering kitchen. The homes should have a space appropriate for work/office/reading. The cottages should be designed to accommodate long-term tenants (e.g., a researcher during a semester fieldwork) as well as short-term visitors (e.g., team of athletes staying during weekend event). The cottages will be geographically clustered around a common area that has an open group kitchen so that groups staying in various cottages can make and enjoy group meals and meetings. The cottages should have easy access to the public entrance and the research facilities.

The target markets for the Village will be collegiate equine sports teams during their October to March season; equine sports teams competing during the regular April to October season; research teams working in studies in the facility and in the region; other researchers spending extended periods of time conducting research in the facility or region; and groups of visitors participating in conferences and meetings in the facility.

Food catering for the village will be provided by local pre-approved companies on demand - i.e. when cottages are rented the guests can solicit the provision of a variety of food services ranging from provision of breakfast/lunch boxes, locating a breakfast cart in the facility, organize a food truck rodeo for dinner, providing a box of produce for a week, etc.

Costs of this unit will include maintenance, utilities and cleaning. There will be need for a reservations staff, and someone to do check-ins and check-outs - new mobile check-in models should be used.

Research, Athlete and Visitor Lodging Business Model Canvas

<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local cleaning services companies • FENCE • TIEC • Local food services providers • Isothermal Community College (hospitality training programs) 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accommodation • Food services 	<p>Value Proposition</p> <p>For high-school and collegiate equestrian teams, who struggle to find team-friendly accommodation close to horse boarding establishments, lodging at SECRC is has the capacity to house all members of a large team as well as board the horses in the same site.</p> <p>Unlike regular hotels and inns' double units which cause teams to separate, SECRC offers a mix of contiguous private and bunk bed rooms in the same facility, respectively for coaches and athletes, eliminating the hassle and inconvenience of overnighing in regular hotels among other guests, often miles apart from the team's horses, which leads both to a reduction in stress and increased supervision over staff, athletes and horses.</p>	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customers are guests of the center 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resident researchers • Visiting researchers • Equestrian teams • Participants in conferences and workshops
<p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proximity to research facilities • Proximity to stables • Large Rooms with Bunk Beds 	<p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proximity to research facilities • Proximity to stables • Large Rooms with Bunk Beds 	<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online marketing through the center's website • Lodging metasearch websites • Direct marketing on-site 	<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online marketing through the center's website • Lodging metasearch websites • Direct marketing on-site 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resident researchers • Visiting researchers • Equestrian teams • Participants in conferences and workshops
<p>Costs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employee salaries • Utilities • Outsourced cleaning services • Linen and furniture updates • Food services 	<p>Revenue and Benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daily charges by unit/person 	<p>Revenue and Benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daily charges by unit/person 	<p>Revenue and Benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daily charges by unit/person 	<p>Revenue and Benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daily charges by unit/person

Horse Boarding Barns

Horse boarding operation with 100 stalls designed to host research and therapy herds as well as visiting athlete horses; earning revenue from fees to grants and therapy programs.

The Center will have 100 stalls to accommodate a permanent research herd, a therapy herd and temporary stays. The facility will need a barn for the storage of materials and equipment. Short term boarding will be mainly for horses participating in competitions nearby, as well as for horses being evacuated from extreme weather events. The facility will be structured in semi-independent sections to accommodate regulations and best practices for the biosecurity of the various herds. In addition, the facility will be designed considering sustainability and horse wellbeing best practices to ensure the welfare of horses and the local environment.

Costs of this unit will include maintenance, utilities and cleaning. There will be need for a reservations staff, and someone to do check-ins and check-outs - new mobile check-in models should be used.

Research.
Therapy.

Horse Boarding Barns

Business Model Canvas

Key Partners <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TIEC (overflow) • FENCE (overflow) • Isothermal Community College (grooming and ferrier internships) 	Key Activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Horse Boarding 	Value Proposition <p>For equestrian teams and private horse owners in transit through the region, who struggle to find horse boarding establishments close to their lodging, the SECRC Horse Boarding Barns provide convenient boarding for horses and lodging for their humans in the same site.</p> <p>Unlike regular horse boarding facilities which cause horses and owners/athletes to separate, SECRC offers flexible stables rentals for single and multiple horses near lodging facilities, which enables owners/athletes/teams to remain close to their horses.</p>	Customer Relationships <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forums 	Customer Segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research teams • Equestrian teams
Key Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stables and equipment 	Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct marketing 	Revenue and Benefits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boarding fees 		
Costs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employee salaries • Feed, Wood Chips • Utilities • Maintenance • Manure Disposal 				

Food Services Marketplace

Online marketplace for local catering companies to list their food services to guests of The Village; with designated indoor and outdoor areas for the provision of food services; earning limited income from membership fees of vetted catering companies.

Institutional food operations are often costly and they often fail to meet customers' ever-evolving preferences. In addition, such institutional food services often fail to source locally and therefore they yield limited trickle down economic benefits to local farmers and micro-businesses. Accordingly the Center will provide food services to staff, residents and visitors through a coordinated outsourcing with local food businesses. The center will use a web-based application for local food businesses to offer their services and for consumers and the Center to book and rate them. Namely, guests of the Village will be able to specify whether they are interested in local farm produce boxes for their self-catering stay, and whether they would like to buy catered meals or food trucks/carts. Likewise, organizers of events in the Center will be able to shop for catering services provided by local companies.

This model will increase the local socio-economic impact of the Center on the local farms and small businesses and will reduce the costs and risk of operating the Center. Cost will consist on the development and integration of the online marketplace in the information and reservation systems supporting the Center; as well as the maintenance of the Center's cooking facilities. Revenues will consist of a small registration fee by interested local food companies, as well as a small percentage of sales.

Food. Marketplace

Food Services Marketplace

Business Model Canvas

<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chambers of commerce; Isothermal Community College SBDC (mentor small food companies) • Extension (mentor farmers to provide produce boxes) 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mediate booking of food services • Collect and manage customer reviews of food service companies 	<p>Value Proposition</p> <p>For local restaurants and catering companies, food trucks and farmers which struggle to focus their commercial efforts in activities with predictable revenue, the SECRC Food Services Marketplace provides an opportunity to make their products and services available to consumers on a by-reservation basis.</p> <p>Unlike other opportunities in which food services companies participate in events with the uncertainty of sales, SECRC customers book food services from their preferred companies ahead of time, which give these companies the assurance of revenue.</p>	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking with food services companies to clarify expectations • Monitor reviews to ensure service quality 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Restaurants • Catering companies • Food trucks • Farmers
<p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Village's self-catering kitchen • Convenient food truck and food cart parking locations • Web application integrated with Center's information and reservations system 	<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct marketing - food services booking integrated into the Center's lodging and events reservation system 	<p>Costs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance of web-based application 	<p>Revenue and Benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Registration fees from interested food services companies and farmers • Small percentage of sales 	

Large Group Multi-Function Community Hall

A multi-purpose facility, serving as venue for special events, conferences and workshops; with easy access to lab facilities and to equine sports venues; earning income from rental of space.

This unit will consist of a facility available to rent for special events, conferences and workshops. The facility will be designed facing the pastures and enclosures so as to make patrons feel embedded in the equine center. Events may include observations and hands-on activities in the various labs of the Research Hub, therefore the venue will be located within convenient access to the labs. Food services to the facility will be provided by local approved catering companies, therefore the venue will have a convenient entry and food prep facility for these companies. The organization of the venue space will be flexible allowing for large group format and small-group working rooms.

These facilities will be available to rent for a fee. A list of local pre-approved event planning companies and catering companies will be allowed to operate in the facility.

Sharing. Community

Large Group Multi-Function Community Hall

Business Model Canvas

<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TIEC • Fence • Isothermal Community College (vet local event and training companies) 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rental of conference space 	<p>Value Proposition</p> <p>For research, Extension, community and equine sport organizations struggling to find venues for equine-related events, the Large Group Multi-function Hall is a venue suitable for conferences and workshops that is integrated in SECRC's equine complex and offers convenient access to labs, pastures, and the museum.</p> <p>Unlike other event spaces in hotels and institutional venues located in urban areas, SECRC's venue is integrated in the equine research and education campus, which allows customers to engage event participants in experiential components.</p>	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customers rent the facilities and hire additional support services from local companies (e.g., catering) • Socialization of the facility among select local and regional institutions 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research, Extension, community and equine sport organizations • Event planners
<p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilities • Curated access to other areas of the Center 	<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct marketing 	<p>Costs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilities • Facility upgrades 	<p>Revenue and Benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fees from rental of space 	

Local Business Hive

In support of the main mission of this Center the local business “hive” aims to provide dynamic opportunities that will optimize the cultural and entrepreneurial activities enabling grassroots equine-based economic development in the local communities. This area will be designed as the front door to the region and will include community oriented multi-purpose facilities and outdoor spaces, such as a visitor center, local farmers and artisans market, business incubator, and equine history and science museum.

Visitor and Community Concierge

A facility welcoming and assisting visitors to the center and to the region with general information, communication with local businesses, and navigation; funded by local government.

The SECRC must serve as a welcoming point dispersing visitors to the rest of the region so as to avoid an enclave tourism development process that will cluster economic growth within the I-74 corridor and to TIEC. The Visitor & Community Concierge area of the Center will aim to advise visitors to the multitude of services, attractions and experiences available in the region and in this way, the Center will help disperse tourism revenue opportunities among the small companies and tourism coops in the region. Often new and long-time local residents are unaware of the interesting activities available in their regions, so this Concierge service will also help local communities experience the natural, agricultural, cultural and equine-related activities available.

The Visitor and Community Concierge will help raise overnight stays in the region; accordingly, this unit will be funded in partnership with regional Tourism Development Authorities which in turn are funded by occupancy tax. During high-flow periods, the Concierge area will also potentially include booths from local tourism business cooperatives/associations interested in the opportunity to reach out to visitors directly. Participating businesses and business coops and associations may be charged participation fees; which in turn may be subsidized through economic development grants.

Visitor and Community Concierge

Business Model Canvas

<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • County governments (support collaboration) • NC State (monitoring fairness of voice and access) 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rental of space to tenants • Collaborative efforts to make the Concierge space representative of the regional equine destination and culture 	<p>Value Proposition</p> <p>For regional tourism development authorities, businesses and associations, which struggle to reach visitors with direct marketing efforts, SECRC's Visitor & Community Concierge is a welcoming bottleneck of visitor traffic where visitors can be engaged in in-depth discussions about things to do in the region.</p>	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking events among regional tourism organizations and businesses 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional Tourism Development Authorities • Local tourism businesses and business associations
	<p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Goodwill among regional tourism organizations and businesses 	<p>Unlike other visitors centers that provide information about limited areas and receive scant visits due to their narrow geographic scope, SECRC's Visitor and Community Concierge engages visitors with information about the entire regional equine destination and invites the participation of local businesses, which make it more effective at influencing visitor behavior and spending.</p>	<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct marketing 	
<p>Costs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance and utilities 				
				<p>Revenue and Benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rental of space paid by local tourism organizations and businesses (fees might be subsidized by grants)

Local Farmers and Artisans Market

A marketplace where local farmers and artisans can easily offer their products to visitors of the center and the region; earning revenue from small fees paid by participating businesses.

As a welcoming point receiving and introducing visitors to the broader equine region, the SECRC will have an area in which farmers and artisans be accessible to the high flow of visitors. The market will have small customer-contact units and also larger areas selling through cooperative agreements or as consignment.

Individual and groups of farmers and artisans will pay rent of space to showcase and sell their food products and crafts to visitors. This component of the Center will generate revenue for utilities and maintenance; and it will partially fund programming coordinator that will engage with community groups and hospitality industry in the region to encourage the flow of visitors and community members through the center.

Farmers. Artisans

Local Farmers and Artisan Market

Business Model Canvas

<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extension offices • Local agriculture organizations • Local arts organizations 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rental of retail space • Communications and other forms of collaborative engagement with tourism industry and community organizations to generate flow of visitors and residents 	<p>Value Proposition</p> <p>For farmers and artisans, which struggle to find direct retail space in equine venues or have a difficult time drawing customers to their homes or small retail units spread out through the region, the SECRC market is a high-flow point of visitors and residents that offers a affordable and flexible retail space for rent.</p> <p>Unlike retail units for rent in neighboring equine sports venues that are priced to target high-end brands and large outside retail companies, and unlike small farms and art studios that are scattered, the SECRC Local Farmers and Artisans Market will be affordable to tenants and convenient to visitors, which will enable micro-ventures in the region to afford reaching visitors and residents with effective direct marketing efforts.</p>	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking opportunities for farmers and artisan tenants 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual farmers and artisans • Groups, associations and coops of farmers and artisans
<p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexible, modular retail space 	<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct marketing 	<p>Costs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staff salaries • Utilities and maintenance 	<p>Revenue and Benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rental fees 	

Regional Business Incubator

A collaborative work environment with shared meeting space and business services, front stage access to visitors, and structured networking and capitalization opportunities; engaging local startups involved in the equine-based economy; earning revenue from office space rental to startups, from economic development grants, and private/public business development partnerships.

In accordance with NC State's commitment to translate scholarship into economic innovation, and indeed in accordance with best practices of impactful universities, the SECRC will include a startup incubator with the goal to fuel the incubation and development of companies that leverage the scholarship being developed in the center, and the burgeoning equine-based economy in the region. The business incubator will consist of a collaborative working space for local startups broadly related to the regional equine-based economy. The physical space will be designed following the emerging best practices in this type of initiative with small modular office spaces for rent and large common shared spaces for collaborative work, social events, and to conduct meetings.

The incubator will be supported by membership fees of various levels to meet the needs and capabilities of startups at progressive levels of development, size, and capital. The incubator can also find support through grants, the support of institutions like Isothermal Community College's Small Business Development Center, financial sector private sponsors from Charlotte, and the facilitation of investment capital.

Collaborative.

Regional Business Incubator Business Model Canvas

Key Partners <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NC State University • Isothermal Community College (nurturing of local innovators) 	Key Activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organize networking events for startups, customers, investors and companies • Facilitate support services to the startups by local partners 	Value Proposition <p>For local equine startups, which struggle to find affordable space that enables networking and access to investors and customers, SECRC's Regional Business Incubator is a collaborative work space that offers modular offices and shared facilities and resources at a range of prices, which enables small companies to access work space appropriate to their developing stages.</p> <p>Unlike other office spaces in which each tenant must cover all their business functions, SECRC's Regional Business Incubator dilutes the cost of meeting space and business functions among all its tenants and passes those savings to the tenants, with the added advantage of fostering networking, cross-pollination of business innovation and supply-chain collaboration, which leads to increased entrepreneurial success.</p>	Customer Relationships <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networking events • Business pitch competitions and networking events 	Customer Segments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Startup companies • Business development organizations • Investment groups
	Key Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modular office space and collaborative working space • Relationships with business development partners • Relationships with investment groups 		Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct marketing 	
Costs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilities and maintenance • Organization of periodic events and catering • Staffing (external and internal communications; programming) 	Revenue and Benefits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Membership fees paid by tenants 			

Equine History and Science Museum

An engaging museum with exhibits about the local equine history as well as exhibits educating patrons about discoveries and innovations developed by NC State and other participating institutions; targeting the local population as well as tourists and serving as a learning lab for interpretation and science communication academic teams; earning revenue from industry sponsorships, private philanthropic donations, heritage conservation grants, space rental for events, and visitor fees.

The SECRC will have a sciences museum where the public will be able to experience first hand the innovations pursued by NC State researchers and other research teams involved with the various labs in the Research Hub. Additionally, the museum will include permanent exhibits on the equine history of the area in partnership with key equine sports partners and with other grassroots equine culture organizations.

The facility will be designed so as to enable the hosting of events, which will help fund its operations. Additionally, the museum can be supported through corporate sponsorships, philanthropy, and small visitor fees. The museum may highlight the role and achievements of key organizations that have fueled the region's rich equine heritage, and those exhibits may be funded by those organizations. The museum is also envisioned as a STEM learning lab in which teams in the Research Hub can interact with the public (i.e. community residents, school groups, equine tourists) to educate them about the scientific advances they have pursued - these efforts may be included in research grants and will help fund the museum operations.

Culture.

Learning Lab

Equine History and Science Museum

Business Model Canvas

<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NC State University (development of exhibits) • Isothermal Community College (liaison with community organizations to develop equine heritage exhibits) • Equine sports organizations (contribute with exhibits) 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work with partners to create and host equine science and heritage exhibits • Facilitate networking and collaborations among stakeholders 	<p>Value Proposition</p> <p>For equine sports enthusiasts visiting the region and interested in engaging activities in addition to spectating events, which struggle with finding things to do, SECRC's Equine History and Science Museum is an attraction that offers fun and engaging opportunities to learn about equine sciences innovations and the rich equine heritage of the region.</p> <p>Unlike other attractions showcasing the history of isolated communities or equine organizations, SECRC's Equine History and Science Museum offers state-of-the-art engaging exhibits that involves its visitors in experiences in fun and educational ways, which leads to more satisfying visitor experiences.</p>	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobile exhibits to surrounding communities • Newsletter to "friends of the museum" • Invitation events for donors 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Residents and tourists visiting region • School groups and homeschooling groups • Equine sports events organizations • Research teams • Equine heritage groups
<p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Museum space • Relationships with research and equine sports partners 		<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct marketing • Event partnerships • Targeted advertising • Packaging deals with tourism and equine events partners 		<p>Revenue and Benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visitor fees • Industry sponsorships • Private philanthropic donations • Heritage conservation grants • Space rental for events
<p>Costs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staffing salaries (curator, support and visitor services staff) • Utilities and maintenance • Updating exhibits 		<p>Revenue and Benefits</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visitor fees • Industry sponsorships • Private philanthropic donations • Heritage conservation grants • Space rental for events 		

Synergies Between SECRC Units

In order to grasp the real potential of SECRC as a driver of economic revitalization to the area, it is crucial to not only to have a clear understanding of the individual business models of each one of its thirteen independent units, but also the synergies between them. The conceptual model emerging from our interactions with stakeholders, and later operationalized in the design of this facility, gives life to the center, in the way there are symbiotic relationships between its units that not only contribute to Center's vibrancy but are also instrumental to the sustainability and economic viability of the project.

Accordingly, Figure 5 illustrates that each unit has ties with several other units, which reflects the interdependent nature of the center.

Figure 5. Relationships between units

- Equine health & sciences lab. Relies on the Village for researchers' food and accommodation, horse boarding, and conferences. The business incubator commercializes technology developed at the lab.
- Smart rural communities lab. Relies on the Village for researchers' food and accommodation and conferences. Sophisticated data-driven local management practices are displayed at the museum for visitors to visualize how the equine-based economic system impacts the region's society, ecology and economy.
- Equine manufacturing lab. Relies on the Village for researchers' food and accommodation. The business incubator commercializes solutions developed at the lab.
- Equine-assisted therapy lab. Relies on the Village for researchers' food and accommodation, as well as horse boarding. The visitor & community concierge will market and sell equine-assisted therapeutic solutions available to the general public.
- Equine-based agribusiness lab. Relies on the Village for researchers' food and accommodation, horse boarding, and conferences. The business incubator commercializes technology developed at the lab. The lab will collaborate with farmers at the Village's market in research projects aimed at optimizing the sector's supply chain.
- Research and athlete lodging. Provides accommodation to fellows and teams working in the Research Hub, as well as to owners of private horses boarded at the center. In terms of food, guests are welcome to use the food marketplace or the farmer's market. The visitor & community concierge will market and sell lodging products.
- Horse boarding barns. Provides boarding for the resident research herd as well as therapy horses. It enables teams and horse owners in transit to stay close to their horses.
- Food services marketplace. Provides food services to the research hub and the lodging unit. It has the potential to cater events at the multifunction hall. Some food items can be purchased through the farmer's market.
- Large group multifunction hall. It serves the research hub by being a privileged space for organizing conferences and workshops. Participants from other research centers can stay at the lodging unit. It can use the food services marketplace for catering services. The visitor center will have an important role in marketing the facility as an event venue. Finally, the incubator can use the space for business pitch competitions, shark tank events, or launching products and startups.
- Visitor & community concierge. It will actively promote the center and sell its many services, such as horse therapy, lodging, horse boarding, the multifunction hall, the artisans and farmers market, and the equine museum.
- Local farmers & artisans market. It will supply the food marketplace with ingredients grown locally, and the lodge with boxes of produce in the case of long rentals. It will collaborate with the agribusiness research lab for optimization of the supply chain.
- Regional business incubator. It is going to serve startups that develop and market products based on technologies developed at the research hub, and it will utilize the multifunction hall for its business events.
- Equine history and science museum. Receives people coming through the visitors' center. It will showcase advances in equine based-research achieved at the center.

Analysis of the independent business model of each of the 13 units of the center reveals a fairly balanced portfolio of business activities that range from higher control and lower risk to lower control and higher risk, which means that there are opportunities for different breeds of investors or the ability to provide balanced investment opportunities to single investors who wish to take on more than one product.

Envisioning the Future SECRC Site

The Southeast Equine Community and Research Center (SECRC) is designed to integrate research, education, and community services in equine related activities and assisted therapies with hands-on experience. This center will create a cutting edge place where communities are served, students can learn, and multi-disciplinary scientists can conduct research on equine health and science, equine-assisted therapy, environmental health, equine manufacturing, agri-business, and smart rural development. This multi-faceted center through its facilities and landscapes will provide cutting edge research opportunities for multi-disciplinary teams in support of region's equine related needs. While supporting regional research endeavors, the Center will also provide spaces to support the Isothermal Community College's equine focused curricular and research activities.

Conceptual Design Vision

Using the proposed framework, a conceptual master plan that addresses the design vision was developed. This framework and supporting master plan were formulated as a result of the feasibility study and the input received from the key stakeholders, such as the Isothermal Community College (ICC) and the equine community during the duration of the project. The philosophy behind the planning and design of the proposed Southeast Equine Community and Research Center (SECRC) is to create facilities and open spaces that reflect the needs of the equine focused educational and research activities, as well as to create spaces that engage the community. The proposed conceptual master plan and the design program solely reflect a vision that enables the collaboration between academia, private industry and local communities for the enhancement of the local equine-based economy and its contribution to equitable and sustainable regional development. This proposed conceptual plan reinforces the core component of the SECRC mission and its vision – education, research, culture, partnerships, health and wellness – by expressing them in overall site and building design concepts.

This vision together with the proposed conceptual facilities and outdoor spaces will provide a place guiding the future efforts to formalize partnerships among key stakeholders designated through this effort.

Hence, this document proposes a visionary framework, which resulted from a process that helped to identify the equine related needs in the region. These needs were then organized in a systematic way informing the development of a new equine-focused education and research center. Using design thinking process, as well as placemaking principles, the SEREP team developed a spatial program and a conceptual site design scenario that aim to support the future research and education activities in a premier equine education and research center complex that can become a focal place for various community based equine services in the region. The key planning and design principles guiding the future SECRC site include:

- Providing accessible, quality, cutting edge, flexible, and adaptive facilities and outdoor environment that will reflect SECRC’s strong and innovative vision for evolving research, education and community based services.
- Prioritizing sustainability that will minimize pollution, energy and water use supporting sustainable land management for research, teaching, farming, natural areas, and other uses.
- Ensuring land, facilities, and activities work together to maximize knowledge transfer and positively impact local equine economy and sustainable development in the region.
- Developing and promoting healthy facility and environment that represent SECRC’s health mission in support of well-being of researchers, faculty, students, visitors, staff, and horses.

Figure 6. Proposed conceptual design framework for the SECRC site.

Creating a strong sense of place and image is essential to the development of the new equine education and research complex. This image must be responsive to the surrounding community utilizing the architectural characteristics of existing equine facilities and landscapes in the region. Movement of people, animals and vehicles in and around the facilities is equally as important and has been carefully planned to encourage safe and efficient flow and interaction among the future users such as students, visitors, researchers, staff, and horses.

An environmentally sensitive design approach has been taken throughout the design of this master plan. Water conservation and management techniques are considered including rainwater collection, retention ponds, rain gardens, waste management and so on.

Facilities have also been designed and positioned on a conceptual site in distinct clusters/zones represented as Research Hub, Business Hive and the Village. However, the master plan thoughtfully connects these zones into one unified complex as a community and research center.

Process and Stakeholder Input

The initial phases of this effort introduced the SEREP project team to the Foothills region understanding the assets, needs, and the opportunities within the equine community. Through the use of GIS based data and mapping strategies the environmental features unique to the area were identified. Site specific characteristics and requirements were also identified through case studies and an online survey conducted in the earlier phases. This phase helped us to identify and understand the key site characteristics and criteria that will help choose the future site and its location in the region. These criteria were also used to inform the “model” site used to present the proposed conceptual master plan, which will be explained in the next section.

Based on the feedback received from key stakeholders, as well as the consulting equine faculty at NC State University and Isothermal Community College the following principles of sustainable design were adopted as guiding objectives for the proposed vision plan:

- SECRC facilities will have size and scale that will be a good fit to the surrounding context.
- The design concept will be inspiring with cutting edge research and education facilities that will provide unique opportunities for key equine related research and educational activities.
- The site will incorporate well-defined and welcoming private and public open spaces within the facilities, as well as the outdoors.
- The overall site will be utilized as a living laboratory.

- The site will integrate sustainable design strategies that will be sensitive to the environment and help preserve water, as well as prevent environmental pollution through the use of sustainable land management practices.
- The site will provide safe and efficient flow and interaction among future users of the site.
- The design of the outdoors will provide access to a variety of nature experiences for all.
- The design will create a sense of place and image that reflects the character of the region, as well as the equine heritage of the area.
- The new SECRC site and its facilities will be designed and developed as a flexible, dynamic living plan.

The primary user groups anticipated for these facilities as part of the SECRC complex include:

- Faculty, students and administrative personnel engaged in research and/or teaching for all equine based programs at ICC and other institutions from the southeast region (e.g. NC State University etc.). The primary research focus include but not limited to equine-assisted therapy, agri-business, smart rural development etc.;
- NC Cooperative Extension staff from Polk/Rutherford Counties and beyond.
- Researchers from corporates.
- Public agencies dedicated to sustainable and equitable development.
- Visitors/community members from the region and beyond.
- Horse owners/athletes etc.
- Business owners.

Proposed Site Model and Its Features

Each project program requires site features that are important for the future project uses and activities to occur. These may include minimum parcel size, proximity to transportation routes and utilities, suitable soils, and many other parameters. Accordingly, the proposed framework and the conceptual master plan will require a site that will be located on a parcel of 100 acres at the minimum. The site will aim to provide a mixture of open pasture land with moderate slopes along with moderate tree coverage and brush vegetation that are unique to the region. Proper drainage strategies would be developed in order to provide rain water run-off management.

Although a thorough analysis of potential sites from Polk/Rutherford Counties was conducted in the earlier project phases, no specific site has been selected at this point. However, a model site has been developed in order to demonstrate how the proposed master plan for SECRC will be positioned on a future site that will include the following key site features and characteristics. The key site features are:

Accessibility/Transportation - The site is recommended to be within 30'-50' of an existing road with more than 1 linear mile away from highway/interstate. Accessibility is an important factor to future occupants and visitors of the SECRC complex.

Slope/Elevation - The site should have less than 20% slope. Avoiding steep slopes can protect against erosion, provide safe pasture areas, and promote easy access. SECRC complex should have minimal slopes to allow for safe horse movement and limit erosion resulting from both horse traffic on pasture and the future development on site.

Watershed/Floodplains - The site is recommended not to be located within substantially large floodplain areas. The constructed area on the site should be 200ft away from surface waters and 200ft away from floodplain. This is essential in order to protect any substantial property damage during storms and preserve the water quality of streams, rivers and floodplains in the meantime. Therefore, the model site provides space outside of the floodplain where facilities are located. There is also adequate buffer area that separates surface waters from any potential pollution the center's activities might create (e.g. animal waste and eroded sediment).

Soils - The site that has prime farmland and well-drained soils are preferred in order to provide ideal pasture conditions for the proposed SECRC complex.

Canopy/Tree Cover- It is recommended that the SECRC site will have less than 50% as tree coverage. It is priority that the development of the center will protect against deforestation and damage to natural beauty of the area.

Location and Proximity - The future site for SECRC should be 200ft away from residential properties. It is also recommended that the site will be in close proximity to population centers, other equestrian and agricultural lands, programs, and activities available in the area.

The image below provides a diagram of the proposed model site and its conditions highlighting the major site/topography features, potential access to/from the site, relationships to any watershed, and the availability of tree coverage that simulate the ideal site conditions for the future SECRC property.

Size: 160 acres

Ideal soils: Prime farmland with well drained soils.

Figure 7. The "model" site and its features conceptualized for SECRC.

Conceptual Master Plan

The proposed master plan implements the conceptual framework introduced earlier. It seeks to provide a functional, efficient, and meaningful conceptual design vision for the Southeast Equine Community and Research Center complex. The master plan was developed as a parallel effort to the programming process initiated in the project's earlier phases and it is based on facility requirements that were presented by the findings of this study. **However, it is important to note that these recommendations are conceptual and visionary aiming to provide some guidance for future conversations and efforts in the establishment of SECRC and its partnerships. The master plan is currently situated on a "model" site of 162 acres, which has been conceptualized for the purposes of this project.**

Figure 8. Proposed site program organized around a series of clusters connected by pathways and open spaces.

Figure 9. The proposed conceptual site plan for SECR.

- | | | |
|-------------------------------|---|-------------------------------|
| 1. Entry Plaza/Axis | 9. Cottage Buildings with Common Pantry House (Lodging) | 18. Mound Areas |
| 2. The Core Research Facility | 10. Horse Boarding Barn | 19. Therapeutic Lab/Center |
| 3. Agribusiness Lab | 11. Equine Storage Facilities | 20. Closed Arena |
| 4. Equine History Museum | 12. Horse Paddock | 21. Open Arena |
| 5. Business Incubator | 13. Semi-enclosed Arena | 22. Therapeutic Sensory Path |
| 6. Market Place | 14. Observation Arena | 23. Therapeutic Round Paddock |
| 7. Thread and Gathering Area | 15. Waste Management Research Lab | 24. Multi-purpose Path |
| 8. Bio-retention Pond | 16. Horse Barn/Stalls | 25. Pasture |
| | 17. Field Testing Research Area (Hay Production) | |

The master plan proposes a collaborative learning and research community that promotes innovative center model through learning and shared research facilities; outdoor spaces, as well as social and community spaces. However, it is highly recommended that the design of the proposed facilities will be reconsidered based on the future site and its existing conditions. The proposed concept of the overall layout of the new Southeast Equine Community and Research Center is comprised of a primary axis along which the primary entrance has been placed, leading up to the Business Hive area that includes a collaborative work space for entrepreneurs, welcome concierge, and an equine museum. The design of this collective incorporates the idea of a community-oriented space that embraces cultural and entrepreneurial activities in an equine-based economy. Both indoor and wrap around outdoor spaces are designed and planned spatially to create unique collaborative environments for both local residents, visitors, faculty, and students alike.

Terminating this axis beyond this Business Hive area are the Research Hub facilities. The research hub incorporates collaborative research team spaces, which accommodate variation of wet and dry labs, as well as meeting and classroom spaces. This area would allow for more privacy and security and would be limited to student, staff, and faculty/researchers. Supporting pasture area for these units wrap around to the North of these facilities. 48% (approximately 77 acres) of the model site is dedicated for pasture fields, 5% (8.3 acres) is considered as outdoor field testing lab area, and 4.2% (6.8 acres) is considered as hay production fields.

Located deeper within the site, on the left section of the site, is the Equine-Assisted Therapy Center /Lab including a building and its outdoor amenities. As an extension of the Research Hub area, the Therapy Lab/Center allows for more privacy and security enabling a perfect environment for therapeutic teaching and research activities. It is also accessible from the secondary road providing vehicular access to the site. Supporting therapeutic outdoor spaces and sensory paths wrap around the facility connecting to both multi-purpose paths and horse trails in proximity.

The village incorporating the housing units and the communal kitchen/community building for the visiting researchers and athletes is located to the right end of the site including a stable surrounded with open pastures.

Outside vehicular access will be provided from a main road to all necessary service areas, central shared parking, and facilities included on the site. All other on-site circulation for the SECRC is to be committed exclusively to horse lanes, small service transportation and pedestrian paths.

Site Systems

Stormwater Management

When it comes to agricultural landscapes that support horse farms and other equine-related operations, it is important to identify potential impacts these types of site programs have on the health of the landscape and the quality of local water systems. Establishing an effective stormwater plan will help reduce the impact horse farms have on water sources such as streams, rivers, groundwater etc. A proposed SECRC should introduce Best Management Practices (BMPs) wherever possible on the site in order to avoid contaminating clean runoff and reduce the amount of contamination produced from on-site agricultural operations by designing landscape systems that can capture runoff and treat it before it reaches nearby water systems.

Figure 10. Proposed stormwater management system and site ecosystem on SECRC.

Water Harvesting Pasture Irrigation Stormwater Treatment from Horse Pastures Stream Restoration

Figure 11. Best management practices for sustainable landscapes.

Figure 12. Proposed stormwater management system on SECRC site.

There are several components of an effective stormwater management system that can be implemented to not only improve the health and conditions of proposed and existing natural systems, but it can also benefit proposed equine-related programs economically. Outlined are some of the BMPs that can be established as part of the site planning and design process:

Water Harvesting: Agricultural and equine-related programs in the landscape will require a source of water for site irrigation, especially when it comes to hay production and pasture management. By collecting and harvesting rainwater, it will reduce the need and costs to obtain water from external water resources. Whether it is through above surface cisterns collecting water from building roof runoff or underground cisterns connected to designed water bodies, the water harvested can be utilized for site irrigation.

Bioretention Basin: This component of the landscape is defined as a shallow planted depression that is designed to provide treatment and filtration of surface water for a short period of time before it's discharged to nearby swales and local environments. Bioretention Basins can be engineered at various scales which will determine the volume of runoff it can store or be reduced. Vegetation in retention areas is utilized to reduce nutrient export through plant uptake, filtration, and absorption. This method can also be a component of a water harvesting system that collects and stores water.

Biofiltration Swale/ Rain Garden: Bioswales & rain gardens are designed as shallow channels of graded soils that contains vegetation that removes silt and pollutants from surface runoff water. They can be used along the sides of horse paddocks & pastures and serve as filter strips to filter out pollutants produced in equine programed areas. They can also be constructed in pastures and graded in a way to direct water into vegetated filtration areas.

Sources - Water Quality Management:
 Rutgers, New Jersey Agricultural Experiment Station, Ryders Lane Farm: Equine Science Center,
<https://esc.rutgers.edu/research/ryders-lane-farm/water-quality-management/>

Waste Management

Properties that have horses on site will require an effective strategy for manure disposal to prevent health and environmental issues. Establishing composting methods as part of a manure management plan will provide sufficient amount of nutrients to the pasture fields and help with manure disposal on site. Development of a successful site manure management plan depends on the following components and practices:

- Placement of the composting area & manure storage pit.
- Proper manure disposal & composting methods.
- Preventing water pollutants from contaminating existing water systems on site & surrounding ecosystems.

The placement of the pit on the proposed model site should include ideal landscape conditions that includes a slight slope on site for proper rainwater runoff with buffer vegetation of native plants around it. Establishing a vegetation buffer around the storage pit and composting site will help clean and filter stormwater runoff from the waste source and prevent any potential waste pollutants from entering into existing water systems.

There are also research and educational opportunities that can explore and study manure as both a management practice and an energy resource on the site. Recent events in the scientific community and equine industry have been exploring horse manure as a renewable energy resource and be utilized for biofuel production. The proposed design and planning for SECRC includes a both a composting station, as well as a lab facility where faculty and students can conduct research and educational activities related to waste management education and biofuel research.

Figure 13. Best manure management practices.

Sources - Waste Management:

Rutgers, New Jersey Agricultural Experiment Station, Ryders Lane Farm: Equine Science Center
<https://esc.rutgers.edu/research/ryders-lane-farm/water-quality-management/>

Pasture Management

Some of the proposed research programs will require resident horses on site in order to efficiently manage research-related activities that involve horses. A proposed SECRC with resident horses will require both a calculated amount of pasture land availability based on the number of horses on site and an effective management system in place that addresses both rotational grazing and forage management. According to the NC Cooperative Extension Service report, it is generally recommended that there should be 2 acres of pasture per mature 1,100-pound horse, which can produce 6 - 8 tons of forage annually to meet the feed requirements for the horse.

It is also known that horses have different behavioral patterns when it comes to grazing on the pasture fields. That is why it is important to establish an effective rotational grazing system to be able to maximize the use of each pasture. Through rotational grazing, horses are rotated from one pasture to another to maintain sufficient forage availability and reducing spot grazing. Pastures can be divided into a number of different sections as seen in the graphic below. The more divided the pasture can be, the less prone each pasture is to spot grazing. Each pasture should have access to shelter and a water source for horses.

In the proposed site design, there are a total of ten horse pastures that equate to 77 acres, which makes up roughly 48% of the total site. Each of these pastures are flexible when it comes to fence arrangement and grazing schedules. While each pasture should include shelter/shade and a water source, some pastures have water features, which horses can take advantage of to cool down.

Figure 14. Best practices in rotational grazing.

Figure 15. Proposed pasture management practices on the SECRC site.

Sources - Pasture Management:
 North Carolina Cooperative Extension Service
<https://content.ces.ncsu.edu/managing-pastures-to-feed-your-horse>

Circulation System

The proposed conceptual master plan recommends organizing the future SECRC around a series of clusters connected via vehicular paths, multi-purpose paths, horse trails, and localized tertiary pedestrian paths. The proposed circulation system aims to provide efficient and accessible paths that are safe for both people and horses, while providing connections to facilities and open spaces, as well as access to main entries of buildings on the site. Each distinct zone represented as Research Hub, Business Hive and the Village is connected via a hierarchy system of pathways supporting the use and activity flow between them.

Figure 16. Proposed circulation system on the SECRC site.

Main Vehicular Circulation: Along the site there are two access points into the property for vehicular traffic. The first entry point located along the existing highway serves as a main entrance into the site. The second entry point on the west side of the property connects to existing minor roads and serves as a secondary entrance into the site. While driving along the driveway at the main entrance, visitors are taken through a pastoral landscape with rows of trees on each side of the driveway. Along the main driveway, visitors are directed towards views of the horse statue at the intersection and the main Research Hub facility. The main driveway provides parking options for both cars, trucks, and horse trailers adjacent to the main research facilities.

At the intersection, another driveway path is introduced, which serves as an inner driveway between major facilities on the site. The east wing of the inner driveway takes drivers to both the Village and the Business Hive facilities. This section of the driveway includes parking for cars at the Business Hive and horse trailer parking at the horse stable facilities within the Village. Continuing the inner driveway heading towards the Equine-Assisted Therapy Lab/Center, drivers are introduced to both the hay production/experiment fields on the left, and the Agribusiness Lab/Center on the right that includes parking for vehicles. The inner driveway then ends at the Equine-Assisted Therapy Lab/Center, which provides both parking and loading for cars, trucks, and horse trailers.

Multi-Purpose Paths: These paths include horse paths, as well as vehicular access for cars, trucks, and tractors. Most of the horse pastures/ experiment fields are also accessible from the defined multipurpose paths.

Figure 17. Proposed circulation system for horses on the SECRC site.

Figure 18. Multi-purpose path on the SECRC site.

Nature/Horse Trail: Along the edge of the property, north of the Research complex, is a nature trail that is roughly 0.8 miles long for both people and horses. The trail itself could be used for both research and therapeutic activities.

Figure 19. Horse trail in the wooded area of the SECRC site.

Pedestrian Circulation: The majority of pedestrian paths are centralized within the research complex and connects people to all of the major facilities on the site. One path towards the south end of the complex flows parallel with the inner driveway connecting the Agribusiness Lab/Center to both the Business Hive and the Village. Another pedestrian path that flows from the Agribusiness Center to the Research Hub intersects with the two other paths from both Business Hive and the Research Hub area converging at the axis which as a result creates opportunities for open space activities. A grid-like system is established for pedestrian movement behind the main Research Hub facilities and engages faculty and students with paddocks and observation spaces. There is also another pedestrian path that connects the main Research Hub and the Equine-Assisted Therapy Lab/Center, exposing users to rain garden and other natural landscape elements along the way.

Access and Edges

Along the edges the property mainly consists of forest vegetation, water systems entering in and out of the property, and pasture land. To filter out potential pollutants, rain gardens are established to serve as an edge along the fenced horse pastures.

All of the major facilities on the site are within walking distance to parking. At the Therapeutic Lab/Center, there is parking for both cars and horse trailers adjacent to the stable entrance. At the west wing of the Research Hub facilities, parking is established for both vehicles, as well as a parking/loading area for horse trailers. The Business Hive includes parking for both cars and trucks and can be utilized for market-based events adjacent to the plaza. Within the Village is a loading area for horse trailers adjacent to two horse stables.

Throughout the places designed on the site, it will be important to identify what areas are accessible for both public and private uses. The multi-purpose paths will only be accessible for private uses for faculty, staff, students, and other service-related activities. For an inclusive and controlled environment, the sensory paths within the Therapeutic Lab/Center will also be private. One area that is designated for public and visitor access is the Business Hive, which includes both the plaza and the lawn areas enclosed by the Business Hive facility. Spaces created around the main Research Hub facilities and the Village would be defined as semi-private spaces, meaning that these areas are flexible for both public and private uses.

Figure 20. Proposed site access and main circulation paths for the SECR site.

Open Space System and Key Landscape Elements

The proposed conceptual master plan presents an open space system and landscape elements that provide access to the buildings and extends the indoor activities into outdoors. Various open space types were created including informal gathering spaces such as courtyards, open lawn spaces, as well as more programmed activity spaces such as horse paddocks, semi-covered arena, observation arenas, therapeutic sensory areas etc.

From the Business Hive, to the back of the main Research Hub facility, an open space corridor or a “thread” is proposed connecting these two entities together which include open space components along the way. At the lower end of the thread next to the Business Hive is a plaza space, which includes canopy structures for shade and a seating area. Along the thread there is an open green space that is enclosed by the U-shaped Business Hive facility. The mid-point of the thread expands into an open gathering/resting space between the main Research Hub facility and the Business Hive, creating opportunities for seating and resting near the adjacent bioretention pond area. The end of the thread opens up at the rear end of the main Research Hub facility where spaces are created for outdoor learning activities for students and faculty.

- Thread and Gathering Spaces
- Open Lawn Space
- Spaces for Equine Activities
 - 1 Horse Paddock
 - 2 Covered Arena
 - 3 Multi-purpose Space
 - 4 Observation Arena
 - 5/6 Therapeutic Round Paddock and Sensory Paths

Figure 21. Proposed open space types for the SECRC site.

Key landscape elements such as bio-retention ponds, rain gardens, elevated mounds, and specific vegetated spaces are also proposed to create unstructured fun, engaging, and pleasant spaces. These landscapes also aim to mitigate stormwater run-off on site, as well as remove the pollutants from soil and water.

- Bio-Retention Pond
- Rain Garden / Vegetation
- Elevated Mound Topography

Figure 22. Proposed functional landscape elements on the SECRC site.

Building Systems

The proposed buildings on the site will be designed incorporating passive sustainable design principles including day lighting and natural ventilation.

Day lighting – building and window placement should maximize the beneficial aspects of day light in the spaces and buffer against the negative aspects of sun exposures via the use of shading structures specifically on the south side of the buildings. These strategies will also help minimize glare, as well as heat gain that could stress the mechanical units in the buildings.

Natural ventilation – building orientation, window placement and landscape design should capture cooling summer breezes, while controlling the cooler winter breezes.

Figure 23. Proposed sustainable building design principles on the SECRC site.

Proposed Research and Education Facilities: Building, Spatial Program and Outdoor Components

Research Hub

The Research Hub contains four facilities: The Main Research Building, Agribusiness Research Center, the Waste Management Research Lab, and the Therapeutic Lab/Center. Each of these facilities have different research focus areas and activities but include similar or relevant spatial program and design strategies.

a) The Main Research Facility

This core research facility has been proposed as part of the SECRC conceptual master plan to provide an efficient and cutting edge facility for conducting equine related transdisciplinary research projects for scientific advancement that will also benefit the needs of the equine community in the region. The design of the main research facility creates the focal point on the site. It is placed between Business Hive facility and the observation arenas that are also connected via a “thread”, which is part of an open space system created on the model site. This thread connects the Research Hub, Business Hive, observation arenas, and the Village as an iconic pathway and a working landscape.

Figure 24. A view from the “thread” - the Core Research Facility and the Semi-Covered Arena

Figure 25. An aerial view of the “thread”, the main Research Hub Facility and the Business Hive to the left.

A straight view of the main Research Hub building can be seen as visitors enter the complex from the main entry to the site. This commanding view of the facility helps create strong physical and visual connections for visitors entering the complex. A field of grass in front of the building creates a unique threshold effect and also minimizes the amount of maintenance required. A brick seating wall in front of the facility helps maximize outdoor activities. Open gathering lawn spaces adjacent and behind the main facility serve as gathering spaces for expanded activities that are adjacent to the observation arenas and paddocks. Located behind the main Research Facility lies five horse paddock spaces, which include four observation paddocks, a semi-covered arena, and a flex area. These spaces can be utilized for multiple outdoor research & equine-related activities. Parking areas for both cars, trucks, and trailers are established with access to the main Research Facility, as well as the horse stable facilities.

Figure 26. The front entry of the core Research Facility.

Figure 27. An aerial view of the main Research Facility.

The proposed research facility (approximately 25,000 sq ft) will incorporate both research lab and educational spaces in support of focus areas related to equine health and science, equine manufacturing, and smart rural development. This building will include a welcoming, large atrium/gallery space, which can be utilized to exhibit information and products on the ongoing research efforts. This atrium will also serve as the main “indoor tread”, which connects various research lab wings in the building. It overlooks to two indoor enclosed courtyard spaces, which are part of the idea of “research yard” enabling researchers in residence to congregate and share their work among each other or with public. These inner courtyards also aim to provide a pleasant atmosphere with views toward the adjoining outdoor spaces and the rain garden.

Openness.

Linkages

Figure 28. Plan view of the main Research Facility.

Figure 29. A view from the interior of the main Research Facility - Research Yard.

There is increasing demand for researchers and disciplines to team up and collaborate to address many of the challenges and research inquiries rather than working in silos and independently. Many of these transdisciplinary and collaborative research efforts require flexible, open, and more connected lab spaces that also include spaces for meeting, brainstorming, ideation, co-sharing, testing, and teaching. Hence, this proposed research facility includes research lab wings, which incorporate collaborative team spaces including wet/dry labs, meeting/conference rooms, office/computer workstations, informal gathering areas, and classrooms. Each wing incorporates an entry space, which also provides privacy and security to each research area as needed. These research wings are designed to provide spaces with flexibility to change or adapt to the changing nature of research activities by researchers who will cycle in and out of the building as projects evolve. A model for physical space is outlined that is focused on this dynamic research team model that will aim to create networks, catalyze interactions, and spur multiple contacts rather than the creation of traditional individual lab spaces, which siloes the researchers. Hence, this facility is designed to provide more open, visually connected, and integrated research and educational spaces that can accommodate team and/or collaborative activities among researchers as needed.

Flexibility.

Figure 30. A view from the interiors of the main Research Facility - Typical dry lab area.

Figure 31. A view from the interiors of the main Research Facility - Flexible study/work area in a research-lab wing.

Figure 32. A view from the interiors of the main Research Facility - Typical wet-lab area.

The proposed research building is single story envisioned as a steel frame, wood building with a gabled roof. It will have a rustic equine vocabulary, with wood siding and large windows for daylighting the indoor work spaces and the atrium/gallery space.

Behind the main Research building is the Waste Management Research Lab that includes an outdoor composting station, as well as an indoor lab space for activities related to manure management and biofuel research. Across the driveway from the main Research building is also the Agribusiness Lab, with access to hay production fields and field testing/research areas located in the front part of the property.

Figure 33. Plan view of the Agribusiness Research Lab area.

b) Equine-Assisted Therapy Lab/Center

Establishing both a stress-free and controlled environment will be a key component for the proposed therapeutic center. That is why this master plan recommends that the location of the therapeutic center on the site to be isolated and separated from other programs.

The Equine-Assisted Therapy Lab/Center will aim to integrate research and education in equine-assisted activities and therapies. The building and its outdoors will be a place where people with physical, emotional, and development challenges can receive treatment from specialists. It also provides opportunities for students to be involved in hands-on educational activities, as well as enable researchers to be involved in collaborative efforts.

The proposed building will require approximately 32,181 square feet facility. This L-shaped building will include a welcoming, large atrium/gallery space displaying digital and interactive screen surfaces. The proposed plan of the building is ideal for both hands-on instructional and research activities making it a strong asset for ICC students and faculty. Number of classrooms, offices, and various meeting spaces are arranged along the main atrium/gallery space. The facility also includes two indoor and outdoor arenas, dry-lab areas, and therapy spaces along with public areas for clients and their families. Additionally, a 10-stall barn for therapy horses, round pens, an outdoor sensory path, as well as outdoor runs have been proposed.

Figure 34. A view from the atrium of the Equine-Assisted Therapy Lab/Center.

Figure 35. Plan view of the Equine-Assisted Therapy Lab/Center facility.

Figure 36. A view from the Covered Arena of the Equine-Assisted Therapy Lab/Center facility.

Figure 37. A view of stalls in the Equine-Assisted Therapy Lab/Center.

Figure 38. A view of the entry area of the Equine-Assisted Therapy Lab/Center site.

The building is single story envisioned as a steel frame, wood building with a gabled roof. It will have a rustic equine vocabulary, with wood siding and clerestory windows for daylighting the arena and the atrium/gallery space.

The Equine-Assisted Therapy Lab/Center has both indoor and outdoor arenas to serve for a variety of different activities and different user groups. The outdoor arena can be utilized for group riding activities, while separate round pens can be used for personalized therapeutic activities. These arenas can also provide an observation space for researchers to understand equine based therapeutic activities and human behavior.

As part of the outdoor amenities, a sensory path has also been proposed in order to help people, particularly kids with autism who often struggle in directions and communication. Professional equine assisted riding helps these individuals balance, focus, coordinate and interact with the environment through their senses during the ride or walk. Hence, it is proposed that this sensory path will include landscaping and different riding surfaces that will help engage kids with matching colors, stepping, counting as part of the types of different activities throughout the path which can engage their attention to observe and make decisions.

Figure 39. An aerial view of the Equine-Assisted Therapy Lab/Center facility and its outdoors.

Figure 40. An aerial view of the Equine-Assisted Therapy Lab/Center outdoors - sensory paths, open arenas, paddocks.

Figure 41. A view of the sensory paths around the Equine-Assisted Therapy Lab/Center facility.

Business Hive Facility

The proposed Business Hive facility is first introduced with a statue of a horse (similar to other existing equine-statues within the region) that functions as a gateway entry into the overall SECRC site. The design of this collective facility incorporates the idea of a community-oriented space that embraces cultural and entrepreneurial activities in an equine-based economy. Both indoor and outdoor spaces are designed and planned spatially to create unique experiences and collaborative environments for both local residents, visitors, faculty, and students alike.

Figure 42. A view of the gateway entry to the SECRC site.

The 17,000 square foot U-shaped building offers community oriented spaces and activities that sets the pulse for the entire site. The main entry to the building is a visitor center, which also serves as the main entry space for both Equine Museum and the Business Incubator spaces. This main entry area includes a souvenir shop, as well as a small coffee kiosk. The museum and business incubator offices are located on separate wings. The museum incorporates combination of open, flexible, and semi-fixed exhibition spaces with visual and physical access to the outdoor courtyard area. This courtyard provides an opportunity for extending the exhibition opportunities into the outdoors, which can also serve as event space as needed. The business incubator, on the other hand, incorporates both indoor and outdoor group/team work spaces, conference/meeting rooms, a multi-functional space for events/workshops, as well as individual enclosed office spaces. The workspaces primarily are designed using the open space concept to trigger collaboration and sharing among entrepreneurs, small business owners etc. The business incubator section also has a separate entrance toward the front, as well as the open spaces created for activities such as local farmers and artisan market.

Figure 43. A plan view of the Business Hive facility.

Figure 44. A view of the entry area toward the Business Hive facility.

Figure 45. An aerial view of the Business Hive facility and its outdoors.

The open space next to the second entry of Business Incubator facility includes the canopy structures that help create a “farmers market” environment, where local farmers and artisans can offer their products to visitors in these spaces. Adjacent to the designed canopy structures is a plaza space that includes seating areas to help maximize and complement activities within a market environment. Enclosed within the Business Hive facility is a lawn space (internal courtyard) that can maximize the outdoor activities for special outdoor events. All of these outdoor spaces are designated for public activities and are separated from other nearby private research functions on the site. Overall, this area presents visible, civic, and welcoming spaces to the surrounding community. All of these uses, supported by well-designed spaces, can help encourage community interaction on the site.

Figure 46. A view of the outdoor gathering space - the Market area.

The Village Facilities

The village is a cluster of different cottage buildings and common pantry house that can house faculty, students, and athletes for overnight stay. The cottages have close walking access to a main common pantry house, two horse stables, and an exercise paddock that can be utilized by guests, athletes, etc. The horse stables and cottages are connected by a pedestrian axis corridor, which includes views of the rain garden from the horse stable complex.

Plots of small-scale courtyard spaces are scattered between cottages along the main pedestrian corridor. These small spaces are created to encourage passive outdoor activities and gathering spaces for residents. These small-scale courtyards connect the blocks in a way that the design creates a spatial collaborative environment. At the center of the Village lies a gathering space where people can explore a variety of different outdoor and engagement activities.

Figure 47. An aerial view of the Village area.

Figure 48. A view of the outdoor gathering space - the Village area.

Figure 49. A plan view of the Village cottage buildings and common pantry house.

Expected Impacts of the Proposed Master Plan

It was the goal of this planning and design process to conceptualize how the future site could best support the holistic vision created for the new Southeast Equine Community and Research Center (SECRC). The site planning and design process helped to investigate ways in which new structures, open spaces, fields, and surrounding areas could facilitate opportunities to support that vision of the future center. It is our hope that the key stakeholders can use the proposed concepts in this report to assist in cultivating partnerships with diverse stakeholders able to contribute to the realization of the proposed vision. It is also our hope that this vision inspires and guides the future efforts and help securing funding for site selection and the refinement of the proposed design concepts.

References

- American Horse Council Foundation. (2018). *Economic Impact of the Horse Industry in North Carolina*. Washington, D.C.: American Horse Council Foundation.
- Anderson, S., & Meints, K. (2016). Brief report: the effects of equine-assisted activities on the social functioning in children and adolescents with autism spectrum disorder. *Journal of autism and developmental disorders*, 46(10), 3344-3352.
- Bizub, A. L., Joy, A., & Davidson, L. (2003). "It's like being in another world": demonstrating the benefits of therapeutic horseback riding for individuals with psychiatric disability. *Psychiatric rehabilitation journal*, 26(4), 377.
- Brookins, C. C., Morais, D., Pasalar, C., Scheunemann, A., Kuss, T., Jones, T. & Ferreira, B. (2017). Southeast Equine Research and Education Partnership – An NC State-Isothermal Community College Partnership. Retrieved from https://serrep.wordpress.ncsu.edu/files/2017/05/SEREP-Progress-Report-July-2017-spread_Final_080717.pdf.
- Burgon, H. L. (2011). 'Queen of the world': Experiences of 'at-risk' young people participating in equine-assisted learning/therapy. *Journal of Social Work Practice*, 25(02), 165-183.
- Christian, J. E. (2005). All Creatures Great and Small: Utilizing Equine-Assisted Therapy to Treat Eating Disorders. *Journal of Psychology and Christianity*.
- Hemingway, A., Meek, R., & Hill, C. E. (2015). An exploration of an equine-facilitated learning intervention with young offenders. *Society & animals*, 23(6), 544-568.
- Kelly, S. (2014). Horses for courses: Exploring the limits of leadership development through equine-assisted learning. *Journal of Management Education*, 38(2), 216-233.
- Kemp, K., Signal, T., Botros, H., Taylor, N., & Prentice, K. (2014). Equine facilitated therapy with children and adolescents who have been sexually abused: A program evaluation study. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 23, 558-566. doi: 10.1007/s10826-013- 9718-1
- Lanning, B. A., & Krenek, N. (2013). Examining effects of equine-assisted activities to help combat veterans improve quality of life. *Journal of Rehabilitation Research and Development*, 50(8), VII.
- Lentini, J. A., & Knox, M. S. (2015). Equine-facilitated psychotherapy with children and adolescents: An update and literature review. *Journal of Creativity in Mental Health*, 10(3), 278-305.
- Maujean, A., Kendall, E., Lillan, R., Sharp, T., & Pringle, G. (2013). Connecting for health: Playing with horses as a therapeutic tool. *Journal of Community Psychology*, 41(4), 515-522.
- McCullough, L. M. (2011). *Effect of equine-facilitated psychotherapy on posttraumatic stress symptoms in youth with history of maltreatment and abuse*. Northcentral University.
- Morais, D., Brookins, C. C., Pasalar, C., Ferreria, B. S., Scheunemann, A., Kuss, T., & Jones, B. (2018). Southeast Equine Research and Education Partnership - 2nd Progress Report: Identifying opportunities. Raleigh, NC: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27368.16643
- NC Isothermal Region C. (2017). *NC Isothermal Region C: Economic Development Plan. Stronger Economies Together Initiative*. Retrieved from <https://regioncorg.files.wordpress.com/2017/01/foothillsfinalplan2016-11-30.pdf>
- Osterwalder, A. et. al. (2015) *Value Proposition Design: How to Make Stuff People Want*, John Wiley & Sons, Incorporated, ProQuest Ebook Central, <https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/ncsu/detail.action?docID=1887760>.
- Region C Workforce Development Board. (2016). *The Region C Economy*. Rutherfordton, NC: Isothermal Planning and Development Commission.
- Zadnikar, M., & Kastrin, A. (2011). Effects of hippotherapy and therapeutic horseback riding on postural control or balance in children with cerebral palsy: a meta-analysis. *Developmental medicine & child neurology*, 53(8), 684-691.

Appendix

Equine Assisted Activities: A Proposed Strategic Plan for Harnessing the Power of Equines in Human Health

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Over the last 30 years equine assisted therapy has evolved into a dynamic therapeutic option (Bizub, Joy & Davidson, 2003). Utilizing equines in therapeutic settings has garnered much attention as the application of, and outcomes associated with, horse and human interaction becomes a more common intervention for the treatment of a variety of physical, cognitive, and mental health issues. Although research in this area is emerging, it spans the human experience, including: victims who have experienced sexual violence (Kemp, Signal, Botros, Taylor & Prentice, 2014), veterans (Lanning & Krennek, 2013), children (Lentini & Knox, 2015), individuals with PTSD (McCullough, 2011), at-risk youth (Burgon, 2011; Maujean et al. (2013)), people with autism (Anderson & Meints, 2016), people with cerebral palsy (Zadnikar & Kastrin, 2011), court involved youth (Hemingway, Meek & Hill, 2012), patients with eating disorders (Christian, 2005) and business executives (Kelly, 2014).

As activities utilizing equines in therapeutic contexts increases worldwide, what we “know” about equine’s influence on human health becomes increasingly complex. To date, there are numerous approaches to utilizing equines in human care. These modalities have been categorized into the following areas: equine-assisted physical therapy, equine assisted occupational therapy, equine assisted speech therapy, equine assisted mental health, equine assisted learning and therapeutic riding (Hallberg, 2018; See Table 1). These approaches assess and treat a number of physical, cognitive, language development, and mental health disorders, yet these applications are not governed by one overarching body. The most common and reputable organized bodies that train practitioners include: Professional Association of Therapeutic Horsemanship (PATH), Equine Assisted Growth and Learning Association (EAGALA), Natural Lifemanship (TF-EAP), Eponaquest, OK CORRAL, Human-Equine Alliances for Learning (HEAL), Human-Equine Relational Development Institute (HERD). Ultimately, these modalities, and the people who lead them, encompass differing viewpoints on the process of the therapy and the role of the horse. Often times, implementation in practice depends on the training a therapist or facility has encountered. This varies from person to person, farm to farm, facility to facility. (i.e., professional organizations with curricula and certifications, nonprofit organizations serving a particular population that might draw from a combination of modalities, and/or individual therapists with training in clinical work, but who have limited knowledge about using equines in therapy).

Although decades of research indicate meaningful benefits for humans, in 2001 we begin to see the first published studies that focus on human mental health. Equine facilitated mental health, also known as Equine

Assisted Psychotherapy (EAP) is one of the fastest growing components in today's animal assisted therapy industry (Professional Association of Therapeutic Horsemanship, 2017). The consensus is that therapeutic work with horses improves self-confidence and self-esteem (Chandler, 2005), cultivates conflict resolution skills and relationship skills (Kersten & Thomas, 2004). Equine and human pairings also help to reduce distress (Klontz, Bivens, Leinart & Klontz, 2007) and mitigates maladaptive behaviors (Anderson & Meints, 2016). Interestingly, engaging in EAP has been shown to sustain higher retention and engagement rates than traditional talk therapy (Lentini & Knox, 2015). However, there is little agreement that equine assisted psychotherapy is an evidenced based treatment or on the best practices associated with this treatment (Letini & Knox, 2015; Anestis et al., 2014). Given this framework, there is much to be accomplished in the research and education of equine assisted therapies. In alignment with the literature on equine assisted therapies, we outline five comprehensive areas of focus that guide a 3-year strategic plan for equine therapy research and education with the Southeast Equine Research and Education Partnership.

There are opportunities for the Center to:

- Engage in evidence based studies to organize knowledge and legitimize treatment and practice (Anestis et al., 2014). Many of the published articles have small sample sizes, heterogeneity across populations (e.g., lack of diversity in the sample's demographics) and anecdotal data (i.e.,g lack of rigorous qualitative and quantitative research design and implementation) (Pauw, 2000).
- Investigate the role of the horse, as it varies in different therapeutic modalities. Some practitioners view the horse as a machine or a tool giving a specific movement (Uchiyama, Ohtani & Ohta, 2011), where others view the horse as an equal sentient being on the therapy team (Frewin & Gardiner, 2005).
- Provide space for practitioners, leaders, and organizations that provide equine assisted interventions to collaborate and organize working knowledge on the industries best practices. Currently, there is disorganized and contradictory knowledge on best practices (Letini & Knox, 2015).
- Engage in equine facilitated activities that serve different people groups, in varied contexts, through diverse modalities. From Hippotherapy where licensed health professionals work with clients on movement and balance (Zadnikar & Kastrin, 2011) to equine assisted psychotherapy where psychotherapists work one-on-one with traumatized clients on healthy relationship building and communication skills (Kersten & Thomas, 2004; Chandler, 2005), to equine assisted learning where educators teach conflict resolution to business executives and employees (Kelly, 2014).
- Identify and engage populations of people that could benefit from equine assisted activities that might typically self-select out of interacting with equines. For example, how might the Center be a place where individuals with allergies to equines, or immunocompromised individuals, be able to benefit from interactions with equines. Or, how might we provide guidance and education for individuals that have a history of animal mistreatment (Morrison, 2007).

The national and international conversation around equines and human mental health is ongoing and vitally important to the health and well-being of both humans and equines. The SEREP Center has the potential to not only join this conversation, but to be a world leader in research on Equine Assisted Activities. Below we outline a general strategic plan for continuing these efforts at the local, state, and national level.

Equine Assisted Activities for Research and Education Center Three - Year Strategic Plan Overview

	Year #1	Year #2	Year #3
Goal #1- Local Focus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Host an “Open House” event for the local community. - Identify potential partnerships with FENCE, TROT, and Isothermal Community College (e.g., possibly a co-sponsorship for the open house event) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plan for a pilot program with local participants, partnering with local agencies - Continue to development partnerships with FENCE, TROT, ICC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Begin “normal operations” at the center. - Sustain partnerships with FENCE, TROT, ICC
Goal #2- State Focus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop a database of all programs and individuals that are practicing EAP/EAL/TR across the state of North Carolina. - Begin Research efforts (e.g., recruiting EAP/EAL/TR facilities for program assessment). - Locate and apply for state funding for continued research. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Host an EAP/EAL/EAA/TR conference at the center inviting all the programs across the state. - Share research findings at conference. Highlight leading practitioners in the state, provide opportunities for networking. - Locate and apply for state funding for continued research. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Begin “normal operations” at the center. - Implement evidence-based findings into practice at the Center with an EAA/EAP pilot program serving community members; new research efforts at the Center (e.g., experimental design, control groups). - Locate and apply for state funding for continued research.
Goal #3- National Focus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Begin communication efforts spreading the knowledge that SEREP exists, its goals and future opportunities. - Locate and apply for funding through national grants (e.g., NIH, Horse and Human Research Foundation, etc.). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop a database of all programs that are practicing EAP/EAL/TR across the United States. - Locate and apply for funding through national grants (e.g., NIH, Horse and Human Research Foundation, etc.). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Host an EAP/EAL/EAA/TR conference at the Center inviting leading researchers and practitioners from across the country. - Locate and apply for funding through national grants (e.g., NIH, Horse and Human Research Foundation, etc.).

YEAR 1:

“Open House” Event

- Invite stakeholders and members of the community to attend and to present
 - Local trainers, veterinarians, trimmers/farriers, etc.
 - Co-sponsorship with FENCE, TROT, ICC, and/or other local organizations
- Demonstrations of multiple types of EAA/T
- Classroom style presentations on multiple aspects of EAA/T

Develop a database of all programs and individuals that are practicing EAP/EAL/TR across the state of North Carolina.

- Internet Search with different key terms (Equine therapy in NC, Horse therapy in NC, Equine Facilitated Psychotherapy in NC, Equine Assisted Learning in NC, etc.)
- Search “Find a Practitioner” Databases in the major modalities (EAGALA, PATH, OK Corral, HEAL, HERD, etc.)
- Post in active Equestrian Facebook groups (Triangle Area Equestrians, Triad Area Equestrians, NC Horse Council, etc.) to ask if they know of or are anyone practicing EAA/T
- Create a master list of all centers/programs in the state along with the contact info, the type of program/services provided and the modality that they use
 - After list is created, reach out to all organizations to ensure information is correct and to let them know that SEREP exists

Begin communication efforts, branding the EAA component of the Center, communicating goals and future opportunities.

- Reach out to the programs and centers across the state (as outlined above)
- Visit horse events across the state (shows, events, vet school open house, clinics, etc.)
- Make connections with potential community partners (therapists, court counselors, police departments, local law enforcement, etc.)
- Develop communication plan for EAA and the Center (branding, social media presence, promotion)

Begin research efforts, recruiting state facilities for program assessment, and locating and applying for research funding.

YEAR 2:

Plan for a pilot program with local participants, partnering with local agencies

- Determine program most needed in the local community
 - What population should be served?
 - What modality should be explored first?
- Determine staffing and facility needs (horse and human) for the particular program
- Develop a plan to run said program in Year 3

Host an EAP/EAL/EAA/TR conference at the center inviting all the programs across the state.

- Round table discussions
- Panel Discussions
- Question and Answer with key leaders in the industry
- Invite practitioners to present their models in mini lecture series

Develop a database of all programs that are practicing EAP/EAL/TR across the United States.

- Internet Search with different key terms (Equine therapy, Horse therapy, Equine Facilitated Psychotherapy, Equine Assisted Learning, etc.)
- Search "Find a Practitioner" Databases in the major modalities (EAGALA, PATH, OK Corral, HEAL, HERD, etc.)
- Post in active Equestrian Facebook groups to ask if they know of or are anyone practicing EAA/T
- Create a master list of all centers/programs in the state along with the contact info, the type of program/services provided and the modality that they use
 - After list is created, reach out to all organizations to ensure information is correct and to let them know that SEREP exists
- Create an interactive space (online group, forum, database, website etc.) to house all of the information and to encourage connection and collaboration from all

Continue research efforts, recruiting state facilities for program assessment, developing the EAA program at the Center for potential research samples (e.g., experimental and control groups) and locating and applying for state and federal research funding.

YEAR 3: Defining “normal operations” at the center

For the first 6-months of year 3, the center will analyze the work thus far. By thoroughly considering the effectiveness of the databases created, networks attained and pilot program completed, the center will be able to propose how it best fits into the community. The following plan outlines potential options for “normal operations.”

1. The center will act as a research lab for equine assisted activities.
2. The center will provide EAA/T services to the local community.
3. The center will be a network hub for those practicing EAA/T across the state and nation.

Potential Organizational Staffing (if offering a full range of equine assisted activities to the public):

1. Executive Director
 - a. Business Director
 - b. Communication Director
 - c. Health Director
 - i. Licensed Mental Health Professional
 - ii. Licensed Occupational Therapist
 - iii. Licensed Physical Therapist
2. Equine Director
 - a. Barn Manager
 - b. Facilities Manager
 - c. Equine Specialists
 - d. Therapeutic Riding Instructors

Potential Horse Needs:

- 2 Resident Herds- 12 horses total
 - 6 horses best fit for Therapeutic Riding Curriculum
 - Partner with local community to take horses that are entering retirement and/or not able to do their jobs anymore
 - Very well trained
 - 6 horses best fit for Equine Facilitated Activities
 - 3 rescues from difficult situations
 - 3 horses with a known history
 - Training not necessary
 - If additional horses are needed, the center could partner with local farms and horse owners for access and use of their horses.

References

- Anderson, S., & Meints, K. (2016). Brief report: the effects of equine-assisted activities on the social functioning in children and adolescents with autism spectrum disorder. *Journal of autism and developmental disorders*, 46(10), 3344-3352.
- Anestis, M. D., Anestis, J. C., Zawilinski, L. L., Hopkins, T. A., & Lilienfeld, S. O. (2014). Equine-related treatments for mental disorders lack empirical support: A systematic review of empirical investigations. *Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 70(12), 1115-1132.
- Bizub, A. L., Joy, A., & Davidson, L. (2003). "It's like being in another world": demonstrating the benefits of therapeutic horseback riding for individuals with psychiatric disability. *Psychiatric rehabilitation journal*, 26(4), 377.
- Burgon, H. L. (2011). 'Queen of the world': Experiences of 'at-risk' young people participating in equine-assisted learning/therapy. *Journal of Social Work Practice*, 25(02), 165-183.
- Chandler, C. (2005). *Animal assisted therapy in counseling*. New York: Routledge.
- Child maltreatment. (2017, February 27). Retrieved from <http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs150/en/>
- Christian, J. E. (2005). All Creatures Great and Small: Utilizing Equine-Assisted Therapy to Treat Eating Disorders. *Journal of Psychology and Christianity*.
- Frewin, K., & Gardiner, B. (2005). New age or old sage? A review of equine assisted psychotherapy. *The Australian Journal of Counselling Psychology*, 6(2), 13-17.
- Hallberg, L. (2018). *The Clinical Practice of Equine-Assisted Psychotherapy*. New York, New York: Routledge.
- Hemingway, A., Meek, R., & Hill, C. E. (2015). An exploration of an equine-facilitated learning intervention with young offenders. *Society & animals*, 23(6), 544-568.
- Kelly, S. (2014). Horses for courses: Exploring the limits of leadership development through equine-assisted learning. *Journal of Management Education*, 38(2), 216-233.
- Kemp, K., Signal, T., Botros, H., Taylor, N., & Prentice, K. (2014). Equine facilitated therapy with children and adolescents who have been sexually abused: A program evaluation study. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 23, 558-566. doi: 10.1007/s10826-013- 9718-1
- Kersten, G., & Thomas, L. (2004). *Equine assisted psychotherapy and learning un-training manual*. Santaquin, UT: Equine Assisted Psychotherapy and Learning Association (EAGALA).
- Klontz, B. T., Bivens, A., Leinart, D., & Klontz, T. (2007). The effectiveness of equine-assisted experiential therapy: Results of an open clinical trial. *Society & Animals*, 15(3), 257-267.
- Lanning, B. A., & Krenek, N. (2013). Examining effects of equine-assisted activities to help combat veterans improve quality of life. *Journal of Rehabilitation Research and Development*, 50(8), VII.

Lentini, J. A., & Knox, M. S. (2015). Equine-facilitated psychotherapy with children and adolescents: An update and literature review. *Journal of Creativity in Mental Health, 10*(3), 278-305.

Maujean, A., Kendall, E., Lillan, R., Sharp, T., & Pringle, G. (2013). Connecting for health: Playing with horses as a therapeutic tool. *Journal of Community Psychology, 41*(4), 515-522.

McCullough, L. M. (2011). *Effect of equine-facilitated psychotherapy on posttraumatic stress symptoms in youth with history of maltreatment and abuse*. Northcentral University.

Morrison, M. L. (2007). Health benefits of animal-assisted interventions. *Complementary health practice review, 12*(1), 51-62.

Uchiyama, H., Ohtani, N., & Ohta, M. (2011). Three-dimensional analysis of horse and human gaits in therapeutic riding. *Applied animal behavior science, 135*(4), 271-276.

Professional Association of Therapeutic Horsemanship International. (2017). *PATH Intl. Student Manual: Equine Specialist in Mental Health and Learning Workshops* (1st ed.).

Pauw, J. (2000). Therapeutic horseback riding studies: problems experienced by researchers. *Physiotherapy, 86*(10), 523-527.

Zadnikar, M., & Kastrin, A. (2011). Effects of hippotherapy and therapeutic horseback riding on postural control or balance in children with cerebral palsy: a meta-analysis. *Developmental medicine & child neurology, 53*(8), 684-691.

Table 1 - Common definitions for Equine Assisted Activities and Therapies

Term	Definition
Equine Assisted Physical Therapy	“This term describes the inclusion of horses in a physical therapy service. Physical therapy uses treatment techniques to promote the ability to move, reduce pain, restore function and prevent disability” (p.7).
Equine Assisted Occupational Therapy	“This term describes the inclusion of horses in an occupational therapy service. Occupational therapy addresses physical, psychological, and cognitive aspects of well-being” (p.7).
Equine Assisted Speech Therapy	“This term describes the inclusion of horses in a speech, language or hearing therapy service. Speech language pathologists treat speech, language, social communication, cognitive communication and swallowing disorders” (p.7).
Equine Assisted Mental Health (aka- Equine Assisted Psychotherapy)	“A term that is used to describe any type of mental health service that includes horses or the farm milieu. Mental health services are provided by professionals who have graduated from an accredited education program and are allowed by law to include mental health treatment as part of their scope of practice” (p.7).
Equine Assisted Learning	“A type of equine assisted activity that broadly refers to non-therapy, skills-based services that focus on teaching life skills, social skills, communication skills, relationship skills, or leadership skills while facilitating personal growth and increased self-awareness through both mounted and unmounted interactions with horses” (p.7).
Therapeutic Riding (aka adaptive riding)	“Non-therapy skills based service in which specially trained instructors teach horseback riding and horsemanship skills to students with disabilities or special needs” (p.4).

Note: All definitions found in Hallberg (2018).

Acknowledgements

NC State University is committed to research and scholarship efforts of its faculty and students toward the enhancement of communities in the State of North Carolina. Community development and design projects are conceived to empower the communities with the tools necessary to craft a vision and direct their own futures – as well as to develop and maintain a pride of place!

A community exists as a manifestation of its cultural, social, economic and physical attributes. Conceptual design projects and visioning processes assist a community in orchestrating the specific interests and activities of groups or individuals in the community within a shared vision of the community's character, its present and future.

This effort provides a conceptual framework for establishing a new Southeast Equine Community and Research Center (SECRC) focused on horse, human, and environmental health. Creating new economic opportunities, building on the existing equine culture, and enhancing the character of the built environment are the main focal points of this project. The project aims to help the Isothermal Community College (ICC) engage in organized and proactive discussions about the future of the new SECRC.

We would like to thank the Isothermal Community College (ICC) leadership, members of the equine community, and representatives of the various groups focused on the social and economic development of the region for their continuing support and input throughout the project.

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The Southeast Equine Research and Education Partnership was a reflection of the dreams and aspirations of many people who are devoted to improve the Isothermal community and its assets. NC State University remains committed to working in partnership on the next steps in turning this vision into a reality.

Praise for SEREP

"As Vice Provost for Outreach and Engagement at NC State, it has been a privilege to see the collaboration between Isothermal Community College and NC State on this initiative focused on equine and animal research and human therapy services. The challenge of determining how to productively and responsibly manage growth is one communities across the state are facing, and making progress involves bringing together community voices, economic and workforce agencies, and anchor institutions like Isothermal. NC State is pleased to be involved in this effort and looks forward to our continued work together."

Leslie Boney, Director, Institute for Emerging Issues, Vice Provost, Outreach and Engagement at NC State University

"As Chair of the Institute for Emerging Issues, I have always looked with favor upon the expansion of research and higher education in our state. Also, as a resident of Western North Carolina, I have advocated for a greater presence of these initiatives in Western North Carolina. The plan brought forth by Isothermal Community College and NC State University for a collaborative research center with the potential for other universities and private research companies to participate is a good one and when brought to fruition, will strengthen our region, our state, and provide greater opportunity for our people."

Jack Cecil, Chair of Institute of Emerging Issues at NC State University and President of Biltmore Farms

"North Carolina's universities and community colleges are our greatest assets. When they collaborate, the result is always a success. This effort between Isothermal Community College and NC State will result in new opportunities for advancement and prosperity in the state's growing equestrian industry."

Anthony M. Copeland, N. C. Commerce Secretary

"It is a wonderful thing when one of North Carolina's great universities and one of its great community colleges work together with a community to plan for the future and opportunities for advancement and prosperity. That is what Isothermal Community College and NC State University have done, together with the work for local citizens, in developing this study. It not only lays a foundation for the area, but it also helps to strengthen a growing equestrian industry in our state and through programs for human therapy, improve the quality of life for some of our most vulnerable citizens."

Pryor Gibson, Director of Hometown Strong

"I appreciate the work of Isothermal Community College and its efforts to provide the best of educational opportunities for our students. This study looks to the future and looks for ways to expand opportunities, while respecting our traditions and pastoral lifestyle."

Tommy Melton, Chair of the Polk County Commission

"As Commissioner of Agriculture, I am pleased when communities envision our state's number one industry- agriculture- as part of their future. The equestrian sector is a strong component of that economy. As we look to move agriculture forward, ag research will undoubtedly be part of our future success."

Steve Troxler, NC Commissioner of Agriculture

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